

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

DFG Deutsche
Forschungsgemeinschaft

NFDI4Objects

FAIR Data Infrastructure for Material
Remains of Human History

Funding Proposal

Applicant Institution	German Archaeological Institute (DAI)
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DEUTSCHES
ARCHÄOLOGISCHES INSTITUT

Contents

1	General Information	3
1.1	Name of the consortium in English and German:	3
1.2	Summary of the proposal in English and German	3
1.2.1	Summary of the proposal in English	3
1.2.2	Summary of the proposal in English and German	4
1.3	Applicant institution	5
1.4	Spokesperson	5
1.5	Co-applicant institutions	5
1.6	Co-spokespersons	6
1.7	Participants	7
1.8	Names and numbers of the DFG review boards (DFG-Fachkollegien) that reflect the subject orientation of the proposed consortium	18
2	Scope and Objectives	19
2.1	Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, specific aim(s)	19
2.2	Objectives and measuring success	20
3	Consortium	22
3.1	Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest	23
3.2	The consortium within the NFDI	25
3.3	International networking	28
3.4	Organisational structure and viability	29
3.4.1	Organisational Bodies and Community Involvement	29
3.4.2	Viability and community engagement	35
3.4.3	Risk management	38
3.4.4	Operating model	42
4	Research Data Management Strategy	43
4.1	State of the art and needs analysis	43
4.2	Metadata standards	48
4.3	Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance	50
4.4	Services provided by the consortium	52
4.4.1	Community, support and qualification services	52
4.4.2	FAIRification services	53
4.4.3	The N4O service within a broader context	57
5	Work Programme	58
5.1	Task Area 1: Documentation	61
5.1.1	Brief description and aims	61
5.1.2	Goals of TA1	61
5.1.3	Measures and tasks in TA1	62
5.1.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA1	66
5.1.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies	67
5.2	Task Area 2: Collecting	67
5.2.1	Brief description and aims	67
5.2.2	Goals of TA2	68
5.2.3	Measures and tasks in TA2	68
5.2.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA2	72
5.2.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies	73
5.3	Task Area 3: Analytics and Experiments	74
5.3.1	Brief description and aims	74
5.3.2	Goals of TA3	74
5.3.3	Measures and tasks in TA3	75

5.3.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA3	79
5.3.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies .	79
5.4	Task Area 4: Protecting	80
5.4.1	Brief description and aims	80
5.4.2	Goals of TA4	80
5.4.3	Measures and tasks in TA4	81
5.4.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA4	85
5.4.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies .	86
5.5	Task Area 5: Storage, Access and Dissemination	86
5.5.1	Brief description and aims	86
5.5.2	Goals of TA5	87
5.5.3	Measures and tasks in TA5	87
5.5.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA5	92
5.5.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies .	92
5.6	Task Area 6: Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation	93
5.6.1	Brief description and aims	93
5.6.2	Goals of TA6	93
5.6.3	Measures and tasks in TA6	94
5.6.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA6	97
5.6.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies .	97
5.7	Task Area 7: Support and Coordination	98
5.7.1	Brief description and aims	98
5.7.2	Goals of TA7	99
5.7.3	Measures and tasks in TA7	99
5.7.4	Key Performance Indicators for TA7	102
5.7.5	Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies .	103
6	Abbreviations	103
	References	110

1 General Information

1.1 Name of the consortium in English and German:

- NFDI4Objects – Research Data Infrastructure for the Material Remains of Human History
- NFDI4Objects – Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für die materiellen Hinterlassenschaften der Menschheitsgeschichte

1.2 Summary of the proposal in English and German

1.2.1 Summary of the proposal in English

Material remains, hereinafter “objects”, are the only source of knowledge about most of the cultural and biological evolution of humanity. Tools made, monuments built and landscapes shaped by humans bear witness to essential aspects of human history, such as technological development, innovation, human–environment interaction, migration, cultural exchange and transformation. Material remains gain their scientific, historical and cultural significance through multilayered analyses and contextualisation. Their diversity, manifold contexts and complex (object) biographies pose a particular challenge to integrated digital research. The strategy to empower the NFDI4Objects (N4O) Community to integrate and develop solutions that benefit the entire NFDI the initiative has nine objectives:

1. to provide reliable and interoperable data services;
2. to foster awareness of data quality;
3. to improve research data quality;
4. to implement, align and expand standards;
5. to promote professionalism and qualification;
6. to strengthen NFDI-wide cross-cutting topics;
7. to embed N4O into the national and international landscape;
8. to assure collaborative governance and sustainability;
9. to increase the diversity of those actively involved in the consortium.

The N4O work programme will implement these objectives in seven Task Areas (TAs):

TA1 Documentation covers all needs arising from exploring, collecting and documenting primary data sources (of excavations, field projects, artefacts, landscapes, sites, monuments, etc.).

TA2 Collecting provides an integrated research data infrastructure and quality-oriented data management processes that meet the complex requirements of artefact collection contextualisation and provenance research.

TA3 Analytics and Experiments sets up platforms, standards and services for desk-based research, controlled experiments and laboratory-based object analysis.

TA4 Protecting offers applications and data management solutions to meet the complex requirements of protection, conservation, restoration.

TA5 Storage, Access and Dissemination delivers comprehensive technologies and standards for the long-term archiving and reusability of FAIR research data.

TA6 Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation systematically establishes appropriate research data management (RDM) skillsets with tailored qualification concepts and aligns research data and metadata to integrate digital representations of object biographies.

TA7 Support and Coordination manages and develops structure and content for N4O. It coordinates the processes between fields of activity, and ensures the continued scientific and community-driven development of the consortium.

1.2.2 Summary of the proposal in English and German

Materielle Hinterlassenschaften sind die einzige Wissensquelle für den weit größten Teil der kulturellen und biologischen Entwicklung der Menschheit. Von Menschen gefertigte Werkzeuge, gebaute Monumente und geformte Landschaften geben Aufschluss über technologische Entwicklung, Innovation, Wechselbeziehungen zwischen Mensch und Umwelt, Migration, kulturellen Austausch und Wandel. Ihre Aussagekraft erhalten diese Überreste durch vielschichtige Analysen und kontextbezogene Informationen. Ihre Vielfalt, mannigfaltigen Kontexte und komplexen (Objekt-)Biographien stellen dabei eine besondere Herausforderung für digitale Forschungsprozesse dar. Zur Entwicklung von Lösungen durch die NFDI4Objects (N4O) Community, die für die gesamte NFDI von Bedeutung sind, verfolgt die Initiative die folgenden neun Ziele:

1. Zuverlässige und interoperable Datendienste bereitstellen,
2. Bewusstseins für die Relevanz von Datenqualität fördern,
3. Qualität von Forschungsdaten verbessern,
4. Standards anwenden, angleichen und erweitern,
5. Aus- und Weiterbildung fördern,
6. NFDI-weiten Querschnittsthemen stärken,
7. N4O in die nationale und internationale Forschungslandschaft einbetten,
8. Kooperative Governance und Nachhaltigkeit gewährleisten,
9. Diversität der aktiv am Konsortium Beteiligten erhöhen.

Diese Ziele werden durch das Arbeitsprogramm von N4O und sieben Task Areas (TAs) umgesetzt:

TA1 Documentation deckt alle Bedürfnisse aus der Erfassung und Dokumentation primärer Datenquellen (Dokumentation von Ausgrabungen, Feldforschungen, Artefakten, Landschaften, Fundstellen, Denkmälern usw.) ab.

TA2 Collecting baut eine integrierte Forschungsdateninfrastruktur und qualitätsorientierte Datenmanagementprozesse auf, die den Anforderungen der Objektsammlung und Kontextualisierung gerecht werden.

TA3 Analytics and Experiments entwickelt und stellt Plattformen, Standards und Dienstleistungen für Desktop-basierte Forschung, kontrollierte Experimente und laborbasierte Objektanalyse bereit.

TA4 Protecting befasst sich mit Fragen der Datenverwaltung und Anwendungen, die sich auf die Anforderungen von Schutz, Konservierung und Restaurierung konzentrieren.

TA5 Storage, Access and Dissemination stellt umfassende Technologien und Standards für die Langzeitarchivierung und Nachnutzung von Forschungsdaten unter Berücksichtigung der FAIR-Prinzipien bereit.

TA6 Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation fokussiert auf die systematische Etablierung geeigneter FDM-Kenntnisse mit maßgeschneiderten Qualifizierungskonzepten und die Zusammenführung von Forschungsdaten und Metadaten mit dem Ziel integrierter digitaler Repräsentationen von Objektbiographien.

TA7 Support and Coordination verwaltet N4O, organisiert die Prozesse zwischen den TAs und sichert die kontinuierliche wissenschaftliche und gemeinschaftsgetragene Weiterentwicklung des Konsortiums innerhalb der Gesamt-NFDI.

1.3 Applicant institution

Co-spokespersons	Location	Abbreviation
German Archaeological Institute	Podbielskiallee 69–71 14195 Berlin	DAI

1.4 Spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location
Dr. Philipp von Rummel	German Archaeological Institute, Head Office Berlin

1.5 Co-applicant institutions

Co-spokespersons	Location	Abbreviation
Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum – Leibniz Research Museum for Geo-resources	Am Bergbaumuseum 28 44791 Bochum	DBM
Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinland-Pfalz	Schillerstraße 44 – Erthaler Hof 55116 Mainz	GDKE
Kiel University	Christian-Albrechts-Platz 4 24118 Kiel	CAU
Landesamt für Denkmalpflege im Regierungspräsidium Stuttgart	Berliner Str. 12 73712 Esslingen am Neckar	LAD-BW
Continued on next page		

Co-spokespersons	Location	Abbreviation
Mainz University of Applied Sciences	Lucy-Hillebrand-Straße 2 55128 Mainz	MUAS
Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V., here: Max Planck Institute for the History of Science	Boltzmannstraße 22 14195 Berlin	MPIWG
Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum – Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology	Ernst-Ludwig-Platz 2 55116 Mainz	RGZM
Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz	Von-der-Heydt-Str. 16–18 10785 Berlin	SPK
University of Bonn	Heussallee 18–24 53113 Bonn	UBN
Verbundzentrale des GBV	Platz der Göttinger Sieben 1 37073 Göttingen	VZG

1.6 Co-spokespersons

Co-spokespersons	Location	Task Area(s)
David Bibby	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege im Regierungspräsidium Stuttgart, Referat 84.1 – Zentrale Dienste und Denkmalforschung, Fachgebiet Prospektion, Dokumentation und Archäobiowissenschaften	TA1 Documentation
Dr. Matthias Lang	University of Bonn, Bonn Centre for Digital Humanities	TA1 Documentation
Prof. Dr. Alexandra Busch	Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum – Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology	TA2 Collecting
Prof. Dr. Christina Haak	Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz, Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, Generaldirektion	TA2 Collecting
Prof. Dr. Matthias Renz	Kiel University, Department of Computer Science, Archaeoinformatics – Data Science	TA3 Analytics and Experiments
Prof. Dr. Thomas Stöllner	Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum – Leibniz Research Museum for Georesources, Abteilung Forschung	TA3 Analytics and Experiments
Christian Eckmann	Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum – Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology	TA4 Protecting

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Co-spokespersons	Location	Task Area(s)
Dr. Ulrich Himmelmann	Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinland-Pfalz	TA4 Protecting
Henriette Senst	German Archaeological Institute, Head Office Berlin, Zentrale wissenschaftliche Dienste	TA5 Storage, Access and Dissemination
Frank Dürrkohp	Verbundzentrale des GBV, Department Digital Library	TA5 Storage, Access and Dissemination
Prof. Dr. Kai-Christian Bruhn	Mainz University of Applied Sciences, School of Engineering, Department of Geoinformatics and Surveying	TA6 Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation
Dr. Dirk Wintergrün	Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V., here: Max Planck Institute for the History of Science	TA6 Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation

1.7 Participants

ID	Participating institutions	Abbreviation	Location
01	Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz	AdW	Mainz
02	Bavarian State Archaeological Collection Museum for Prehistoric and Early Medieval Archaeology	ASM	Munich
03	Archaeological Museum Hamburg	AMH	Hamburg
04	Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum (CIL), Corpus Nummorum, Inscriptiones Graecae	BBAW	Berlin
05	Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology, German Chapter	CAA-DE	Mainz
06	Curt Engelhorn Centre for Archaeometry	CEZA	Mannheim
07	German Society for Pre- and Protohistory	DGUF	Bonn
08	German National Library, Office for Library Standards	DNB	Frankfurt a.M. / Leipzig
09	German Library Association	DBV	Berlin
10	German Museum Association, Special Interest Group on Documentation	DMB	Berlin
11	Deutscher Verband für Archäologie e.V.	DVA	Berlin
12	University of Tübingen, eScience Centre	UTU	Tübingen
13	FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, eResearch	FIZK	Karlsruhe

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ID	Participating institutions	Abbreviation	Location
14	Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin Graduate School of Ancient Studies	BerGSAS	Berlin
15	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Interdisciplinary Centre for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences	FAU - IZdigital	Erlangen
16	Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Thuringian University and State Library Jena	ThULB	Jena
17	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen	SUB	Göttingen
18	Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities	AdWH	Heidelberg
19	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department of Monitoring and Exploration Technologies	UFZ	Leipzig
20	Herzog Anton Ulrich-Museum, Braunschweig	HAUM	Braunschweig
21	hessenARCHÄOLOGIE, Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Hessen	hA	Wiesbaden
22	University of Applied Sciences und Arts Hildesheim/Holzminen/Göttingen, Hornemann Institute	HAWK	Hildesheim
23	University of Applied Sciences Mittweida, Faculty Applied Computer Sciences & Biosciences	UAS-MW	Mittweida
24	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Institute for the History of Arts and Musicology	JGU-IKM	Mainz
25	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Efficient Computing and Storage Group	JGU-ECSG	Mainz
26	Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany at the Hermann von <i>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Kulturtechnik</i>	HZK	HU Berlin
27	State Office for Heritage Management and Archaeology, State Museum of Prehistory in Halle	LDA-SA	Halle
28	State Office for Heritage Management Saarland	LDA-Saar	Schiffweiler
29	Niedersächsisches Landesmuseum Hannover	NLM	Hannover
30	Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V., here: Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Department of Archaeogenetics in Leipzig	MPI-EVA	Leipzig
31	LVR-Amt für Bodendenkmalpflege im Rheinland	LVR-ABR	Cologne, Bonn, Xanten
32	LWL-Museum für Archäologie und Kultur Westfälisches Landesmuseum	LWL-MfA	Herne
33	Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science	MfN	Berlin

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ID	Participating institutions	Abbreviation	Location
34	Lower Saxony Institute for Historical Coastal Research	NIhK	Wilhelmshaven
35	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Projekt Denkmal Atlas	NLD	Hannover
36	University of Bamberg, Institute for Archaeology, Heritage Conservation and Art History	UBA	Bamberg
37	RWTH Aachen University, Chair of Architectural History	RWTH	Aachen
38	Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Institute of Archaeological Studies	RUB	Bochum
39	Heidelberg University, Heidelberg University Library, Department Publikationsdienste, Propylaeum Specialized Information Service Classics	UBH	Heidelberg
40	Heidelberg University, Heidelberg Centre for Cultural Heritage, Institut für Klassische Archäologie und Byzantinische Archäologie	UHE	Heidelberg
41	Archives of the Bavarian State	GDA	Munich
42	Staatssammlung für Anthropologie München, Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns	SNSB	Munich
43	The Schleswig-Holstein State Museums Foundation Schloss Gottorf, The Archaeological Museum Schloss Gottorf and Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology	ZBSA	Schleswig
44	Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Art Studies and Historical Urban Studies, Chair of Digital Provenance	TUB-DP	Berlin
45	Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Urban and Regional Planning	TUB-IURP	Berlin
46	Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institut für Geschichtswissenschaft	TUBr	Braunschweig
47	Technische Universität Darmstadt, , Department of Architecture, Institute Classical Archaeology	TUD	Darmstadt
48	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie (LDA Thuringia)	LDA Th	Erfurt
49	TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Lab Non-Textual Materials	NTM	Hannover
50	Universität Hamburg, Institut für Archäologie und Kulturgeschichte des antiken Mittelmeerraumes	UHA	Hamburg
51	University of Cologne, Institute for Archaeology, Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory	UzK - Co-DArch-Lab	Cologne
52	University of Cologne, Data Centre for the Humanities and Cologne Centre for eHumanities	UzK - DCH	Cologne

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ID	Participating institutions	Abbreviation	Location
53	University of Cologne, Department for Digital Humanities	UzK - DDH	Cologne
54	Leipzig University, Georg Steindorff Egyptian Museum	UL	Leipzig
55	VARUSSCHLACHT im Osnabrücker Land gGmbH – Museum und Park Kalkriese	VARUS	Bramsche
56	Verband der Landesarchäologien in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland e. V.	VLA	Bonn

01 Academy of Sciences and Literature | Mainz: The Academy is the hosting institution of NFDI4Culture and connects research communities dealing with material and immaterial cultural heritage. The Academy plans to develop and implement digitisation workflows for these collections with Heidelberg University Library and the FID Propylaeum. It will contribute its archeological collections, existing web applications, data models and APIs to the consortium.

02 Bavarian State Archaeological Collection, Museum for Prehistoric and Early Medieval Archaeology: The Collection supports N4O within TA2 to enable data interoperability, exchange and standardisation for collection research.

03 Archaeological Museum Hamburg (AMH): The AMH will contribute its expertise in cataloguing databases, media administration and digitisation workflows to N4O. This includes making resources developed in AMH available to N4O: excavation and surveying software (archaeoDox and Tachy2GIS) and the archaeological standard geodata model NormA to integrate GIS into data management.

04 Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum (CIL), Corpus Nummorum, Inscriptiones Graecae: The CIL will advise on and participate in developing a plan for FAIR archaeology object-related RDM. It will devise a concept and strategy for community-driven development to advance the IANUS-IT recommendations. CIL is actively generating best practices for RDM and developing materials to increase the FAIRification of archaeological data and data literacy. The Corpus Nummorum project is committed to improving data exchange and will coordinate the iconographic thesaurus within TA2. The Inscriptiones Graecae project will facilitate and intensify research data exchange across disciplinary boundaries: this includes defining suitable interfaces within TA2 and helping to build a sustainable portal on Greek epigraphy.

05 Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology, German Chapter (CAA-DE): CAA-DE will support N4O's community-based technical management of conflicts in existing and potential infrastructures and services. CAA will regularly inform its 200+ members from all levels of digital archaeology about N4O, use its platforms, promote a collaborative NFDI and provide their own outreach formats for RDM skills.

06 Curt Engelhorn Centre of Archaeometry (CEZA): The CEZA holds several reference sample datasets, including archaeological metal and the dendrochronological archive with around 50,000 wood samples, and offers their competences in analysing and dating archaeological materials to establish standards and procedures.

07 German Society for Pre- and Protohistory (DGUF): The DGUF is an experienced multiplier for N4O. Since summer 2020, we have been regularly reporting on N4O in the DGUF newsletter, with over 1,800 subscribers. Besides continuing this, the DGUF will play an important role in the continuous monitoring of user feedback from the collector and detector community to N4O on their online services, and support in communicating methodological, technical and legal aspects of citizen science tools. The DGUF will also help to structure and collect needs, expectations and feedback from the professional and lay communities it represents, to adapt and develop services within the N4O Commons. It will mediate and maintain contacts with archaeological excavation firms to integrate this data-generating expert group adequately into N4O services and processes.

08 German National Library, Office for Library Standards (DNB): The DNB vision is to create a reliable, machine-readable linked data network of culture and science, i.e. a cross-NFDI knowledge graph. To achieve this, activities inside NFDI need to be harmonised and integrated with existing standardisation networks. Therefore, the DNB is involved in all humanities-related consortia (N4O, currently NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory and especially Text+).

09 German Library Association (DBV): The German Library Association will contribute the perspective of object provenance research to the methodological and conceptual modelling within TA6. It will support activities in NFDI's cross-cutting topic of provenance data. In N4O, it will support modelling the interdisciplinary research data lifecycle of objects and integrating N4O data. Within TA7 it will support the advisory board to deal with ethical issues. Furthermore, the Kommission Provenienzforschung und Provenienzerschließung (Provenance Research and Development Commission) commits itself to inform its members regularly about N4O, to promote a collaborative NFDI and to use the existing platforms for dissemination.

10 German Museum Association – Special Interest Group on Documentation: The interest group commits itself to communicate topics of N4O, especially from TA2, to its members, to encourage better data exchange and a unified NFDI and to make existing N4O platforms available to its members.

11 Deutscher Verband für Archäologie e.V. (DVA): The DVA is the umbrella organisation of archaeological associations and associated sciences in Germany and confirms its support for N4O. The DVA serves the professional and scientific exchange of its members and the professional, educational and positive public representation of archaeology.

12 University of Tübingen, eScience Centre: As the operator of an institutional repository, the eScience Centre provides N4O with extensive experience in developing and operating repositories, to develop NFDI-compliant data structures and repositories. The eScience Centre can provide digital infrastructures, training and test environments for N4O's research data and prepare them for joint work.

13 FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, eResearch: FIZ Karlsruhe contributes the research data repository and archive RADAR, which is an infrastructural component of the technical backend for baureka.online. It integrates the archive interface developed in M5.1 into this system. FIZ Karlsruhe contributes its expertise to the design and implementation of the discovery system in M5.4 and provides data from baureka.online to the consortium.

14 Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin Graduate School of Ancient Studies (BerGSAS): FU Berlin commits to support summer schools, workshops and lectures/lecture series, to test the standards developed by N4O and apply them in graduate education. Specific content will be taught by N4O members in courses leading to key qualifications, which are mandatory in all doctoral programmes of the BerGSAS. The course content will cover all core topics of digital RDM, assembled in TAs 1–5. Constant contact with the BerGSAS will enable the consortium to learn first-hand about issues that arise in digital RDM during doctoral research, and enable the BerGSAS to help develop instruments that meet these needs. Thus, BerGSAS is involved in all three key stages of measures, namely development, testing and implementation.

15 Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Interdisciplinary Centre for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences (IZdigital): IZdigital contributes its expertise in developing ontologies and data modelling on cultural heritage, computer vision techniques and intensive work with the CIDOC-CRM. It will do this in work meetings, workshops and consultation with the co-applicants, participants and other experts. This helps to achieve the goal of TA6: an integrated data model for object biographies.

16 Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Thuringian University and State Library Jena (ThULB): The ThULB will contribute to constructing and sustainably maintaining repositories, matching and mapping, and generating metadata standards, particularly for museums, archives and university collections. It will offer N4O its entire scientific service portfolio, including metadata and digital asset management and 2D and 3D digitisation.

17 Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Niedersächsische Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Göttingen (SUB): SUB activities cover a wide range of data modelling tasks for cultural heritage and digital humanities projects. Metadata profiles for describing object biographies have been developed in several projects. The SUB is significantly involved in developing and promoting various metadata standards, and contributes all this expertise to N4O.

18 Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities (AdWH): The Research Centre on the Role of Culture in Early Expansion of Humans (ROCEEH) will be primarily involved with to mapping authority files and community-driven vocabularies in the TRAIL. ROCEEH will provide its own specialist thesauri to embed these in a network of diverse subject vocabularies using semantic linking. This will formalise relationships between vocabularies from different fields to enable a multidisciplinary view on digital cultural objects.

19 Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department of Monitoring and Exploration Technologies: The UFZ Department contributes extensive knowledge and experience in the design, implementation and evaluation of geophysical and direct push-based surveys. Its staff provides a direct link to the Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft (DGG, German Geophysics Association), in particular to the Environmental and Engineering Geophysics Working Group, whose concern is the proper and standardised use of near-surface geophysical methods.

20 Herzog Anton Ulrich Museum, Braunschweig (HAUM): The HAUM, with the expertise of its Numismatic Department and Numismatic Collection, was significantly involved in establishing TA2. It will continue to take on leading tasks for TA2 in RDM, quality management, internal and external communication. In addition, the HAUM brings the Digital Numismatic Collection (www.virtuelles-muenzkabinett.de)

into N4O as an important service for digital numismatics research, and will expand this service on a project-related basis.

21 hessenARCHÄOLOGIE, Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Hessen (hA): The hA will contribute its strong international connections plus scientific and technical expertise to N4O . Through long-standing membership of the Archaeology and Information Systems working group (modelling, archiving) of the Association of the State Archaeologists of the Federal Republic of Germany, hA also guarantees exchange with relevant national institutions.

22 University of Applied Sciences und Arts Hildesheim/Holzminden/Göttingen, Hornemann Institute (HAWK): The Hornemann Institute contributes expertise in developing subject-specific, online research data portals and restoration thesauri. It offers content and services such as developing an open access online learning programme, and will recruit contributors and relevant content from institutes and universities across Europe.

23 University of Applied Sciences Mittweida, Faculty Applied Computer Sciences & Biosciences (UAS-MW): The UAS-MW will work on a web-based, distributed infrastructure to make archaeological/anthropological data FAIR, harmonise and manage metadata, and act as a template for other information systems in these domains and in general.

24 Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Institute for the History of Arts and Musicology (IKM): The IKM intends to contribute its expertise from its master's programme, "Digital Methods in the Humanities and Cultural Studies", provide conceptual support for the creation of open teaching material, contribute to qualification events, and offer training itself. It will work on the definition of a multifaceted competence framework and help to define qualification profiles.

25 Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Efficient Computing and Storage Group (ECSG): The ECSG provides services and capacities of JGU Data Center (ZDV) regarding storage, archiving and user administration (Shibboleth) and offers backup for the operation of services. ZDV accompanies the development of N4O's service portfolio as a counterpart for the integration of overarching solutions within the NFDI and mediates integration into other consortia.

26 Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany at the Helmholtz-Zentrum für Kulturtechnik: The Coordination Centre will contribute to the TRAIL on RDM in museums and collections. With other partners, the Centre will analyse the landscape of existing (metadata) standards, vocabularies, ontologies, interfaces and services used within German university collections.

27 State Office for Heritage Management and Archaeology, State Museum of Prehistory in Halle (LDA Saxony-Anhalt): With its partners, the LDA Halle will support the consortium to develop cataloguing databases, especially the finds databases and media administration.

28 State Office for Heritage Management Saarland (LDA Saarland): The LDA Saarland will contribute to TA4, as its restoration workshop is only responsible for the care of excavation finds, all aspects of collection management and future presentations. The LDA will help to ensure that digital RDM reflects all challenges related to cultural heritage, renovation and restoration in an interdisciplinary manner.

29 Niedersächsisches Landesmuseum Hannover: The WorldMuseum will be responsible for indexing databases within the N4O, provide test data and incorporate the experiences of the last few years in this field.

30 Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V., here: Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology (MPI-EVA), Department of Archaeogenetics: Beyond the planned TRAILS, the Department of Archaeogenetics will provide input for consortium-wide discussions. It will also provide resources for developing public data frameworks to enable effective querying and implementation of genetic data from archaeological research perspectives, and vice versa.

31 LVR-Amt für Bodendenkmalpflege im Rheinland (LVR-ABR): The LVR-ABR will generate primary data from excavations and other measures, and contribute these to N4O. It will develop and establish standards for documenting archaeological sites and will recommend workflows for selecting and post-processing existing digital site and feature data. The LVR-ABR will work towards creating basic interfaces and standards to support online services for the exchange of archaeological site and feature data.

32 LWL-Museum für Archäologie und Kultur, Westfälisches Landesmuseum: The museum will provide archaeological data for TA2 to develop, evaluate and adapt data collection systems. Currently, the LWL Archaeological Museum is planning to release a webGIS, which could be developed in consultation with TA2. The museum is committed to supporting N4O with both personnel and data resources.

33 Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science (MfN): The MfN has co-developed the TRAIL on interoperability of archaeological and natural history object data. MfN will contribute to the TRAIL with its expertise in RDM regarding natural history collection objects, their socio-historical contexts and their provenance. MfN will provide use cases, requirements analysis and the formal specification of the model developed in the TRAIL.

34 Lower Saxony Institute for Historical Coastal Research (NlhK): The NlhK contributes to the development of digital RDM by means of standardised excavation and drilling documentation or its transfer for digital evaluation (TA1). NlhK is involved in developing GIS tools to process this data and is the current location of ArboDat, the program package for botanical macro remains (TA3). The research excavations and courses at NlhK provide an infrastructure in which the measures can be tested and evaluated extensively.

35 Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege (NLD), Projekt Denkmal Atlas: The NLD contributes its expertise in documenting monument data in archaeology, building and art monument preservation and restoration to TA5. Furthermore, it provides data via a portal and open OAI and OGC-API interfaces with the Niedersachsen atlas of monuments.

36 University of Bamberg, Institute for Archaeology, Heritage Conservation and Art History: The University of Bamberg research group of Digital Geoarchaeology and the Centre for Heritage Conservation Studies and Techniques (KDWT, research groups on Digital Technologies in Heritage Conservation and Historic Building Research/Building History) contribute significant expertise to the consortium in geophysical techniques, remote sensing, 3D digitisation, 2D and 3D modelling, semantic modelling, authority files and community-driven vocabularies, digital description routines and analysis methods, as well as teaching.

37 RWTH Aachen University, Chair of Architectural History: The Chair of Architectural History will contribute its expertise in developing the research data portal baureka.online. In this context, it will promote the work of the consortium to the communities of historic building research, monument preservation and architectural history. In addition, with its subject-specific expertise, the Chair will support the development of interfaces, mapped thesauri and data services through TA4.

38 Ruhr-Universität Bochum (RUB), Institute of Archaeological Studies: The RUB Institute of Archaeological Studies, with the Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum – Leibniz Research Museum for Geo-resources, will contribute its experience from digitising numerous field projects to develop digital standards and provide infrastructure for N4O.

39 Heidelberg University, Heidelberg University Library (UBH), Department Publikationsdienste, Propylaeum Specialized Information Service Classics: The specialist information service for Classical Studies, Propylaeum, with its ePublishing service represented by Dr. Maria Effinger, offers a complete technical infrastructure for open access digital publication for Classical Studies. The UBH provides advisory services (second level support) to the N4O Community on questions of data publication and data archiving.

40 Heidelberg University, Heidelberg Centre for Cultural Heritage, Institut für Klassische Archäologie und Byzantinische Archäologie: In TA2, the HCCH will contribute to N4O in several ways. It supports the project by processing and integrating results of the project into its E-Learning-Platform NumiScience.de as a reference implementation. By actively using it within university courses, it supports knowledge transfer of the workflow to students and next generation curators. Furthermore, the HCCH offers N4O the use of its graffiti database, enabling innovative semantic modelling on fuzziness and wobbliness. The HCCH will also support the coin finds database, AFE4HD and the documentation of the University of Heidelberg Numismatic collection in N4O.

41 Archives of the Bavarian State (GDA): The GDA contributes extensive expertise in digital archiving and data curation to N4O. As a contracted service, GDA also provides a generalised XML interface, developed within TA5, and participates in recording, specifying and implementing other relevant interfaces. In TA1 and TA5 GDA contributes to evaluation of data worth preserving, and links to its similar commitments in NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Biodiversity and FAIRagro.

42 Staatssammlung für Anthropologie München, Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns (SNSB): The SNSB will contribute its expertise in anthropology and archaeozoology and relative to the databases AnthroBook and Ossobook database, which have been specifically developed to store and process anthropological and archaeozoological data.

43 The Schleswig-Holstein State Museums Foundation Schloss Gottorf, The Archaeological Museum Schloss Gottorf and Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology (ZBSA): The ZBSA's archaeozoological contribution to TA3 is a basis for more fruitful dialogue between archaeozoology and disciplines such as history, archaeobotany and archaeology. It provides N4O with access to a large amount of digital primary data from archaeozoological investigations of animal bones from Late Glacial to Early Modern sites, mostly in the northern German Iowlands, and a comprehensive data collection of archaeological animal remains from all over Europe.

44 Technische Universität Berlin (TUB), Institute of Art Studies and Historical Urban Studies, Chair of Digital Provenance: Prof. Dr. Meike Hopp commits herself to mediate regularly between N4O and the community of provenance researchers. As she is already involved in NFDI4Culture, she will help with knowledge transfer between consortia. She will support N4O to introduce standards for name authority files on previous owners and sellers, and to set up and run an ethical advisory board.

45 Technische Universität Berlin (TUB), Institute of Urban and Regional Planning: The TUB provides documentation and collaborates in consolidating and simplifying existing metadata standards for documenting objects (within TA1). The TUB provides a work package on historical building research, which deals with dating partial objects in the context of building archaeology as a model case within the TRAIL.

46 Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institut für Geschichtswissenschaft: The NUMiD network at the TU Braunschweig is actively involved in N4O (especially in TA2), and contributes with its quality management system, offers its competencies in continuing professional development and knowledge transfer, mediates between N4O and its network partners, and develops its services on a project-specific basis in close coordination with the Universitätsbibliothek Braunschweig (Braunschweig University Library) and the Herzog Anton Ulrich Museum, Braunschweig.

47 Technische Universität Darmstadt (TUD), Department of Architecture, Institute Classical Archaeology: The TUD contributes extensive experience in archaeology and archaeological building research. This includes implementing field projects and developing digital reconstruction methods. Within the working group Objekte.Digitalität.Hochschule, it will support measures in TA6 regarding innovative teaching methods and digital archaeology.

48 Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie (LDA Thuringia): The Thuringian LDA contributes its expertise in the acquisition, management and presentation of object and finds data in archaeology, the professional supervision of a DAM and its role as professional coordinator of the KENOM network (cooperative indexing and use of object data of coin collections), especially in the RDM of coin finds.

49 TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Lab Non-Textual Materials (NTM): The NTM contribution is the TIB AV portal, an open and reliable infrastructure for indexing and hosting audiovisual media, and its extensive expertise in this field. It will contribute its expertise in the automatic processing and analysis of image data, including technical and descriptive requirements of research data, to the work meetings and workshops, and to the quality assurance of the outcomes and documents developed within TA6.

50 Universität Hamburg, Institut für Archäologie und Kulturgeschichte des antiken Mittelmeerraumes: The Institute for Ancient Mediterranean Archaeology and Cultural History will advise on developing tools to digitalise the laboratory workflow from object sampling strategy to joint interpretation of analysis data. With TA1, the Institute will help catalogue and develop standards and tools for geophysical prospection. It will support the efforts to formulate best practices for RDM and to develop training concepts. The Institute will advise on and participate in developing a discipline-specific plan for FAIR object-related RDM. It will help devise a concept and strategy to promote the IANUS-IT recommendations in the community. The institute will actively mediate between expert and community clusters, and support the establishment and running of an advisory board to deal with ethical issues.

51 University of Cologne, Institute for Archaeology, Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory (CoDArchLab): The CoDArchLab will contribute to TA6 to define competence frameworks and qualification profiles, catalogue existing courses and trainee programmes, plan qualification and training events and transfer knowledge between RDM professionals.

52 University of Cologne, Data Centre for the Humanities (DCH) and Cologne Centre for eHumanities: The DCH will provide advice for and participate in the development of a discipline-specific research data management plan for object-related research data, which will also aid in advancing the IANUS-IT recommendations and devise a concept and a strategy for a community driven further development. It actively supports the efforts for generating best practices for the creation and processing of research data as well as the development of materials to increase the FAIRification of archaeological data and data literacy. The DCH will also contribute to the design of open and interoperable interfaces for long-term archiving systems.

53 University of Cologne, Department for Digital Humanities: The Department for Digital Humanities supports the development of tools for managing and reasoning of fuzziness and wobbliness in research collections (TA2). The department plans to involve MA and/or doctoral students in this process within the consortium.

54 Leipzig University (UL), Georg Steindorff Egyptian Museum: The Georg Steindorff Egyptian Museum participates in monthly meetings of its Egyptology thesaurus working group to analyse the datasets of the databases currently in use. With the other museums, it will produce vocabularies and for trilingual (German/English/French) data on ancient Egyptian collections (TA2). The museum will also create authority files on persons/corporations of the respective institutional history and object provenance. Based on this standard data, with the computer centre of Leipzig University, the museum will work out a workflow for the metadata acquisition of Egyptian collections, to provide a good template for other collections and, long-term, to enable better data exchange and reuse.

55 VARUSSCHLACHT im Osnabrücker Land gGmbH – Museum und Park Kalkriese: The museum and park at Kalkriese and the VZG are developing an app to digitally record prospective finds in the field and feed them into the existing find database. The medium term aim is to record all processes of find acquisition, processing and analysis in an open access database network. The museum will contribute to N40 with this experience in the TRAIL to design and produce an excavation database – and to test it in practice.

56 Verband der Landesarchäologien in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland e.V. (VLA): The VLA commits itself to inform its members regularly about N40, to promote a collaborative NFDI and to use existing platforms for dissemination (M5.5). The VLA will exchange experience regarding the activities, problems and standards of archaeological heritage management and contribute to coordinating and representing common interests in the consortium (TA7).

ID	Participating individuals	Institution, location
57	Dr. Karsten Tolle	Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main
58	Prof. Dr. Johannes Lipps	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Institut für Altertumswissenschaften
59	Prof. Dr. Janoscha Kreppner	University of Münster, Institut für Altorientalistik und Vorderasiatische Archäologie

57 Dr. Karsten Tolle: Dr. Tolle will contribute his expertise in semantic modelling, data quality, fuzziness and wobbliness, and iconography and commits to participate in TA2 and these thematic areas.

58 Prof. Dr. Johannes Lipps: Prof. Dr. Lipps will accompany the initiative in all aspects of digital data collection and visualisation of excavation results, surveys and above all architectural documentation. He will integrate the concerns of N4O, especially TA1, into this teaching and introduce interested students to the work of NFDI.

59 Prof. Dr. Janoscha Kreppner: Prof. Dr. Kreppner, in close cooperation with the Network Archaeology Diagonal at the University of Münster, will contribute to N4O his expertise in developing digital standards from ongoing field research with purely digital data collection and in processing field research and excavation documentation. With TA6, he will develop university teaching and internships.

1.8 Names and numbers of the DFG review boards (DFG-Fachkollegien) that reflect the subject orientation of the proposed consortium

Review Board 101 Ancient Cultures, with relations to:

- 106 Social and Cultural Anthropology, Non-European Cultures, Jewish Studies and Religious Studies
- 201 Basic Biological and Medical Research
- 202 Plant Sciences
- 203 Zoology
- 205 Medicine
- 207 Agriculture, Forestry and Veterinary Medicine
- 314 Geology and Palaeontology
- 315 Geophysics and Geodesy
- 316 Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry
- 317 Geography
- 410 Construction Engineering and Architecture

2 Scope and Objectives

2.1 Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, specific aim(s)

Material objects are a fundamental source of knowledge about the cultural and biological evolution of humanity. Tools made, monuments built and landscapes shaped by humans bear witness to essential aspects of human history, such as human-environment interaction, innovation and technological development, knowledge transfer and exchange, social and ritual practices, migration, or social, cultural and ecological change. In N4O the term “object” is used to cover the entire spectrum of traces and material legacies of past human activities preserved in soil archives or collections: artefacts, architecture, archaeological finds and anthropogenically shaped landscapes, as well as biological or ecological remains. This makes archaeological objects an outstanding source documenting and understanding the human past.

The findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of research data representing these objects is crucial for both the humanities and sciences, to understand human evolution, the development of societies and the Anthropocene. These objects are our only source for reconstructing global human evolution and history for most of the last three million years. By focusing on material objects to document and understand the human past, N4O not only makes an outstanding contribution to the research data ecosystem, it also bridges the gap between humanities and sciences and provides relevant data to a wide range of disciplines.

The scope of N4O covers communities that work with and on the material remains of human history. The initiative is centred on object-specific research methods in a broad, multidisciplinary environment. The N4O Community represents institutions, organisations and individuals across archaeology and anthropology, the biosciences (anthropology, archaeobotany, archaeozoology, archaeogenetics, paleopathology) and geosciences (geoarchaeology, geophysics, geology, mineralogy and petrology, physical geography, landscape archaeology, paleoclimatology), with the archaeosciences and archaeometry, as well as buildings research, restoration and archaeological conservation.

The consortium comprises universities, non-university research institutions, cultural heritage management offices for the German federal states (Landesdenkmalämter), museums, scientific collections and infrastructure providers, research groups, individual academics, and commercial service providers. Numerous professional and voluntary associations and citizen scientists provide invaluable support to N4O, including a considerable amount of data. Research methods in N4O encompass the collection, exploration, analysis and documentation of primary data sources (excavations, artefacts, ecofacts, archaeological sites and monuments etc.) on site and in repositories, collections and laboratories. Research on objects includes methods of conservation, restoration, protection and provenance, as well as controlled experiments and analysis of combined data.

The various disciplines and institutions represented by N4O are united by common needs. Objects pose a particular challenge to digital research, due to the diversity of data types, contexts and complex (object) biographies. Hundreds of millions of objects are stored in scientific collections and the volume of data associated with them is growing continuously. This constant growth of data and the fragility of the objects’ materiality and contexts underline the need for sustainable research data services and infrastructures. Questions about the development of humankind can only be answered if primary research data are available and integrated from different sources.

N4O thus aims to promote access to interoperable data and to provide standardised and easy-to-use solutions to combine inherent data of an object with its provenance, its association with other finds, its sociocultural embedding, and the complex transformation processes it may have undergone (object biography). This challenge is ubiquitous in N4O, but not restricted to this community. Thus, N4O provides unique multidisciplinary expertise in digital RDM related to physical objects. This meets a major need of the entire scientific community and contributes significantly to the overall goal of the NFDI.

The infrastructure created by N4O will support knowledge transfer beyond research, e.g. for museum outreach and education, or for authorities to prevent illicit trade in cultural objects. N4O forms a unique initiative to make existing but heterogeneous data management solutions available sustainably.

The consortium aims to achieve a significant increase in community awareness of FAIR data principles, compared to the current awareness identified in the N4O survey. Training and qualification options will enable a constantly growing community to generate FAIR data. To achieve this, N4O will not only build bridges between the humanities and sciences. It must also bridge different digital strategies between federal states inside Germany and connect them internationally. In this process, N4O aims to anchor FAIR RDM more deeply in the community by collaborative governance, consulting, education and vocational training services. This will promote digital transformation and cultural change in the community. N4O also aims to adapt, promote and implement both the TRUST principles for maintaining the trustworthiness of digital repositories and the CARE principles in terms of RDM.

From day one, N4O will tailor data services to the community's specific needs to create standards, authority files and community-driven vocabularies, and ensure long-term availability of data. Based on its position between the humanities and sciences, N4O will lay a broad foundation for RDM in other disciplines and thus promote the generation of new knowledge on a global scale.

2.2 Objectives and measuring success

Based on the current state of RDM in the N4O research landscape and on the needs that have been identified by surveys, N4O pursues the following nine key objectives:

- 1) Provide reliable and interoperable data services for all stages of the FAIR data lifecycle: custom-developed software that is widely used in the community, is sustainable and developed in line with community needs through integration into the N4O Commons (see section 3.4). The services built on this will not just enable broad (re)use of research data but will also allow data to be linked across federal states and institutions, thus making data much more findable, accessible and interoperable.
- 2) Foster awareness of data quality as the central to RDM and promote it as an integral part of research on material remains of human history. All TAs of N4O will work on this objective, but TA6 and TA7 have key roles regarding information and dissemination.
- 3) Improve research data quality through FAIR standards and workflows. N4O will make a steadily growing amount of FAIR data available in its research domain. The consortium bases all its work on ethical responsibility in digital RDM. The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance and other initiatives to formulate guidelines for collecting and sharing digital data will be thoroughly discussed and N4O guidelines developed. N4O will also produce a systematic overview of legal and regulatory constraints on the development of consistent RDM.
- 4) Implement, align and expand data standards including metadata models, authority files and community-driven vocabularies, geodata and chronological data, as well as tools to transform, enrich and align data. The consortium will first map all these, then remove many obstacles that unnecessarily isolate data and present an ideal data processing workflow from fieldwork (excavation), collecting and storage to analyses, experiments and restoration processes (TA1–4). This will generate significant new insights

from traditional hermeneutics, data-driven methods, statistical reasoning, spatial analysis, machine learning and pattern recognition. All the new standards, specifications, procedures and guidelines will be integrated into the N4O Commons and continuously improved by the community.

5) Promote professionalism and qualification to increase data literacy and RDM capacities. The education and training materials produced for the N4O Commons (TA6) will not only contribute to embedding RDM and data literacy in university curricula but also strengthen tertiary education and vocational training at all levels. This will contribute to much-needed cultural change, as well as providing training for future generations of researchers and professionals. TA6 will coordinate the consortium's training and qualification activities, based on expertise nurtured in TAs 1–4. TA7 will support this process in terms of organisation. Researchers will be empowered by the activities of N4O to manage their FAIR data. In the near future, this will play an increasingly important role in evaluating academic performance, in addition to traditional publications. N4O is committed to making data competencies a central aspect in career planning.

6) Strengthen cross-cutting topics in collaboration with the entire NFDI with metadata standards and vocabularies, interoperable services, ethical and legal aspects specific to the N4O Community, as well as specific training and qualification measures. The N4O Community will focus on developing methods and procedures at the interface between the sciences and the humanities (particularly in TA3). N4O has signed the Berlin-Leipzig Declaration on Cross-Cutting Topics and works closely on harmonising these topics with neighbouring initiatives (particularly in TA7), including three other initiatives from the humanities (NFDI4Culture, Text+, NFDI4Memory) with which N4O has signed a Memorandum of Understanding.

7) Embed N4O into the national and international landscape. Research on the material remains of human history is not limited to regional or national boundaries. On the contrary, transnational cooperation is essential for quality-driven research. The members of N4O have already built a strong international network (see section 3.3) that will be expanded to strengthen interoperability with national and international data repositories and services, including the European Open Science Cloud. TA7 will coordinate international implementation and will provide harmonised access to existing services. This will enable effective data communication between different federal states and institutions. N4O can contribute this experience of interdisciplinary data management to the whole NFDI. It is also open to ideas from other areas of the humanities, natural and material sciences. Active and integrative networking with other NFDI consortia ensures that N4O will not generate data silos solely for object-related data.

8) Assure collaborative governance and sustainability by (1) continuing systematic surveys addressing general matters pertaining to the N4O Community, (2) collecting and analysing user feedback on (the quality of) services and measures in N4O, (3) recording and analysing anonymised usage statistics and usage patterns of supplied services (TA7), (4) monitoring the progress of the N4O Commons in relation to the work programme. In addition to insights gained by other NFDI consortia into user behaviour and compliance, the results of these monitoring processes will be used to iteratively improve the quality and effectiveness of our measures, as well as to actively counteract misdirected developments.

9) Develop and implement strong measures that will increase the diversity of active members of the consortium and ensure gender balance on advisory boards and working groups. Success will be measured through periodical surveys that will show developments since the most recent N4O survey.

3 Consortium

ID	Involvement of participants in other NFDI consortia
01	Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz is Co-applicant in NFDI4Culture and Text+
04	Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Inscriptiones Graecae is participating in Text+ and NFDI4Culture
08	German National Library, Office for Library Standards is participating in NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory and Text+
10	Deutscher Museumsbund e. V., Fachgruppe Dokumentation is participating in NFDI4Culture
12	University of Tübingen, eScience Center is participating in DataPLANT, NFDI4Earth, Text+, DAPHNE4NFDI, NFDI4Memory, TheoReS, NFDI4Immuno, DeBioData, NFDI-Neuro and GHGA
13	FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure is participating in NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Agri, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Chem, MaRDI, InnoMatSafety, NFDI4Memory, MatWerk, NFDIxCS and NFDI4Phys
15	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen, Interdisciplinary Centre for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences (IZdigital) is participating in NFDI4Culture
17	Göttingen State and University Library (SUB) is participating in Text+, NFDI4BioDiversity, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Earth and NFDI4Memory
19	Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung gGmbH (UFZ) is participating in NFDI4BioDiversity, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Bioimage and NFDI4Agri
23	Mittweida University of Applied Sciences is participating in NFDI4Health
25	Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Efficient Computing and Storage Group is participating in PUNCH4NFDI, NFDIxCS, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Culture and NFDI4Memory
26	Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany at the Helmholtz-Zentrum für Kulturtechnik der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin is participating in NFDI4Culture
33	Museum für Naturkunde – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science is participating in NFDI4BioDiversity, NFDI4Culture and NFDI4Earth
35	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege is participating in NFDI4Ing
39	Heidelberg University, Universitätsbibliothek Heidelberg is participating in NFDI4Culture
41	Archives of the Bavarian State are participating in NFDI4BioDiversity, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Memory and FAIRagro
42	Staatssammlung für Anthropologie und Paläoanatomie is participating NFDI4BioDiversity
44	Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Art History, Chair of Digital Provenance is participating in NFDI4Culture
Continued on next page	

Figure 1: N4O Co-applicant institutions.

ID	Involvement of participants in other NFDI consortia
01	Academy of Sciences and Literature Mainz is Co-applicant in NFDI4Culture and Text+
46	Technische Universität Braunschweig, University Library is participating in NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Cat and NFDI4Chem
47	Technical University of Darmstadt, Fachgebiet Klassische Archäologie, FB Architektur is participating in NFDI4Ing, Text+ and NFDI4cat
53	TIB – Leibniz Information Center for Science and Technology is participating in NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Phys, NFDI4Microbiota, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Earth, FAIRmat, NFDI4Mobility and MetadataTools4NFDI
51-53	University of Cologne, Archäologisches Institut, Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory, Data Centre for the Humanities, and the Department for Digital Humanities are participating in NFDI4Culture, Text+ and NFDI4Memory
54	Leipzig University is also involved in NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory and Text+

3.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

Since 2018, the N4O initiative has been developed in a comprehensive bottom-up process. More than 100 institutions and community members came together in physical and online meetings to identify specific needs and to shape the structure and the working programme of N4O. The structural design developed during the application phase has already proved its operational efficiency and will be continued during the funding phase.

Figure 2: Timeline of key dates in development of N4O.

With 11 co-applicants and 59 participants, N4O represents a significant body of research communities and the broad range of stakeholders with a focus on objects and their contexts. The participating institutions, encompassing the whole institutional and disciplinary range of the German archaeological community, share common RDM needs. Cross-disciplinary cooperation is a central concern of N4O, which bridges the sciences and humanities and forges links within and beyond the professional community.

The diversity of stakeholder requirements was identified in a series of surveys, the two most recent N4O conducted itself.¹ The first N4O survey² was directed towards the entire community; the second survey focused on early career researchers³. We also asked for user stories, and received over 100.⁴ This enabled us to prioritise within the work programme and develop the composition of the consortium. N4O is an open and community-driven consortium: N4O plans various incentives to stimulate new ideas and to enlarge and diversify the community participating in NFDI (see section 3.4).

In response to the identified needs, N4O collaboratively developed the work plan for the proposal submitted in October 2020. In the DFG review process, the expert panel noted that the N4O initiative is a strong applicant with very good preparation and digital infrastructures, and that modern, multidisciplinary archaeologies and their neighbouring disciplines need representation in the NFDI. However, the reviewers advised that we (a) give more weight to university research, (b) collaborate with other consortia, (c) present our plans more clearly and (d) demonstrate more strongly how the community will be involved.

To respond to these recommendations, we held a series of (largely virtual) plenary meetings and workshops, resulting in detailed adjustment of the work plan. The significance of university research and transfer of funds to the university participants is clarified in the measures and tasks. Collaboration with other consortia is more specific (e.g. section 3.2) and services are explained more clearly throughout.

A new component was designed to better explain community involvement in all its forms. Task-Related Activities for the Implementation and Launch of services (TRAILS) show how aspects of the N4O work programme will be implemented. They were prepared within the community in an open call for proposals and are published online.⁵ The TRAILS are individual model projects and case studies (see section 5) to specify the TAs. The three-month process to formulate the TRAILS (April-August 2021) has proven

¹ Guntram Geser and Selhofer 2014; Heinrich et al. 2015; Geser, Niccolucci, and Richards 2019; Schmidt et al. 2020.

² Schmidt et al. 2020.

³ Publication in preparation.

⁴ <https://osf.io/4t29e/wiki/User%20Stories/>.

⁵ TRAILS online: <https://www.nfdi4objects.net/index.php/arbeitsprogramm/trails/>.

Figure 3: Distribution of N4O co-applicants and participants by type of institution and location.

Figure 4: Schematic timeline of the different phases of the N4O consortium work.

and further strengthened the already existing commitment of the community and the engagement of the participants.

To ensure flexibility and openness to innovation, N4O’s work is divided into five phases (fig. 4). After a three-month build-up, during which the collaborative working and communication tools and processes are established (phase 1), in a two-year phase the TAs are set in motion and the TRAILS are brought to life (phase 2). After 2.5 years of N4O, which coincides with the end of the funding of the first-round NFDI consortia, a three-month interim evaluation is planned (phase 3). Based on this, the consortium can adjust its structures and processes; more model projects will run for two years in a second, openly tendered TRAIL phase (phase 4). The TRAILS will expand the community actively involved in N4O, not least by providing flexible funds so that resource-constrained members can contribute their expertise. In a final consolidation phase (phase 5), working and proven structures will be transformed into sustainable long-term solutions.

3.2 The consortium within the NFDI

Since 2018, N4O has been in dialogue with other NFDI consortia to advance cooperation, minimise overlap and enhance complementarities. This included participation in a series of workshops entitled Research-driven Research Infrastructures for the Humanities

and Cultural Studies in Germany.⁶ N4O is institutionally interlinked via its partners with several NFDI consortia and initiatives (see section 3.1). Building on the results of the abovementioned workshops, four NFDI initiatives – N4O with NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory and Text+ – in the humanities have formed a memorandum group⁷ open to all related disciplines (fig. 5). The four initiatives will coordinate continuous development in complementary fields and integrate common concerns into the NFDI. The collaboration is described in a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), which is open to be signed by further initiatives (version 2 in September 2020).⁸ Four of the NFDI cross-cutting topics⁹ were identified where members can share expertise to develop services to benefit the whole NFDI: (a) metadata, authority files and community-driven vocabularies, (b) provenance, (c) rights and ethics, and (d) data literacy and qualification. In recent months, the group has focused on how best to bring its strengths to the NFDI.¹⁰ N4O is a signatory of the Berlin-Leipzig Declaration on Cross-Cutting Topics in the NFDI,¹¹ and will contribute to Data Commons, making a significant contribution to interdisciplinary research within the whole NFDI. N4O will share expertise and practical experience with other NFDI consortia in the following areas:

Metadata, authority files and community-driven vocabularies: make available overarching standards, such as chronologies (TA1–5) or analytical procedures (TA3), and the steadily growing N4O Commons (see section 3.4).

Provenance: N4O as a whole and TA2 in particular can contribute to the debates on restitution and postcolonialism within and beyond NFDI through its experience with provenance studies, object biographies and data stories to show international historical connections in finding, acquisition, smuggling or purchase and transfer of cultural goods.

Rights and ethics: N4O is committed to promoting and applying the FAIR and CARE principles to data in all disciplines by developing legal and ethical guidelines. Participants of N4O have many years of international experience, which makes us aware of the tensions between the FAIR and CARE principles and societies with diverging views on data sharing. Building on this, N4O can help to avoid the misunderstandings a national data infrastructure can cause in the context of international research projects.

Qualification and data literacy: In TA6, with other NFDI consortia and in consultation with the edutrain section of the NFDI e.V., N4O will develop training and qualifications, and make FAIR OER available on the N4O Commons and to the entire NFDI. A number of N4O members in archaeoinformatics and digital heritage management already maintain relevant services.

FAIRification: In Germany, data relevant to N4O is mainly produced by public authorities, research and educational institutions. Members are thus experienced in integrating FAIR data management across different sectors.¹² Supporting citizen science and engaging the public plays a key role in TA4 and can strengthen the general NFDI efforts in these areas.

Data, service and software quality management and assurance: The consortium brings together partners with extensive, proven expertise in sustainable and agile software development (e.g. DAI, VZG, GDKE) and in data integration processes across

⁶ <https://forschungsinfrastrukturen.de>.

⁷ Brünger-Weilandt et al. 2020.

⁸ Brünger-Weilandt et al. 2020.

⁹ Ebert et al. 2021.

¹⁰ See for example Geisteswissenschaftliches Forum NFDI (<https://nfdi.hypotheses.org/>).

¹¹ Bierwirth et al. 2020.

¹² e.g. in the BMBF-funded project EcoDM – Ökosystem Datenmanagement, the DAI is responsible for the public sector.

Figure 5: Cooperation of the humanities NFDI-initiatives and their communities.

the humanities and sciences, regions and (federal) states, local and international regulations, that extend into science diplomacy. This expertise, expanded in M7.4, can benefit the entire NFDI.

Search and interoperability solutions: The TAs will guarantee a steadily growing volume of available FAIR archaeology data. With the MoU we will work on interoperability solutions, to make our data available to other disciplines, especially in the humanities. The research data in N4O is made available via a knowledge base with standardised interfaces for integration into central NFDI services or discovery solutions of other NFDI consortia.

In addition to the humanities NFDI-initiatives, N4O has been proactive to exchange with further consortia, particularly from the sciences:

Archaeology has a close relationship to the geosciences, since much of its research methodology is based on geoscientific methods and knowledge. N4O works closely with NFDI4Earth, which integrates common analytical methods and shares research questions from the sciences and the humanities, to exchange knowledge and to address overlapping topics: geochemical analysis and geodetic modelling. The consortia will coordinate the involvement of local, institutional RDM offices and the development of competence profiles and qualification measures. In this partnership, we offer expertise in data models for chronological concepts. Together, we plan to develop joint use cases to implement specific projects for knowledge exchange.

Due to the extensive botanical and zoological data relating to finds and their contexts in archaeological research, N4O has a close relationship to biodiversity and ecosystem research and has thus initiated close exchanges with NFDI4BioDiversity. We will work together on the archaeobotanical database ArboDat+, which will be integrated into the Research Data Commons (RDC) of the Common Infrastructures section of the NFDI Association. This multi-cloud-based infrastructure, entitled FAIR Data Spaces Project, is jointly being developed by NFDI and GAIA-X and a number of NFDI consortia, including NFDI4BioDiversity. RDC will enable uniform access to data, software and computer resources as well as sovereign data exchange and collaborative work. This integration and the associated connection to PANGAEA, will ensure the long-term sustainability of ArboDat+.

Agricultural science according to NFDI4Agri covers a heterogeneous field of research disciplines that are also relevant for N4O, e.g. soil science and near-surface geophysics. Consequently, N4O seeks to establish a close exchange with FAIRagro. N4O has agreed

with FAIRagro to participate in joint meetings to ensure an exchange of experience in RDM and for mutual learning. This will take place in FAIRagro Task Area 2 "Community involvement and networking". N4O will participate in the "Data Stewards Networks Corners" at the FAIRagro Community Summits as well as in the "FAIRagro Data Stewards Network Meetings". In addition, N4O will regularly exchange with FAIRagro and NFDI4Earth on how to optimise, develop and synergise community support through the helpdesk.

Genetics is important in both medicine and archaeology; it serves as a bridge between N4O and the German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) initiative in the NFDI. N4O also maintains close contact with the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) that is currently the central place for storing and accessing human genotype data. N4O will contribute human archaeogenetics data generated in Germany to be integrated into the GHGA-EGA node. This will ensure FAIR principles for archaeogenetics data and enable cross-disciplinary analyses between modern medical research and ancient genomics.

3.3 International networking

For a long time, the institutions and individuals within N4O have been collaborating closely on RDM with networks, partners and colleagues around the globe. Many members of N4O are active in Computer Applications & Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) International and participate in the leading international projects on standards, such as Ariadne+, CARARE, Pelagios, NAHAN and the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC). Many N4O actors are engaged in creating the global network LinkedPasts that links the growing body of historical datasets as Linked Open Data (LOD) to the community of researchers who create and use them.

The main applicant's own RDM infrastructure, iDAI.world, is used all over the world. To create it, DAI drew on experience in conducting research projects worldwide and discussing standards internationally and according to national requirements in its host countries. The DAI has also close links to PeriodO, the Initiative Open Context (for which the DAI infrastructure hosts a mirror website), and the American School at Athens (Bruce Hartzler), whose excavations documentation system idig provided a basis for iDAI.field2. The DAI coordinates the community-based DFG project IANUS (Forschungsdatenzentrum Archäologie und Altertumswissenschaften), which collaborates with the British Archaeology Data Service (ADS), the Dutch Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) and other data repositories, and will be part of N4O.

Through the LAD-BW, N4O participates in the EU COST Action Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age (SEADDA) that seeks to secure LTA and accessibility of archaeological data across Europe and beyond. N4O members who are active in SEADDA guarantee synergy between the two communities. LAD-BW is participating in the Europae Archaeologiae Consilium (EAC), and members co-authored the EAC Guidelines 1, The Standard and Guide to Best Practice in Archaeological Archiving in Europe.

The German National Coordinating Institution of The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). Co-applicants in TA5, TA6 and TA7 (VZG, MPIWG, DAI) are members of DARIAH, as are AdW, BBAW and UBA. Due to the close links between the iDAI.world thesaurus and the Backbone Thesaurus (BBT), the DAI is working closely with DARIAH-EU. The DAI participated extensively in developing the BBT content relating to objects and has adapted the architecture of its idai.thesauri to that of the BBT.

The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) seeks to make expertise, data and technologies available through standardisation. Both the DAI and the Rathgen Research Laboratory of the co-applicant SPK are involved in E-RIHS and thus strengthen N4O's access to the existing European infrastructure. Staff members of the DAI participate in the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC-CRM) Special

Interest Group of the International Council of Museums (ICOM). N4O member i3mainz is involved with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and thus links the consortium to a worldwide community creating geospatial (location) LOD. Through the TU Berlin, N4O is linked to the international research database Provena of the German Lost Art Foundation (Deutsches Zentrum Kulturgutverluste). The German National Library, a participant in N4O, is part of the cooperation managing the Integrated Authority File (Gemeinsamen Normdatei, GND) and a respected partner in major global collaborations, for example as an initiator of the project Virtual International Authority File (VIAF), which links the GND with other national authority files. Co-applicant RGZM and others are actively involved in EXARC, the ICOM-affiliated organisation for archaeological open-air museums, experimental archaeology, ancient technology and interpretation. With 300 members in over 40 countries, it offers a strong supportive network. MPIWG is a member of the Consortium for Open Research Data in the Humanities (CORDH).

N4O will foster its multiple international relationships to compare international contexts and approaches, share theory and best practice, learn from each other and network the services of N4O internationally. N4O will intensify collaboration with other international data services such as the Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH), the Digital Archaeological Record (tDAR), the Swedish National Data Service, the Europeana Task Force on 3D Content, the Community Standards for 3D Data Preservation (CS3DP) initiative, and the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF). N4O will be the hub for exchange between international services developing data standards related to archaeology and other consortia in the NFDI. In harmony with NFDI, N4O members will implement legal requirements and digitisation strategies of the German federal and state governments, while keeping an eye on the European and international level. Thus N4O will decisively contribute to making internationally relevant research data more accessible.

3.4 Organisational structure and viability

The organisational bodies of N4O, their individual tasks and means of involving the community are introduced in 3.4.1. The community-based decision-making processes embedded in them, the prospects for their viability, and means for resolving conflicts and risk management are described in 3.4.2-3.

3.4.1 Organisational Bodies and Community Involvement

General Assembly (GA): The central decision-making body of the N4O is the GA. It consists of one delegate from each N4O participant and co-applicant as well as one delegate of the professional associations (Fachgesellschaften) in the academic fields of N4O. The GA decides on all aspects of the formal standards process of N4O. This includes proposals and other questions concerning the N4O Commons and the admission of new members. The GA also approves the consortium's strategic planning for the following year based on a proposal from the Steering Committee (SC).

Steering Committee (SC): The SC is the central executive body in the N4O governance structure. It is headed by the SP, with the co-spokespersons as members, and is responsible for compliance with decision-making processes, monitoring and evaluating the progress of the work programme. The SC decides on the scientific coordination, budget, management and strategic planning for N4O, admits and processes the exit of consortium members.

Spokesperson (SP): The SP leads the administration of the consortium and chairs the SC. The SP is responsible for applying generally binding regulations of the governance bodies, e.g. on procedure and elections. The SP facilitates all decision-making

Figure 6: N4O governance structure.

processes within the SC and the GA, and is elected by the members of the statutory consortium according to §22 (2) of the constitution of the NFDI e.V.

Task Areas (TAs): TAs are the central operational bodies of N4O, led by the co-applicants to meet community needs where they are. Since the TAs were formed in 2019, they have ensured the early involvement of scholars in planning and prioritising N4O services. Each TA is based on existing practices, structures and needs assessments, covers the entire funding period and is organised into specific measures and tasks (see section 5). The TRAILS are practical extracts from this work programme. The community accompanies the TAs in the CCs and refines their work programme in the second-phase TRAILS process. In each TA, the CCs and TWGs accompany the transition to FAIR data standards on objects and their histories.

Community Clusters (CC): As the needs analysis revealed that RDM requires a partial digital redefinition of traditional academic boundaries, N4O fosters restructuring of the community into CCs according to its RDM needs. CCs are made up of individuals from the N4O member institutions, specialists from outside N4O and all other interested persons, regardless of membership status in N4O. Thus CCs are key to openness and community participation to meet common RDM challenges in the long term; they can be formed to focus on different stages of the data lifecycle or TAs. CCs cooperate with corresponding structures in other NFDI consortia. They meet regularly and document their activities and outcomes in the N4O Commons. The SC appoints a CC upon proposal from the TA or the community, and the CO supports them. Each CC has two co-leads, from a participant and a co-applicant. CC's can be set up and adjusted as needed. At the beginning we start with the following CC:

Table 3.4.1: Community cluster set to be included in the N4O consortium from the beginning and extended as needed

CC	Cluster name	Assignment	Lead	NFDI	Communities
CC1	Knowledge Modelling and Interoperability	This cluster is a pool of computer scientists, data scientists and digital humanities specialists, covering the processing, enrichment and publication in the research data lifecycle. It facilitates interdisciplinary knowledge exchange on (meta)data modelling to achieve FAIR data in RDM. The domain-specific aspects are: meta- and research data structures, semantic modelling, LOD, fuzziness and wobbliness.	Uni Cologne Uni Frankfurt RGZM DAI	NFDI4Culture NFDI4Memory NFDI4Earth FAIRagro	CAA DE / International Linked Pasts Pelagios Commons DHd AG Graphen und Netzwerke RDA DE e.V., FDO Working Groups
CC2	Data Capture and Creation	A group of experts in the multiple processes of deriving digital data from cultural heritage objects will design and apply quality systems and workflows, understand and code software solutions, and can assess the diversity of data formats for suitability in RDM.	VZG DAI RGZM GDKE	NFDI4Culture NFDI4Memory Text+	RDLC
CC3	Authority Files and Community-driven Vocabularies	A pool of scientists within and across all TAs in N4O, and with other NFDI consortia, will collaborate to exchange decentralised authority files and community-driven vocabularies.	Institut für Museumsforschung VZG DAI	NFDI4Culture NFDI4Memory NFDI4Earth NFDI4Chem NFDI4Biodiversity	RLDC
					Continued on next page

CC	Cluster name	Assignment	Lead	NFDI	Communities
CC4	Research Software Engineering (RSE)	This cluster is a pool of research software engineers, computer scientists, and digital humanities specialists. It will facilitate interdisciplinary knowledge exchange on the development and sustainability of software to achieve FAIR data in RDM. This involves domain-specific aspects: RSE, UX/UI, and N4O core services.	CAA-DE RGZM	NFDI4Culture NFDI4Earth NFDI4Ing	deRSE e.V., CAA International (SIG SSLA, Little Minions), CAA Deutschland, AG Research Software Engineering in den Digital Humanities (DHd), Linked Past
CC5	Provenance Research	A pool of digital provenance researchers. The aim is to establish authority files on previous owners and sellers and to reconstruct networks across collections; in contrast to other forms of provenance research, the starting point is the data on the history of the objects.	TU Berlin SPK	NFDI4Culture	Community
CC6	Collection Management	A pool of scientists to accompany the project of scientific identification, addressing and recording of the objects kept in the museums, their documentation and enrichment with digital concepts, the creation of common thesauri and enrichment with LOD.	Arbeitsstelle Sammlungen der Univer- sitäten SPK	NFDI4Culture	Community
CC7	Citizen Science	This cluster is a pool of professional and citizen scientists and digital humanities specialists. It will facilitate interdisciplinary knowledge exchange on research data publication and harvesting of community-driven hubs, as well as information related to processing and dissemination of citizen science data.	GDKE	NFDI4Culture	Wikimedia Deutschland

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CC	Cluster name	Assignment	Lead	NFDI	Communities
CC8	Objects as information carriers	The cluster works on objects as carriers of (semantic) information, which can be expressed in signs, literals/letters or images. The aim is to model the relationships between the physicality and semantics of each object from a multidisciplinary, RDM perspective.	Inscriptiones Graecae (BBAW) SPK	NFDI4Culture Text+ NFDI4Memory	Community
CC9	Biosciences	A pool of archaeologists well connected to other consortia to create a network for exchange on biosciences.	Staatssammlung für Anthropologie und Paläoanatomie München, Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns DAI	Text+ NFDI4Culture Memorandum of Understanding	Community: Gesellschaft für Anthropologie
CC10	Material Sciences	A pool of archaeologists well connected to other consortia to create a network for exchange on material sciences.	CEZA Mannheim		Community: GNAA e.V., AK Archäometrie
CC11	Cultural Anthropology	A pool of archaeologists well connected to other consortia to create a network for exchange on cultural anthropology in accordance with the CARE principles.		NFDI4Culture	Community: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Volkskunde e.V.

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CC	Cluster name	Assignment	Lead	NFDI	Communities
CC12	Building History	A pool of building researchers, primarily at universities, concerned with the multimodal documentation and preservation of built architecture. The aim is to consider the specific requirements this genre of object in the digital context by networking and integrating specialist vocabularies and for exchange across consortia.	Uni Bamberg	NFDI4Ing NFDI4Culture NFDI4Memory	Community
CC13	Geosciences	A pool of archaeologists well connected to other consortia to create a network for exchange on geosciences.	UFZ	NFDI4Earth	Community: Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft e.V., European Geosciences Union, GDI-DE, OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium, IUGG – International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
CC14	Conservation Science	A pool of practising restoration/conservation scientists and a network for exchange across consortia on conservation science.	RGZM		Community: Verband Deutscher Restauratoren

Advisory Board (AB): The AB provides N4O with external strategic advice. It consists of 10 members, external to N4O, representing national and international perspectives of N4O stakeholders (see section 4.1). Following an open call for candidates, five members of the AB will be elected by the GA. Following nominations, the SC will elect another five members of the AB. The spokesperson cannot vote, but attends the meetings of the AB. The AB is invited to the GA by the SC. The AB reviews the status of N4O and gives recommendations to the SC on strategic development of the work programme (including community proposals). It advises on the international networking of N4O services. The AB meets during the N4O Annual Meeting, participates in the GA, and can be asked to advise on controversial issues.

Coordination Office (CO): The CO supports all decision-making, executive and operational bodies of the consortium. The DAI hosts CO management and coordination, while its staff is distributed among applicants, located in each TA to assist the SC in monitoring and ensuring networking within N4O. At least 6 FTE staff plus the Berlin part of the CO drive the work of the consortium (fig. 7). The CO is the main helpdesk and contact point for external and internal requests and actively supports the CCs. It also provides contract management, financial management and documentation and is responsible for systems integration and technical supervision (fig. 8). The CO draws up a Project Management Plan and provides an efficient digital communication system for all members of N4O. It informs the AB and organizes the AB meetings.

To guarantee continuous participation of its community/ies, transparency and community-driven adjustment of the working programme, N4O has developed the following formats:

N4O Annual Meeting: This central communication event of the consortium is a multi-day meeting open to all interested parties. The N4O Annual Meeting is intended to be a major event for everybody interested in RDM in N4O domains. At the heart of the meeting is a conference to present results, create space for scientific exchange (posters, lectures), and conduct structured community discussions in sessions with the governance body of N4O.

Temporary working groups (TWGs): TWGs are formed to solve specific problems in N4O. Work in TWGs is based on a detailed outline document, which defines the deliverables to the N4O commons. TWGs drive the consortium's development of standards and specifications, are open to everyone and convened along thematic lines to support work in a TA. A TWG has to be proposed by at least one co-applicant institution and has to be approved by the SC on the basis of the proposal; the spokesperson (SP) then appoints members based on this proposal. A TWG is dissolved if it merges with another TWG, becomes inactive, or as soon as it meets its goals.

N4O Commons: Results on all aspects of RDM developed by the N4O Community with the TAs are collected and openly shared in an online portal, including policy and procedure documents and standard workflows (section 3.4.3). The N4O Commons represents consensus on community suggestions, recommendations and standards, good and best practices, technical descriptions, OERs and recommendations for developing services. Thus, the N4O Commons offers constantly updated access to outcomes of the consortium's work, and clearly articulates the community's needs within the NFDI.

3.4.2 Viability and community engagement

The clear organisational structure of N4O strengthens collaboration across disciplinary boundaries and creates sustainable processes for long-term work in the consortium.

To meet community needs, a key aim of N4O is to define community standards and develop a corresponding architecture of services (see section 4.4). In an environment characterised by individual, domain- and institution-specific solutions, N4O will steer

Figure 7: The CO, as a structure linking all the task areas, is the administrative and organisational backbone of N4O.

the move towards increasing levels of standardisation, from stimulative to normative (fig. 9). These five levels correspond to the services and documents stored in the N4O Commons to provide FAIR data. This ensures that community needs are met in a simple, transparent and participatory way. The CCs (see above) ensure that all participants, regardless of discipline or interest, have equal access to these processes. N4O services are tailored to target and interest groups, shown in the figure and table (table 3.4). TWGs are formed to solve particular problems in the operating process of N4O. Clearly structured process chains ensure that sustainable community relationships are built and maintained through active engagement. Work in TWGs is based on a detailed outline document, which defines the deliverables. The relevance of a TWG to the N4O Commons is reflected in the response of the community and commitment of a co-applicant institution to form each TWG, which provides publicly accessible information on its progress, closely monitored and actively supported by the CO. A preliminary draft of TWG deliverables is submitted to the public for comment for a limited period. At the end of this process, the GA will have sufficient information to vote on adopting the deliverables to the N4O Commons and making them a regulatory document for further consortium work. Change requests will enable timely adaptation of each TWG document. This process is a formal expression of the N4O community's input into the NFDI as a whole: the interested community worldwide has a reliable and citable basis for adoption, OERs can be based on an up-to-date consensus, and the content can be integrated into higher-level services. Thus the N4O offers the community a reliable framework for collaborative solutions and increases acceptance of the results (fig. 10).

The CO provides administrative support so CCs and TWGs can focus on sharing knowledge and experience, identifies community needs for technical supplements to core services (e.g. new software solutions) and supports joint initiatives to apply for third-party funding.

In the N4O programme, various incentives enlarge and diversify the community participating in NFDI and stimulate new ideas. These include TRAILS, ECR scholarships, and bursaries for the N4O Annual Meetings. TRAILS (see section 3.1) expand the community actively involved in N4O and provide flexible funds that enable resource-constrained

Figure 8: Fields of activity of the Coordination Office.

members to contribute their expertise. The format is particularly interesting for universities: 15 German universities are involved in the first round of TRAILS. N4O offers ECR scholarships enabling early-career researchers to refine data sets or software solutions over several months, so that they can be transferred to the N4O service architecture. The equitable selection process is coordinated with the DFG and awards decided by the GA. N4O will also provide €15,000 per year in bursaries to enable community members to attend the N4O Annual Meetings.

N4O will launch a website to guide the community on modes of participation, consultation services and incentives, the work in the TAs (TWGs and CCs) deliverables to the N4O Commons, and RDM services. The website will include information about N4O and community events to raise awareness of the NFDI processes and the challenges of RDM, recruit new supporters, and reach the broader community. This will be accompanied by constant information on social media channels (esp. Twitter).

To ensure that the community receives immediate, reliable and practical answers to its RDM questions, a central helpdesk will deliver enquiries straight to the TAs. This integrated service will be supported with OER materials and consultation outside NFDI (TA6), especially at the universities, to dovetail with local services as closely as possible. This ensures constant, bidirectional communication to meet needs. All participating institutions will assure second level support for core services (see section 5.5).

Figure 9: Commons contributions in a framework of increasing levels of standardisation.

Figure 10: Commons decision making procedure.

To ensure that the community receives immediate, reliable and practical answers to its RDM questions, a central helpdesk will deliver enquiries straight to the TAs. This integrated service will be supported with OER materials and consultation outside NFDI (TA6), especially at the universities, to dovetail with local services as closely as possible. This ensures constant, bidirectional communication to meet needs. All participating institutions will assure second level support for core services (see section 5.5). The consortium drives and supports seamless integration of RDM into research projects. Templates for RDM plans for different application scenarios are being developed with local consultation offices. The consortium supports third-party funding institutions such as the DFG to develop RDM guidelines and research institutions to plan RDM strategies.

3.4.3 Risk management

In case of any problems in achieving their objectives (including the reporting of any potential conflict situations), the co-spokespersons must immediately inform the SP. The SP will mediate between the parties to find a solution that is supported by the SC. In case the conflict remains, the SP will collect the differing positions which then have to be voted on in the GA by a simple majority (electronic voting in case of urgency). If the problem cannot be solved in this way, the AB and the NFDI Directorate will be consulted.

The large number of partners in a project like N4O, their interdependence, the speed of developments and changes in the digital world, plus the challenge of long-term sustainability of personnel, know-how and services pose risks to the success of the overall project. These can also have a significant impact on its progress. Therefore, we have summarized the risk assessment for N4O in the following table:

Table 3.4.3: Risk assessment for N4O

Risk	Impact	Scale	Reaction
TEAM: Key project staff leaves	Delay in progress of TA work	High	Rapid recruitment of replacement capacity; superordinate, systematic documentation of the work progress for seamless handover; distributed knowledge in CO.
TEAM: Single partners drop out	Support and development of services could suffer	Medium/ High	Search for new partners/participants to fill the gap; in case key infrastructure components are affected, the main applicant or one of the co-applicants will take over
TEAM: Project positions cannot be filled	Work cannot be initiated by partner, delay in TA work	Medium	Establish task groups to fill gaps with partners and existing staff. Recruitment in a concerted action and capacity building in academic curricula.
INFRASTRUCTURE: Curatorial capacity and/or processing/archiving components do not scale with acquired amount of data	Processing and/or archiving tasks are delayed or cancelled	Medium	Increasing capacities by additional commitments from N4O partners, new participants; development of sustainable operating models
INFRASTRUCTURE: Central infrastructure components fail	The service portfolio of N4O is seriously affected	Low	The core of the central infrastructures offered in N4O is already in operation and guaranteed by the institutions. In the unlikely case that a key partner drops out we will ask for other partners to step in (funds will be reallocated)
NEEDS: Shift of research and infrastructure requirements due to international developments	N4O developments do not match the overall objectives	Low	Monitoring of, continuous contribution and reaction to international developments; adaption of the work programme and revision of N4O Commons documents

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Risk	Impact	Scale	Reaction
NEEDS: A considerable portion of the community remains entrenched in established patterns of data handling and is not open to cultural change	The N4O service portfolio is not accepted well enough to warrant their continued development	Medium	Analysis of the user surveys and adjustment of the measures in the evaluation phase. Activation of the network deeply rooted in the community and communication of success stories based on the results already achieved
COMMUNITY: Community activity in the N4O participatory formats (TWG, CC) is not sufficient	Delay or withdrawal of the development of N4O Commons documents; decrease of acceptance	Medium	Increase publicity for N4O and the incentive measures; make specific contact with possibly interested partners; make intensive use of the networks and channels of the participating associations
COMMUNITY: Insufficient participation of specific groups of stakeholders, e.g. universities, in the further development of N4O	Insufficient acceptance of NFDI in this group; low impact of N4O developments and services	Medium	Use of information measures specifically tailored to the respective group; if necessary, reaction to the needs of the specific group through adjustments in the work programme; special promotion of the incentive measures in groups to be further activated
PRIORITIES: Diverging views on project priorities	Affects the entire project planning and progress	Medium	Find a joint solution in the SC by involving CCs; get AB involved; discuss and possibly reset priorities in consultation with Directorate
PRIORITIES: Partners are pursuing their individual objectives and disregarding common goals	The integration of different N4O components will be affected	Medium	On the basis of monitoring SP and SC point out the problem in time and influence partners to work towards joint contributions to the N4O Commons; progress is closely monitored through TWGs; if necessary escalation to AB and Directorate. As a last resort, the next share of funding should be cut
Continued on next page			

Risk	Impact	Scale	Reaction
ENTANGLEMENT: Parallel developments of already running consortia or decisions within NFDI e.V. make adjustments of the work programme necessary	Planned contributions of partners become obsolete. Retraction from participation by partners; decreasing acceptance of N4O	Low	Adjustment and reprioritisation of the work programme; changed involvement of the partners concerned; activation of previously postponed or shortened tasks; active contribution to bottom up development to NFDI
TIME: Partners do not have the same speed of progress	Delayed actions on one side could slow down speed of entire project	Medium	Monitoring progress (KPIs, reports); problem analysis and respective reaction; shifting tasks to other partner by changing priorities (funds will be reallocated)
GENERAL: Lack of user acceptance	Project failure	Medium	Increase outreach activities and incentives for involvement in CCs and TWGs; reaction to concrete problems of acceptance in single services; cooperate with the the whole NFDI

3.4.4 Operating model

The N4O operating model is regulated in a cooperation agreement signed by all (co-)applicants and participating institutions. The operating model will comply with non-profit/public benefit (Gemeinnützigkeit) requirements. Unless clearly identified as sub-contracts, the exchange of services between (co-)applicants and/or participants within N4O must meet these requirements and not involve financial transactions of any kind. N4O will integrate itself into the published statutes and structure of the NFDI e.V. It is committed to the goals formulated in §2 of NFDI e.V. statutes and aims to create a consortium according to §22 of those statutes (“gemäß Satzung”). In N4O, no decisions will be taken that conflict with the legal framework conditions (consortium agreement) and decisions of the N4O governance (Steering Committee, Advisory Board; “gemäß BLV”). N4O takes responsibility in sections of the NFDI e.V. according to §23. N4O members are either already members of the NFDI or will join it soon.

The CO supports all executive and operational organs of the consortium and is responsible for contract management, financial management, documentation and reporting (see section 3.4). It will also operate the central helpdesk and central portal of N4O. As a subordinate federal authority within the German Foreign Office, the DAI can draw on well-established administrative workflows and financial control mechanisms to ensure the appropriate use of funds. All co-applicants and participants can also demonstrate substantial experience in managing third-party funds for collaborative projects. The SP and CO will ensure regular financial monitoring. The work programme of N4O includes a variety of measures to ensure the effective functioning of the consortium and the sustainability of the N4O services (see M1.7, M2.4, M3.7, M4.7, M5.6, M6.1, M7.1). Central decisions within the N4O are made by the GA with a simple majority of the votes. To have a quorum, 75% of the delegates must be present at the GA physically or through teleconference facilities at the time of voting. The agenda of the GA meetings and the necessary documents (e.g. proposals for resolutions) will be prepared by the SC based on the work of the TAs, TWGs and CCs. Depending on the nature of the decision, the GA may be called to a meeting in accordance with §22 of the constitution of the NFDI. The GA will be held during the N4O Annual Meeting (see section 3.4), face to face or in exceptional/urgent cases as a digital meeting. At the GA, the SP gives his annual report.

As N4O is projected for a minimum of 5+ years, some fluctuation in the N4O membership is to be expected, so N4O will set up consolidated admission and exit procedures. Effective mechanisms will regularly evaluate the work, the results and the overall structure of the consortium (see section 3.4.3). The long-term success of N4O depends on its services achieving a high level of acceptance. Therefore, N4O will utilise a number of means (surveys, the helpdesk, the N4O Annual Meetings, meetings of professional associations and usage statistics, monitoring the progress of N4O Commons in relation to the work programme) to receive and respond to feedback from the community. Every N4O service will be maintained either by the respective operating institution, or sustainable non-profit operating models (see section 4.4).

4 Research Data Management Strategy

The RDM strategy of N4O is guided by the research of object biographies: documenting, collecting, protecting, analysing, storing and sharing. This leads to the definition of TA1–5 (which develop and provide services for the different stages), while TA6 will oversee the integration. To write an object biography, divisions between material objects and their digital representation fade: both have to be kept together. The phases of object research need to be interlinked with the research data lifecycle.¹³ N4O is committed to this central challenge to RDM for objects. While the needs of the N4O stakeholders are best described and structured along the object biography, to develop FAIR and CARE data services and embed them within NFDI requires orientation to the research data lifecycle. The link between these two levels is organised and bridged by the different TAs (see fig. 11).

The biography of objects play a key role in the N4O Community because scientific approaches towards objects have shifted away from seeing objects as independent or only locally contextualised manifestations, which can be managed in idiosyncratic systems, to objects with manifold histories within complex, macro-scale socio-epistemic networks. Therefore, digital research on individual object biographies requires interoperable, enriched data from different sources with different levels of quality, all of which need to be aligned and integrated in a common data ecosystem.¹⁴

In addition to the digital representations of physical objects, the associated quantitative and qualitative metadata are also research data. Consequently, in object-related research, data must allow the handling of fuzziness and wobbliness (as an overarching pair of concepts for e.g. uncertainty, vagueness, accuracy, blurriness, precision, imprecision and ambiguity¹⁵) and must be readable to both machines and humans.

Digital transformation fundamentally changes the view of what an object is and the ethical and legal constraints on how to model, store, share and maintain not only the physical object but also its (meta)data and representations. In N4O, all stages of RDM have to represent the current discourse on the multiple meanings of objects in different societies and their provenances, to contribute to knowledge equity and justice.

4.1 State of the art and needs analysis

The N4O RDM strategy takes into account the historical developments in producing and processing object-related digital data until today. Within the humanities, archaeology and related disciplines are early adopters of digital technologies. Over the last 30 years, rapid developments in measurement technology (e.g. GNSS, total stations, LiDAR scanning), online networking, IT services and more complex software packages (e.g. RDBMS, GIS, CAD) have led to a highly fragmented, heterogeneous world of individual routines and strategies for dealing with digital research data. One inherited problem is that object research is still widely conducted within specific disciplinary structures and confined by different legal and organisational frameworks. The present heterogeneity of how data for research on objects is created, processed and used in archaeology and its related fields, identified in the N4O Community survey,¹⁶ has a major impact on our RDM strategy. The majority of the stakeholders have no internationally recognised authorities that develop and maintain RDM standards, and instead adopt regulations from other disciplines. The availability and use of metadata in the N4O Community is very diverse depending on the origin of the data and the data types used. Further constraints and dependencies arise from how the data was created and who is responsible for it.

¹³ Inspired by Jisc RDM toolkit and Phasen des Datenlebens, Landesmuseum Stuttgart.

¹⁴ Examples include: Atlas der Innovationen, ROCCEH, Numid-Online & KENOM, Roman Transport Network Connectivity and Economic Integration (<https://doi.org/10.1093/restud/rdab036>), see: Renn et al. 2016

¹⁵ see CIDOC-CRM Group Document on Recording Uncertainty, and Approximate Dimensions, Vocabularies Swiss Art Research Infrastructure (SARI), NFDI4Culture Proposal.

¹⁶ Schmidt et al. 2020.

Figure 11: Research Data Lifecycle, FAIR Data Services and Object Biography.

The individual handling of digital data led to very specific processes in its acquisition and management within different institutions with different policies, which at the same time led to a specialisation of individual practitioners. Consequently, traditional disciplinary structures still dominate the practice of object research, although the management of digital research data requires alignment of standards and, partially, a redefinition of traditional academic boundaries. In building a common data ecosystem, many members of the N4O Community face two major challenges: incompatible processes and isolated data repositories, and high variance in staff expertise.

One major group of stakeholders are universities where a multitude of specialised institutes exist which are organised in different faculties and subject-clusters. Only in a few cases are all object related disciplines represented together in one university. With their international connections and dedicated research profiles, universities generate new RDM needs for cutting-edge questions. Another importance of the universities arises from the large number of object collections, often small and linked to individual institutes and departments, that play a major role as resources for research and teaching.¹⁷ However, as the German Wissenschaftsrat noted in 2011, their scientific potential is not always exploited to the fullest.¹⁸ Thus, they have to be made digitally more findable, accessible and interlinkable on a large scale to strengthen their scientific impact. Due to legal and financial constraints, infrastructures at universities generally address only the RDM needs of specific research projects or their own students, graduates and employees. One rare example of an overarching service is the Propylaeum Specialized Information Service Classics provided by the university library (UB) Heidelberg.

Non-university research institutions such as the DAI, the German academies, several Max Planck¹⁹ and Leibniz²⁰ institutes, and specific research centres²¹ play a specific role for object research because long-term specialist research projects with well-established data management procedures can be carried out there (even over several decades). These institutions are often large enough to operate their own scientific IT departments which can provide sustainable services and infrastructures to the N4O Community. However, the RDM requirements for object biographies are comparable to those of other research institutions but with a special focus on the long-term perspective and sustainability of technical solutions.

Data from national archaeological activities inside Germany is to a large degree generated in the context of administrative actions and duties and is organised by the 16 German federal states, each with their own offices of heritage management, technical

¹⁷ <http://www.universitaetssammlungen.de/>.

¹⁸ Wissenschaftsrat 2011.

¹⁹ MPIWG, MPI-EVA.

²⁰ Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut für Archäologie - RGZM (Mainz), Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen - Deutsches Bergbau-Museum (Bochum).

²¹ Zentrum für Baltische und Skandinavische Archäologie in Schleswig (zbsa.eu); Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie gGmbH in Mannheim (www.rem-mannheim.de/forschung/curt-engelhorn-zentrum-archaeometrie/).

framework and legislation for heritage protection. So national standards, e.g. data exchange formats, require long discussions and coordination processes. N4O thus needs to bridge the different approaches and responsibilities between the federal states.

Another major group of stakeholders are engaged in research-driven collecting of objects, mainly public and private museums. Here the material remains of human history are described and classified, preserved and restored, researched and presented. One RDM distinctive task of these stakeholders is to exhibit and explain the objects also to the general, non-scientific public and to diverse societies worldwide.

There are also commercial stakeholders who produce and process research data about objects, e.g. companies for archaeological excavations, surveying, material analysis or architectural documentation. On the one hand, they need clear data requirements to fulfil service contracts; on the other hand, contracting bodies profit from standardised RDM specifications in calls for tender.

Finally, thousands of volunteers contribute to and support the tasks of the cultural heritage authorities. As citizen scientists, these stakeholders make a fundamental contribution to knowledge of Germany's monuments and cultural landscape. Until now, third-party transfer of object information between cultural heritage authorities and citizen scientists has mostly been analogue. A common data infrastructure, community standards, templates and tools are needed to e.g. record small archaeological finds and their contextual information as well as to integrate the knowledge of these independent citizen scientists into research data services. N4O members are already involved in a variety of community-driven initiatives for volunteered data and FLOSS software (e.g. Wikidata²², Open Street Map).

Cross-cutting RDM needs arise for data-driven research on objects that often lead to specific individual questions about the data. Addressing these questions and bringing them into line with the data offered by heterogeneous providers is a central challenge for data management. This requires the inclusion of research groups in the N4O Commons process (section 3.4.4) in modelling object biographies and discussing elements of an ObjectCore data model. Another cross-cutting requirement, provenance research, is supported by collection and data curators, historians and cultural researchers. This is increasingly attracting public interest and can have implications on the presentation of objects or on political issues, for example in cultural and foreign policy. Using qualified referenced data is the only way to clarify international connections between the actual contexts of finds, smuggling and illegal transfers of cultural objects, or relationships between forgeries and fakes.

N4O's overall RDM strategy is developed in line with the research processes of object biographies: documenting, collecting, analysing, protecting, storing and sharing.

Documentation serves as the primary source for the context of an object and even for the object itself. Archaeological objects are subject to constant change – primarily deterioration due to environmental influences, deliberate and accidental destruction, conservation and restoration, cultural-scientific interpretation and presentation. Due to the irretrievability of the features once excavated around an object, sustainable documentation is key. Increasingly sophisticated digital solutions have long since replaced conventional, paper-based methods. For excavation data, a wide range of contextual information must be recorded to make this crucial stage in the object's history digitally accessible and perpetuated for future generations. Stratigraphic units, building structures, find contexts and find associations form the backbone for the historical valorisation of objects. Existing conceptual schemes for complete documentation (e.g. CRM_{Archaeo}) must be developed further so experts can use them to express the archaeological information fully, and in a machine-readable way.

Technologies to capture 2D and 3D geodata (position on the earth's surface) are becoming more mobile and diverse. At the same time, the quality of georeferencing must be aligned with the precision required for a specific documentation purpose. Therefore, all parameters that have contributed to the calculation of a 3D coordinate and that

²² e.g. WikiProject Cultural heritage, and the Wikimedia Germany Open Science Fellow Program Projects WikiProject Prähistorische Keramik or WikiProject Irish Ogham Stones.

influence its usage in photogrammetric and computer vision methods must be described and recorded, especially in destructive documentation processes. In a market dominated by commercial suppliers, only a few open-source tools exist that are capable of providing the entire data acquisition and evaluation process for sustainable data management. The same holds true for corresponding metadata schemas and vocabularies which are largely used by individuals in isolated institutional contexts or projects. The result is a multitude of terms and concepts existing in parallel systems, often describing the same objects and their properties. As these domain-driven vocabularies cannot be completely harmonised, semantic alignments and mappings of data models will be needed to enhance the data management and exchange.

Systems for recording objects in collections focus on two different task categories: management (i.e. inventory, conservation, exhibitions, loans: collection management systems), and scientific in-depth recording with thematic focuses and contextualisation (domain-specific research collections).²³ Both task categories contribute to collection research, e.g. provenance questions, at different levels of granularity, data quality and knowledge modelling. Currently, the landscape of collection management systems in the museums is extremely heterogeneous: different commercial or open source systems (e.g. easydb, MuseumPlus, Robotron Daphne, Arches, Hida) are in use. Due to this heterogeneity, machine-readable interfaces are often not well-defined and standardised, thus making it difficult to fully implement existing metadata schemas for data exchange (e.g. LIDO, CARARE 2.0, Europeana Data Model [[252C?]EDM], CIDOC-CRM), making data interoperability and object referencing a huge challenge for the collections community. Domain-specific research collections (e.g. epigraphy, papyrology, lithics, nautics) are often individually modelled for specific materials and questions. Some research fields like numismatics and ceramics have made considerable progress yielding widely accepted domain-specific object data hubs (e.g. nomisma, kerameikos, numid.online, ikmk.net). For most institutions, however mapping and integration of research collection data into object collection union systems (e.g. museum digital²⁴, cultural web hubs of the federal states²⁵) and overarching major union systems (e.g. Europeana, Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek or Community Systems like Wikidata) are still a major challenge. At present, data quality and alignment issues play only a minor role in the data enrichment process for collection and provenance research. A wide palette of authority files and community-driven vocabularies (e.g. thesauri, typologies, controlled vocabularies, persons in GND and ULAN, institutions in ISIL), ontologies (e.g. EDM, CIDOC-CRM) and domain-specific knowledge modelling aspects (e.g. metadata, research data structure, semantic modelling, LOD, fuzziness and wobbliness) all follow their own rules. Consequently, these resources do not fit all the needs of the collection research community, which negatively affects the implementation of machine-to-machine interfaces (M2M) and the exchange of data. Authority files and community-driven vocabularies that are not centrally created and managed often cannot be merged. Therefore, there is a need for coherent technical implementations to share and interconnect cultural heritage collection data and to make objects accessible via cross-collection discovery systems.

The study of artefacts and objects with analytical and experimental approaches has a long tradition in archaeology, involving physical, chemical, geological and biological disciplines and new methods such as archaeometry and archaeobiology. Therefore, N4O datasets for analytics and experiments are highly diverse and based on different material archives and data acquisition strategies.

Geoarchives of soils, landscapes and mineral resources (lithic raw materials, ores, pigments, etc.) that shaped the resource-based living conditions of societies are studied in geoarchaeology. They provide the context in which archaeological remains were embedded. The production of artefacts (e.g. ceramics, metals, vitreous materials) is based on these resources, providing important indications of the exchange processes in early

²³ Detailed at https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Collection_Research_Network.png.

²⁴ <https://www.museum-digital.de/>.

²⁵ e.g. <https://kulturerbe.niedersachsen.de>,
<https://thue.museum-digital.de>, <https://kulturportal-bayern.de>.

societies. The numerous partial databases and systems in geoscientific archaeometry which already exist need to be unified in larger, accepted digital repositories. In addition, image-based (e.g. microsections and thin sections) and chemical analyses on the composition of ancient lithics, metals, glass, and ceramics are all structured by using sample data kept in isolated institutional repositories. Such datasets are also connected with laboratory studies (e.g. on isotopes and radiometrics) about the provenance, dating and context of artefacts.

Archaeobiology is concerned with the scientific exploration of archaeological remains of humans, plants and animals. It comprises anthropology, palaeobotany and archaeozoology and provides manifold information on the anthropogenic use of bioresources, mobility and health status of humans and animals, their relationship to their natural environment and changes in climate and biodiversity. Traditional morphological studies of biological remains are supplemented by innovative molecular biology approaches such as stable isotope and archaeogenetic analyses. Besides the large datasets on ecofacts relating to the interactions between humans, animals and the environment, organics also constitute raw materials for producing artefacts (e.g. wood, dyes, bones, fibre fabrics) and yield insight into ancient production and living conditions. Digital and analytical data on organics require specialised preservation strategies and linkage to datasets on composition and material origin. Another source for production and consumption practices in past societies are experimental and testing approaches that have traditionally taken the form of replication, reconstruction and re-enactment of these practices. More recent formal experiments performed under controlled conditions use sophisticated high-tech equipment to digitally record both methods and observations.

In total, analytical and experimental data management needs to start in community-driven processes, with the development of material-specific interoperable data repositories which fulfil the FAIR principles and to establish their acceptance and use by scientists in relevant sub-communities.

Several institutions that are responsible for physical sites and artefacts have an abundant stock of unpublished data from measures to safeguard and protect them (e.g. [rescue] excavations, prospecting, research, restoration, conservation). They also provide regulations on a sites' legal heritage protection status or recommendations on handling cultural assets according to international guidelines. These issues of cultural (and natural) heritage protection, conservation and preservation must be integrated as early as possible into spatial, urban and regional planning processes. This is not happening in part because of a lack of a unified data exchange and because the granularity and availability of data holders' vocabularies vary considerably. Aligned and harmonised authority files and community-driven vocabularies are needed to make data about sites and protection measures more interoperable. In an effort to strengthen national and international cooperation in heritage conservation and preservation, as well as to provide FAIR data for research institutions, N4O aims to create standardised data exchange interfaces that will bridge specialised disciplines, legal borders and isolated technical solutions which arose from the cultural sovereignty of the German federal states.

Despite the contribution of German federal states' archives and IANUS – a national research data centre for archaeology – the N4O Community lacks an accessible infrastructure for long term archiving. To fill this gap and improve existing services, the technical requirements for object-specific RDM need to be met. The archival community standard, the OAIS reference model,²⁶ must be applied to the N4O-specific needs to structure submission, archival and dissemination information packages (SIPs, AIPs, DIPs), and to define for each discipline and research field significant properties, archive-worthy formats, curation and migration procedures. These must then be implemented in both data capture and archiving services. The plethora and interdependencies of file types – texts and statistics, vector and raster data, 3D and audio data, measurement and analysis data – poses a particular challenge.²⁷ Domain-specific strategies are needed that ensure both the functional-technical readability as well as the semantic interpretability

²⁶ <http://www.oais.info>.

²⁷ See IANUS test bed: <https://ianus-fdz.de/projects/uebersicht/wiki/Testforschungsdaten>.

and interoperability of the heterogeneous data in the long term.

Since the technical infrastructure of the N4O Community and the existing services both for developing authority files and community-driven vocabularies have, until now, not been designed as a whole and only addressed specific problems, there is a need for an appropriate overarching infrastructural support for object-related RDM. In this context, a common understanding of data quality is necessary to improve (meta)data and to transfer it to a permanent public domain²⁸ (e.g. repositories, data portals, archives, discovery systems, or information infrastructures).

So N4O will develop common standards and specifications for high-quality, FAIR object-related data by means of archiving guidelines with format and metadata mappings, curation processes and supporting tools. A participatory and transparent N4O Commons process (see section 3.4.2) will generate these crucial outcomes.

4.2 Metadata standards

In the context of N4O, metadata is the central link between physical objects, their digital representations and their analysis and interpretations that makes data FAIR. For N4O metadata also comprises qualified references to authority files and community-driven vocabularies, ontologies, knowledge models and technical specifications, all describing defined entities and their properties and dependencies.

Generally, four types of metadata can be distinguished: descriptive, administrative, structural and technical. With the exception of descriptive metadata, established standards are accepted internationally and barely discipline-specific (e.g. METS/MODS; PREMIS). Descriptive metadata poses a challenge in humanities and object-related research: they refer to object biography, actors and events (e.g. provenance), processes and analyses (e.g. capturing, conservation, experiments) and scientific results (e.g. dating, software algorithms) and can be interpretative, can have both quantitative and qualitative scope, and are structured differently depending on the discipline. N4O needs to enable different views on objects usable for different communities by creating interdisciplinary semantic networks of research data about objects. Meanwhile, metadata is often stored as XML (e.g. LIDO, RDF) or markup languages such as JSON and must be machine-readable for applications in the semantic web.²⁹

The origins, formats, models and types of metadata have strategic consequences. N4O applies the following classification of data origins and types:

1. Data that is recorded daily in collections, on site, in the field and in laboratories. Reproducible and non-reproducible measurements must be distinguished. This includes excavation, survey, field and collection data (geodata, 3D), exploratory and survey data (tables, protocols), sensor data, data from scientific analyses and lab protocols, image data and databases (daily data).
2. Existing, self-contained datasets from 20+ years of digital acquisition and/or processing, insufficiently documented databases and semi-structured file collections with proprietary formats (vulnerable data).
3. Analogue datasets relevant for research that have been or will be retrodigitised. One example are bequests of originally printed publications that underwent conversion in several digital formats, e.g. PDF, OCR or (georeferenced) maps (legacy data).
4. Highly aggregated data series derived from a large number of other datasets using complex analysis methods, e.g. paleo-climate charts, relative chronology systems, statistical models, algorithms, software, tables, visualisations, training/reference and signature data, and formally structured terminologies (data products).

²⁸ Klump 2011.

²⁹ Forschungsdaten.info: Metadaten und Metadatenstandards.

5. Data created by interpreting objects in their material, historical and social contexts and in the form of human readable texts, thesauri and modelled datasets (interpretative data).

This classification makes the highly multidisciplinary significance of N4O evident which is also reflected in the large number of existing metadata approaches and services relevant for N4O:

Authority files and community-driven vocabularies: Archaeological Periods; Archäologiethesaurus; Bamberger Vokabular für historische Architektur; DARIAH-EU Backbone Thesaurus BBT; British Museum Materials Thesaurus; Ceramics Typology; Core Data Index to Historic Buildings; Corpus Nummorum iconography thesaurus on Greek numismatics; Eagle Thesaurus (Europeana); European Education Thesaurus; Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH) vocabularies; Gemeinsame Normdaten (DNB); Geonames; Getty Arts and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT); Getty Cultural Objects Name Authority (CONA); Getty Provenance Index (GPI); Getty Thesaurus of Geographical Names (TGN); Getty Union List of Artist Names (ULAN); Iconclass Thesaurus; iDAI.thesauri; Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF); International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organizations (ISIL); KulturNav; Library of Congress Control Number (LCCN); Library of Congress Subject Headings; md:terms vocabulary browser; museumsvokabular.de; NAVIS ship thesaurus; Normdatenportal des Münzkabinetts Berlin; Otfried von Vacanos Typenindex (NUMID); PeriodO; PICO Thesaurus; Pleiades; PROVEANA; ROCEEH Thesauri; thesauri of the Archäologisches Museum Hamburg; UNESCO Thesaurus; VIAF; Wikidata; WortNetzKultur (LVR).

Ontologies, data knowledge modelling concepts, and exchange standards: Access to Biological Collections Data Ontology (ABCD); Basic Formal Ontology (BFO); CIDOC-CRM (including different extensions); Darwin Core Ontology; Dublin Core Ontology; Extension For Geosciences (EFG); INSPIRE; JSKOS; Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO); Linked Open Archaeological Data Ontology (LADO); Linked Places Data Format; Numismatic Description Schema (NUDS); OGC Services; Spectrum; W3C Standards (OWL, RDF, SKOS, Uncertainty Ontology; Time Ontology); Wikidata:List of properties.

A selection of these services will form the basis for a minimum community standard for modelling object biographies (N4Oo). These are the CRM-related ontologies (i.e. CIDOC-CRM, FRBRoo), Dublin Core and LIDO. TA6 will be responsible for organising an interactive harmonisation process, and the N4Oo will be developed as part of the N4O Commons process. At each iteration, a reference implementation in OWL will be provided and realised in the WissKi environment which represents the current version of the N4Oo with example data. TA1 consolidates metadata schemes that describe the diverse information gathered mobile in the field, integrate it into higher-level documentation processes and assure quality. TA2 looks at objects from the perspective of museums and collections and adds corresponding properties to the scheme. TA3 ensures that the data obtained in manifold scientific processes is linked to the objects of research. TA4 includes data generated in cultural heritage management (e.g. monument conservation, archaeological restoration). The four TAs thus ensure a complete digital representation of an object's biography.

4.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

N4O applies the FAIR, TRUST and CARE principles to all object requirements within community-driven processes.

Regarding the FAIR principles, an N4O survey³⁰ showed that the majority of existing research data within the N4O Community is not part of an integrated, supported, connected and sustainable repository and lacks a standardised level of (meta)data quality. Stakeholders (see section 4.1) have varied experience in RDM, so N4O aims to support data producers and repository operators to implement the FAIR principles within all phases of the research data lifecycle and helps them to attain the level of data quality agreed upon within the community.

To preserve information on the context of objects, it is essential to document excavations and field projects carefully and sustainably. A large amount of object-related (meta)data, both analogue and digital, is unique and not reproducible; to preserve them, N4O is committed to maintaining sustainable long-term services and infrastructures. The TRUST principles (transparency, responsibility, user focus, sustainability and technology) provide N4O with a common framework for facilitating best practice in digital preservation.³¹

N4O seeks to adhere to the CARE Principles³² for Indigenous Data Governance (collective benefit, authority, responsibility and ethics), to fully engage the general public and specific cultural groups' rights and interests, with awareness of power differentials and historical contexts. These issues arise when curating e.g. Jewish or Sorbic heritage in Germany, conducting research abroad and answering provenance questions on ethnological collections. The N4O Community is currently discussing the implications of colonial history for its own research history and identifying ways to prevent the digital appropriation of cultural heritage data of foreign societies. The aim is to negotiate conflicting demands for open and CARE data.³³

To assure data quality within N4O we follow the RDM model.³⁴ To increase findability N4O will develop object-specific concepts for persistent and globally unique resolvable identifiers (e.g. DOI, URI) for metadata and research data, e.g. using iDAI.gazetteer and iDAI.chronontology to provide URIs for space and time resources. N4O will publish authority files and community-driven vocabularies via the DANTE vocabulary service and provide a catalogue of existing datasets and repositories. An overarching discovery system will function as a single access point for distributed metadata and the basis for a knowledge graph. The concepts will be tested for applications in other disciplines using numismatic data (provided by IKMK and KENOM) which is generally of better quality. To increase accessibility, N4O will negotiate (meta)data information access levels, respecting the different requirements of the stakeholders, including issues of data protection (e.g. restrictions on the publication of sensitive sites to prevent looting). N4O will set up several catalogues with entries about relevant datasets and repositories, authority files and community-driven vocabularies, standards and ontologies. All N4O core services will deliver machine-readable data and implement standardised (open access) data exchange protocols for M2M interaction. These protocols will be implemented for systems that still lack data exchange protocols, and for new services including repositories (e.g. ArchbotLit, Anthrobook, Ossobook, Poseidon, ArbotDat) and FAIRification tools. Common interfaces will make the central services a) accessible, b) affordable for the community and c) applicable in discovery systems.

In order to make data interoperable, N4O will concentrate on the principles of Linked Open (Usable) Data³⁵ (LO(U)D). N4O will develop services so that different stakeholders, even with a low digital profile, can prepare and disseminate their data as LOD.

³⁰ Schmidt et al. 2020.

³¹ Lin et al. 2020.

³² see <https://www.gida-global.org/care>.

³³ Carroll et al. 2020.

³⁴ Bahim et al. 2020, Tab. 1.

³⁵ c.f. Thiery 2019

N4O will also provide FAIRification tools for modelling ontologies for object biographies that build on existing approaches like CIDOC-CRM and LIDO. Authority files and community-driven vocabularies play a central role in relating the contents of datasets from different sources and analysing them to answer new questions. New standards are not envisaged here, but relevant research data will be better integrated into existing systems, e.g. via DANTE, so that they can be connected to other infrastructures and reused throughout the N4O Community.

Regarding the reusability of N4O data, the consortium will define minimum requirements and criteria for the (technical) quality of object data and, based on this, will develop tools for curating and validating object data quality. This will include recommendations about licence models according to CARE, data formats and documentation practices.

Many members of the N4O Community work within different legal frameworks including federal state law, international agreements on heritage protection or prevention of the illicit art trade, and initiatives like those of UNESCO or the European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (Council of Europe, Malta, 1992). As these regulations sometimes draw red lines in terms of procedures, working conditions and IPR, they influence implementation of the FAIR principles, especially sharing research data on objects and their (geographical) contexts.

N4O will implement a set of FAIRification services (see section 4.4) tailored to the different needs and knowledge within the community. These services include ontologies, specifications of technical requirements and reference implementations to make basic technologies and standards (e.g. containment in the WissKI Distillery) easily accessible with direct connection to N4O core services. This will support meta- and research data structures, semantic modelling and LOD, and evaluating fuzziness and wobbliness in individual research practice.

All activities concerning the FAIRification of object data will be coordinated by TA7. The services will be integrated by TA5, which will develop and maintain the technical infrastructure for FAIR published research (meta)data. Within N4O a helpdesk will support data providers and developers to make data FAIR and LOUD, connect users and holders of data that is not open, and mediate licence issues between individual participants in N4O. To monitor the progress of licences, the N4O seeks close cooperation with NFDI4Memory (TA1), NFDI4Culture (TA5), NFDI4Earth and FAIRagro. This includes technical concepts for software containers to automatically extract licence, legal and provenance information, e.g. using FAIR Digital Objects (FDO).³⁶

N4O services will undergo regular quality assurance through systematic surveys, user feedback, anonymised usage statistics and patterns (TA7, M7.1), and monitoring progress of the N4O work programme. All deliverables will be agreed upon in the N4O Commons process (see section 3.4). For N4O, the recognition of source code as research data guarantees transparent processing and long-term reuse of FAIRification tools leading to an environment for sustainable research software.³⁷ This is essential for establishing FAIR principles in both research data and research software (FAIR4RS).³⁸ Code-based research data are made findable and reproducible by making their source code accessible via distributed version control systems, e.g. the git-based software solutions GitHub or GitLab. Because of the large community involved, research software engineering will follow the principles of agile software development, based on iterative and progressive procedures.

³⁶ Islam et al. 2020; Schwardmann 2020.

³⁷ Anzt et al. 2021.

³⁸ Chue Hong et al. 2022.

4.4 Services provided by the consortium

N4O provides technically and organisationally networked services that make knowledge resources available in cultural heritage authorities, universities, research institutions, archives, libraries and museums and enable access to and preservation of object-related (meta)data. These exist in analogue, digital or mixed forms. In addition, N4O sets quality requirements for content indexing, user- and machine-friendly access, technical equipment, international standards and effective FAIRification tools for data processing, analysis and LTA.

N4O will provide and develop a comprehensive range of community services that support the generation and (re)use of research data throughout the object data lifecycle (see section 4.1). This includes guidance on data infrastructure, methods and workflows for any type of user. Synergies between all services offered by N4O will foster cultural change in the way object data are handled in archaeological research. The foundations of digital research in the N4O Community will be transformed by the FAIRification of its research data.

The N4O services are based on a flexible, modular infrastructure that makes existing components interoperable using guidelines and common standards. Open source software principles will be used to develop agile, sustainable services and tools. N4O members engage in relevant national and international initiatives like CIDOC-CRM, OGC, ICOM and LIDO, to ensure that the services are interoperable.

In order to structure its portfolio clearly for its own community, and to facilitate the exchange and coordination of services with other consortia, the N4O services are divided into two major categories: (S1) Community, Support and Qualification services that focus on humans and (S2) FAIRification services that focus on data and systems. Through these types of services (see sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2) N4O members provide the components for a larger, object-specific infrastructure which enables users and data to comply with the FAIR principles.

Services that consortium members contribute as part of their institutional mission based on existing funding (underlined), are distinguished from new services that will be established within the NFDI framework (*italic*). Some services may become community standards after they have been approved by the N4O Commons process (see section 3.4). The following tables list the institutions responsible for providing a service in the long term, either by integrating it into its own service portfolio or by ensuring community-driven negotiations and procedures.

In sum, N4O includes well-established co-applicants that will be responsible for implementing most of these services (TA5) long term and with high quality, using the subject-specific and technical expertise that is brought together in TAs 1–4. In an agile process to constantly evaluate and adopt the portfolio of the services, N4O surveys the evolving needs and requirements of the community. Community Clusters (CC) across all TAs discuss these requirements in close exchange with the actual users.

4.4.1 Community, support and qualification services

The S1 category contains services that contribute to the N4O Commons in three ways. 1.) collections of written output, e.g. documentation, best practices, guidelines, workflows, evaluations, blue and white papers; 2.) catalogues of authority files, community-driven vocabularies, RDM FAIRification tools, standards, ontologies, datasets and repositories; 3.) materials for community engagement, knowledge transfer, qualification, education and training activities. Service types within this category are:

Catalogue and Registry Services (CRoS): CRoS are services to collect, catalogue, register and provide information about resources which are part of the AVS, IntS, SAS and DaS and are collected across the TAs. Thanks to consistent coverage, these resources will be more findable, accessible and reusable.

Qualification Services (QuoS): On the basis of a competence framework and qualification profiles derived from it, N4O offers OER, teaching concepts and appropriate placement formats conveying the services and outcomes of its work programme.

Support Services (SuS): SuS include 1st and 2nd level support for domain-specific issues and individual users of the N4O services, e.g. by providing best practices, workflows, handbooks and OER.

Relevant services are:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
N4O portal	SuS	TA7	DAI
Collection of written output	CreS	TA1-7	DAI
Catalogue of authority files and community-driven vocabularies	CreS	TA1-5	DAI / VZG
Catalogue of RDM FAIRification tools	CreS	TA1-5	DAI / VZG
Catalogue of standards and ontologies	CreS	TA1-5	DAI / VZG
Catalogue of datasets and repositories	CreS	TA1-5	DAI / VZG
Catalogue of quality criteria for object data	CreS	TA5	DAI / VZG
Qualification, education and training	QuaS	TA6	MUAS
Community engagement and knowledge transfer	SuS	TA6 / TA7	MUAS
2nd level support for storage, retrieval and discovery services	SuS	TA5	VZG / DAI

4.4.2 FAIRification services

FAIRification services of the S2 category can be assigned to FAIR aspects of object data and support the research data lifecycle in several sub-categories: data management services (S2.1), data capturing services (S2.2), data enrichment services (S2.3), data discovery services (S2.4), data connecting services (S2.5) and data preservation services (S2.6). Using the N4O Commons processes, N4O Communities will be actively involved in planning, developing and operating FAIRification services to ensure wide acceptance, usage and participation. Service types within this category are:

Support Services (SuS): In the context of FAIRification services, SuS include data management tools, RDM recommendations and templates, and related monitoring activities.

Authority File and Vocabulary Services (AVS): AVS help to improve the usage, referencing, alignment and harmonisation of authority files and community-driven vocabularies. Activities related to these services include formulating and inter-referencing object-specific concepts, editing data entries, providing datasets as LOD resources and implementing technical functionalities for exchange between research data and FAIR-compliant vocabularies. Thus, AVS primarily improve data interoperability and reusability.

Interoperability Services (IntS): IntS address the guidance, documentation and implementation of data models and ontologies, exchange formats, metadata standards, semantic data structures and interfaces, to enhance data interoperability and reusability.

Data Services (DaS): DaS provide and share research data from different stakeholders and domain-specific information systems (e.g. heritage, repository and collection databases) which use the AVS and IntS to integrate into DiS and make object-related data FAIRer.

Software Application Services (SAS): SAS comprise all stand-alone or web-based FLOSS software applications (e.g. tools, APIs and small scripts) which make research data FAIRer for both scientific users and research software engineers. SAS include best practices for research software engineering, documentation, technical specifications and source code publications of these applications.

Discovery Services (DiS): DiS enable user-friendly searches in distributed data sources with access control levels to query results. N4O will integrate these discovery services with DaS to create a knowledge graph. Both approaches help users to find and access hitherto hidden, unconnected and isolated datasets.

Storage Services (StoS): StoS provide physical storage facilities for research data produced within the N4O Community and include guidance for N4O-compliant storage facilities to secure the long-term FAIRness of object-related research data.

FAIRification Services as data management services (S2.1) comprise all steps to plan, design, validate and monitor research data with the aim to make it findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. N4O will provide these five services:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
IANUS.IT recommendations	SuS	TA5	DAI
Monitoring of RDM-related activities and community engagement	SuS	TA2	SPK
Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO)	SAS / SuS	TA5	DAI
Tools for the quality validation of object data	SAS	TA5	DAI
Concepts for FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) as machine-readable software bundles	SuS	TA7	DAI

FAIRification Services as data capturing services (S2.2) comprise tools for creating, editing and storing (primary) object data and are provided on different technical levels, e.g. community-specific repositories, community standards for documentation and protocols or demand-oriented software packages. Altogether they improve the accessibility, interoperability and reusability of new digital data and enable higher data quality for post-processing, evaluation and analysis. N4O will provide these 13 services:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
ArboDat+ – research tool and repository for archaeobotanical data	DaS / DiS	TA3	CAU
ArchaeoDocs and iDAI.field – expert systems for excavation documentation	DaS	TA5	VZG / DAI
Archaeometry service tool, protocols and laboratory standards	AVS / SAS / DiS	TA3	DBM
Concepts for interfaces of the ‘Sondengänger’ (detectorist) App	IntS / DiS	TA1, TA4, TA5	GDKE / VZG
Expert tool for data related to experimental archaeology, reconstructions and traceology	SAS / DaS / DiS	TA3	RGZM
GeoHist - research tool and repositories for georesources in human history	DaS / DiS	TA3	DBM
Goobi – workflow tool for retro digitalisation	SAS	TA5	VZG
KuniWeb – online collection management system	SAS / DaS	TA5	VZG
Ossobook and Anthrobook – research tools and repository for human and animal bones	DaS / DiS	TA3	CAU
Poseidon – research tool and repository for archaeogenetic data	DaS / DiS	TA3	CAU
Spacialist – virtual environment for space and object-related research	SAS	TA1	BCDH
Standards and processes for field, sensor and 3D data	SAS / IntS	TA1	LAD-BW / BCDH
survey2gis – data acquisition tool for offline processing of survey data	SAS	TA1	LAD-BW

FAIRification Services as data enrichment services (S2.3) comprise tools for modelling community-specific concepts, and for creating, managing and interlinking authority files and community-driven vocabularies. The main goals of these efforts are semantic alignment of datasets, enriching them with qualified references to other datasets, and expressing object data as interoperable knowledge representations, including aspects like fuzziness and wobbliness. These services increase the interoperability and reusability of resources and datasets provided as DaS. N4O will provide these 11 services:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
Academic meta tool – API for graph-based modelling of vagueness in research data	SAS / IntS	TA2	RGZM
Conservation process tool	SAS	TA3	RGZM

Continued on next page

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
DANTE	AVS / IntS / SAS / DiS	TA1-5	VZG
Enriched and semantically aligned norm/authority data and ontologies	AVS / DaS	TA1-5	VZG / DAI
iDAI.chronontology	AVS / IntS	TA1-5	DAI
iDAI.gazetteer	AVS / IntS	TA1-5	DAI
re3dragon – lookup and resolve tool for LOD resources	SAS / DiS / CReS	TA1-5	RGZM
Recommendations and best practices for knowledge modelling	IntS / QuaS	TA1-5	RGZM
Research toolkit for knowledge modelling	SAS / IntS	TA1-5	RGZM / MPIWG
RGZM conservation thesaurus and ontology	AVS / IntS	TA4	RGZM
Standards and interfaces for interdisciplinary knowledge modelling	IntS	TA1-5	RGZM / MPIWG

FAIR data discovery services (S2.4) collect and index data about objects and their domain-specific contexts from a variety of sources. These services include concepts for PIDs and access levels, web applications as technical solutions using either a knowledge graph or mechanism to integrate data from heterogeneous, distributed resources. To make objects findable and accessible, N4O will provide these five services:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
Concept of object-specific persistent and globally unique identifiers	IntS	TA5	DAI / VZG
Definition of information access levels	DiS	TA1-7	DAI / VZG
Discovery system and knowledge graph as single access point	DiS	TA5	VZG
Lukida: GUI for rich metadata discovery services	DiS	TA5	VZG
Service for retrieving objects across distributed systems	DiS	TA2 / TA4	VZG

FAIR data preservation services (S2.6) offer concepts and systems for LTA of legacy data and ensure that, after the project funding ends, the data will be accessible and reusable. N4O will provide these two services:

Service name	Type(s)	Addressed in	Responsibility
Enhancing the sustainability of legacy data	StoS	TA1	LAD-BW
IANUS.LZA	StoS	TA5	DAI

4.4.3 The N4O service within a broader context

All N4O services are embedded in a landscape of national and international solutions, developments, services and infrastructures. N4O uses these existing components as appropriate and integrates them into its own new or improved services. The aim is to close specific gaps, so, where services exist, no new services will be developed. Instead, the focus is on integration, substantive strengthening and development of existing services. In many cases, members of the CCs are actively involved, cementing close personal, professional and technical links from which N4O can benefit. Consortium members are active in international fora and infrastructure services, which ensures that N4O services are compatible within Germany, Europe and beyond. If a member of the consortium is responsible for one of these services, that member provides and develops the service independently, i.e. outside the funding and work programme of N4O. These can be categorised into research data services which provide heterogeneous object data in several formats, and (generic and specialised) research software services supporting the management of object-related research data. The lists below give a snapshot of the services that are currently relevant, but this can change over time due to new developments, projects, policies and proposals. Within an open and agile process members of the N4O Community can extend these lists within the planned catalogues of datasets, repositories and FAIRification tools.

Research Data Services: ADABweb (NLDP); African Red Slip Ware Digital Data (ARS3D) (RGZM); archaeology.link platform (RGZM); calpal (RGZM); Corpus of Roman Finds in the European Barbaricum (DAI/RGK); Datenbank Bauforschung/Restaurierung (LD-BW); Europeana (platform); FID Propylaeum (Uni Heidelberg); Graffiti auf römischen Goldmünzen Daten (SFB 933) (Uni Heidelberg); Graffiti-Portal (Uni Heidelberg); iDAI.bibliography (Zenon) (DAI); iDAI.geoserver (DAI); iDAI.objects (DAI); Inscriptiones Graecae (BBAW); K10plus-Zentral (VZG); kerameikos (platform); Ku-LaDig; Linked Open Samian Ware Data (RGZM); lod.academy platform (AdW Mainz); museum-digital.de; NAVIS Database (RGZM); nomisma (platform); numid.online (Portal); numiscience.de (e-learning platform); Numismatisches Portal Baden-Württemberg (platform); recherche.smb.museum (Update von SMB-digital); RGZM collection management system (easydb); Samian Research (online database) (RGZM); smb-digital.de (Portal); TraCEr (RGZM); Wikimedia Universe (community-driven media hub)

Research Software Services: ARCHAIDE (EU); ARIADNE; AV-Portal (TIB); Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies and Classifications (BARTOC); Baureka.Online Storage (FIZ Karlsruhe); CLARIAH-DE; Cocoda / coli-conc; dasis (RGZM); Data acquisition tool for online processing of geoinformation: tachy2gis; Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek; digiCULT.web and digiCULT.xTree; DIMAG (GDE); F-UJI (FAIR Research Data Object Assessment Tool); FAIR Aware; Graphikportal; Heidelberg Storage and Publication Services (UB Heidelberg); Labeling System (mainzed); Linked Open Vocabularies Catalogue; Linked Pipes (software catalogue); MonArch (Uni Passau); open-archaeo; OpenAIRE; OpenDataServer (VZG) (grant application); Pelagios Commons / Recogito / Peripleo; RADAR (FIZ Karlsruhe); re3data; MyCore repository software (VZG); RGZM Alligator; RGZM Archaeological Data Processing Web Services (ADP); TemaTres; WissKI

5 Work Programme

With strict adherence to its RDM strategy, N4O's task areas have been designed to leverage existing expertise and align with the current research processes on object biographies.

TA1 is composed of the disciplines that work directly on the detection, discovery and description of traces of human activity. They generate data in mostly born-digital documentation processes on a daily basis. In field work a massive amount of data is generated on a global scale, feeding object information into the flow of object-related research. The measures of TA1 are oriented on the one hand to the necessary steps for harmonising standards and specifications of formats, models and metadata for primary documentation data (M1.1, M1.6), and on the other hand to recording technologies (M1.2, M1.3, M1.4) and the provision of requirements for the integration of legacy data (M1.5). The management of information on the storage and exhibition of objects provides the necessary supplements to the data from TA1. The focus of TA2's measures is on solving challenges posed by the operation of isolated, proprietary and non-interoperable collection management systems and domain specific research collections (M2.1, M2.2) that prevent data from being opened up for overarching infrastructural aggregation (M2.1, M2.2). In this context, TA2 is working on topics concerning the provenance of objects and corresponding requirements for gradual accessibility (M2.1). It is also stipulating standards for enriched metadata and specifications of interfaces for feeding into distributed object collection and major union systems (M2.1-M2.3). TA3 supplements the data with the results of scientific analysis methods, which add information on the origin, production and use of the object. The measures are primarily aimed at the planning, development and provision of necessary repositories and services derived from existing databases (M3.1-M3.4), which can be interlinked internationally and within the NFDI. They will be supplemented by comprehensive documents on protocols and guidelines, which will also serve as a basis to evaluate data quality (M3.5). The final stage in an object's biography is its sustainable preservation. This task falls to public authorities, such as heritage management offices, who are engaged in TA4. By bridging the federal challenges, they will contribute essential information to the consortium and participate in measures that will make data accessible and interoperable (M4.1-M4.4). Expertise in restoration and conservation that represent another important research data stock (M4.1-M4.4) is provided in TA4 as well.

TAs 5 to 7 are engaged with TAs 1 to 4 in the subsections "preserve, discover, integrate, analyze, publish, qualify and plan" of the RDM cycle and take care of overarching needs of the consortium. TA5 develops an already existing service for long-term archiving further (M5.1) and provides terminology services previously established in the community (M5.3), which interweave different vocabularies and concepts, thus making the existing data on objects centrally discoverable (M5.4, M5.5), FAIR (M5.2), citable and reusable as well (M5.5). The measures also include the continued development of important additional services that ensure the spatial and temporal reference of information (M5.3). TA6 provides the framework for the integration of data to a comprehensive object biography (M6.3, M6.4) and coordinates the creation and dissemination of teaching material (M6.1, M6.2) to enable researchers and the wider interested community to use the provided services. The measures in TA6 and TA7 implement the components described in Chapter 3.4 by connecting overarching thematic branches (M6.5, M7.2), providing a sound and transparent basis for the work of the consortium (M7.1, M7.4), and enabling the community to be more closely involved with regard to other consortia and internationally (M7.3; supported by a shared measure in Task Areas 1-5: M1.7, M2.4, M5.6).

Table 5.0: Overview of task areas

Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-Spokesperson
TA1: *	M1.1 Field Data: processes and standards M1.2 Remote sensing and sensor data: processes and standards M1.3 Georeferenced 3D data: processes and standards M1.4 Spatiotemporal data: processes and standards M1.5 Enhancing the sustainability of legacy data M1.6 Harmonisation and mapping of TA-specific authority files M1.7 Commons contribution and coordination	David Bibby Dr. Matthias Lang
TA2: **	M2.1 Data interoperability and exchange for collection research M2.2 Data standardisation and knowledge modelling for collection research M2.3 Services and tools for collection research M2.4 Commons contribution and coordination	Prof. Dr. Alexandra Busch Prof. Dr. Christina Haak
TA3: ***	M3.1 Data models and interfaces: development, curation and enhancement M3.2 From geoarchaeology to artefact: process-related archaeometry and material sciences M3.3 Humans, plants and animals as agents and resources M3.4 Experiments, reconstruction, replication and reproduction M3.5 Commons contribution and coordination	Prof. Dr. Matthias Renz Prof. Dr. Thomas Stöllner
TA4: ****	M4.1 Interfaces and standards for availability of monument and restoration-related data M4.2 Mapping monument and restoration-related community-driven vocabularies and ontologies M4.3 Specifying web-based (geo)services for monument and restoration-related data M4.4 Commons contribution and coordination	Christian Eckmann Dr. Ulrich Himmelmann
TA5: *****	M5.1 Provide core services for subject-specific LTA (IANUS, baureka.online) including provision of tools for creation of data management plans (RDMO) and develop/scale these services as required M5.2 Quality assurance of N4O data through curation and validation M5.3 IT services for authority and metadata from TA1–4 M5.4 Discovery system as single access point for subject-specific information M5.5 Provision and networking of N4O data M5.6 Commons contribution and coordination	Frank Dürkohp Henriette Senst
Continued on next page		

Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-Spokesperson
TA6: *****	M6.1 Data skills: establishing prerequisites M6.2 Qualification: meeting all community needs M6.3 Improving integration and harmonisation of N4O data M6.4 Objects in context: modelling the interdisciplinary research cycle on objects M6.5 Commons contribution and coordination	Prof. Dr. Kai-Christian Bruhn Dr. Dirk Wintergrün
TA7: *****	M7.1 Administrative coordination M7.2 N4O Helpdesk and website M7.3 Governance processes and N4O Commons M7.4 Service integration and supervision	Dr. Philipp von Rummel

- * TA1 is relevant for NFDI4Culture, Text+ and NFDI4Memory using 3D documentation methods and providing information on historical sources or objects as text media
- ** TA2 is relevant to NFDI4Culture by means of Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums not covered by N4O.
- *** TA3 is relevant to NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Earth, GHGA, FAIRAgro and other consortia handling data from the natural sciences.
- **** TA 4 is relevant to NFDI4Earth through the geographical reference of sites/monuments. Additionally, it is relevant to NFDI4Culture since TA Protecting refers to "cultural heritage". There are relations with FAIRmat, due to the importance of material analyses in the field of restoration.
- ***** TA 5 is relevant to all NFDI consortia, since issues and solutions of storage, access and dissemination are thematically anchored in each consortium. In this respect, the specific relations to the consortia of the MoU group are to be emphasised.
- ***** TA 6 is relevant for all NFDI consortia, providing qualification materials and developing an umbrella conceptual metadata schema.
- ***** TA 7 is relevant for all NFDI consortia in offering access to the commons for cross cutting topics and by representing N4O within the whole NFDI and with respect to the communication with the NFDI Directorate.

5.1 Task Area 1: Documentation

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
Landesamt für Denkmalpflege im Regierungspräsidium Stuttgart	David Bibby
University of Bonn	Dr. Matthias Lang

5.1.1 Brief description and aims

TA1 deals with the data that exist at the outset of object research. Tools and technologies which accompany the entire digital documentation process will be made available to the community via this TA. To this end, existing tools and standards must first be evaluated and then communicated (G1.1, N4O Objective 1). New tools and standards will be developed within TA1 to address unresolved issues in the documentation process (G1.2, N4O Objective 3). TA1 will ensure that these solutions are available open access, are curated and are continually adapted to technical innovations and changing requirements.

With TAs 2–6, TA1 will analyse and evaluate existing thesauri and classification systems, make them available on a sustainable basis and extend them to meet community requirements (G1.4, N4O Objectives 3, 4). Moreover, TA1 will develop standards for generating and harmonising different types of primary documentation data (G1.1, G1.2, N4O Objective 3). TA1 will also convert legacy datasets, which are partly still available only in analogue form, partly in undocumented, non-standardised and/or proprietary formats (and thus not suitable for LTA: G1.3, G1.5, N4O Objective 2), and develop strategies for feeding these sets into the data lifecycle.

TA1 will actively support users to store only datasets that merit LTA (N4O Objective 1) without loss of information. TA1 addresses important aspects of the N4O RDM strategy by developing and consolidating metadata schemas for survey, field and collection data, exploratory and survey records, and sensor data. Additionally, TA1 fosters the integration of data into higher-level documentation processes and data quality assurance (see section 4.2). Finally, TA1 will develop guidelines, manuals and OER (G1.6, N4O Objective 5). These activities will integrate and harmonise data; develop versioned, publishable and citable data and contribute to the FAIRification of data for N4O and beyond.

5.1.2 Goals of TA1

Goal	Description
G1.1	Establish method-specific and cross-method standards to produce and harmonise primary documentation data in the community.
G1.2	Provide a user-friendly and appropriate tool to enable easy acquisition and processing of complex geo, 3D and technical data.
G1.3	Catalogue quality criteria for documenting archivable data and data worth preserving.
G1.4	Harmonise and map vocabularies to describe and document (meta)data.
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Goal	Description
G1.5	Develop well-documented sustainable strategies to convert non-valid, proprietary and insufficient data into data worth preserving.
G1.6	Develop multimodal guidelines for producing and handling primary documentation data and make these available in the N4O Commons.

5.1.3 Measures and tasks in TA1

M1.1 Field data: processes and standards – G1.1, G1.2, G1.5 The N4O Consortium brings together specialisms and disciplines that use a variety of technical documentation methods to generate research data that are heterogeneous in content and structure. In this measure, standards for producing and/or harmonising primary documentation data will be created and established across disciplines. In this process, links to practice are essential and are ensured by user participation in the tasks. The standards for data formats and interfaces will link and exchange heterogenous data from different sources, metadata, vocabularies, mapped thesauri and data structures.

Tasks in M1.1	
T1.1.1	Catalogue and evaluate existing standards and tools for field data
T1.1.2	Develop and harmonise standards for archaeological prospection, excavations and field surveys
T1.1.3	Harmonise, develop and ensure interoperability of data capture tools
T1.1.4	Analyse requirements for standards and services for historical building research
User stories for M1.1	ID 35,; ID 52, ID 53, ID 54, ID 65
TRAILS related with M1.1	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data
Participants in M1.1	ID 3, ID 31, ID 34, ID 35, ID 38, ID 40

M1.2 Remote sensing and sensor data: processes and standards – G1.1, G1.2

The aim of this measure is to develop strategies for exchange of storage-intensive raw data from remote sensing and sensor technology. This includes harmonising standards and developing interfaces for integrating sensor and remote sensing data, which will help to create data acquisition tools and harmonise with GIS systems, thus encouraging open source development of this type of data.

Tasks in M1.2	
T1.2.1	Catalogue and evaluate existing standards and tools for remote sensing and sensor technology
T1.2.2	Develop and harmonise standards for remote sensing and sensor technology
Continued on next page	

Tasks in M1.2	
T1.2.3	Harmonise and ensure interoperability of processing software for remote sensing and sensor technology
User stories for M1.2	ID 35, ID 51, ID 39, ID 40, ID 57, ID 60, ID 62, ID 63
TRAILS related with M1.2	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data TRAIL 1.2 Archaeological remote sensing in the Roman Rhineland
Participants in M1.2	ID 12, ID 19, ID 34, ID 35, ID 36, ID 50

M1.3 Georeferenced 3D data: processes and standards – G1.1, G1.2, G1.3

This measure will develop standards for capturing and processing georeferenced 3D data. It develops solutions for two closely related and complex tasks. Georeferencing is becoming more mobile and diverse, but its quality must be closely adapted to the degree of accuracy required for documentation. All parameters contributing to the calculation of a 3D coordinates must therefore be described and recorded, especially in destructive documentation processes, to be used in photogrammetric and computer vision methods for 3D data acquisition. In a market dominated by commercial suppliers, only a few open source tools are capable of providing the entire data collection and evaluation process for sustainable data management. The same holds true for corresponding metadata schemas and vocabularies. This measure will develop tools to collect and evaluate 3D data.

Tasks in M1.3	
T1.3.1	Catalogue and evaluate existing standards and tools for 3D data
T1.3.2	Develop and harmonise standards for capturing, documenting and processing contextualised 3D data
T1.3.3	Evaluate and develop tools to generate and produce 3D data
User stories for M1.3	ID 9, ID 13, ID 35, ID 50, ID 51, ID 58, ID 83
TRAILS related with M1.3	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data
Participants in M1.3	ID 3, ID 21, ID 31, ID 34, ID 36

M1.4 Spatiotemporal data: processes and standards – G1.1, G1.2 This measure will set standards for representing complex space-time relationships in GIS-supported systems on the basis of standardised geodata. This includes standardising processes in archaeological data capture systems and for documenting projects at a higher level. Another aim is to integrate elements of relative and absolute chronology with common representations of geodata.

Tasks in M1.4	
T1.4.1	Catalogue and evaluate existing standards and tools for chronological concepts and geodata
T1.4.2	Develop and harmonise standards for capturing, documenting and processing complex geodata
T1.4.3	Evaluate and develop tools to integrate chronological concepts and geodata
User stories for M1.4	ID 35, ID 39, ID 40, ID 57; ID 58, ID 60, ID 62, ID 63
TRAILS related with M1.4	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data
Participants in M1.4	ID 31, ID 40

M1.5 Enhancing the sustainability of legacy data – G1.3, G1.5 This measure will develop criteria for assessing which data are both archivable and worth preserving. M1.5 will also convert analogue and non-standard proprietary, inadequately documented legacy datasets into interoperable ones suitable for LTA, transferring them into valid and standardised forms that can be integrated into services provided by N4O.

Tasks in M1.5	
T1.5.1	Define archivable data and data worth preserving in a catalogue of criteria
T1.5.2	Establish strategies for converting non-valid, proprietary and insufficiently documented data into data worth preserving
User stories for M1.5	ID 35, ID 49, ID 51, ID 56, ID 37, ID 92; ID 95, ID 96, ID 38, ID 52
TRAILS related with M1.5	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data
Participants in M1.5	ID 21, ID 31, ID 38

M1.6 Harmonisation and mapping of TA-specific authority files – G1.4 Existing authority files are harmonised by mapping the cross-links between them across the TAs. For this purpose, technical standards will be developed to enable subject-specific mapping and alignment by proven experts in specific disciplines and methods.

Tasks in M1.6	
T1.6.1	Catalogue and systematise existing authority files
T1.6.2	Map the individual sets of authority files
T1.6.3	Develop and provide authority files
Continued on next page	

Tasks in M1.6	
User stories for M1.6	ID 9, ID 13, ID 35, ID 49, ID 51, ID 56; ID 37, ID 39, ID 57, ID 58, ID 60, ID 62, ID 63, ID 83, ID 92, ID 38, ID 52, ID 95, ID 96, ID 53, ID 54, ID 65;, ID 50, ID 58
TRAILs related with M1.6	TRAIL 1.1 Directory and evaluation of existing tools, standards and data
Participants in M1.6	ID 21, ID 31, ID 35, ID 41, ID 45

M1.7 Commons contribution and coordination – G1.6 In M1.7, qualified specialists develop multimedia and multimodal guidelines covering all requirements and steps in object documentation. With N4O Community involvement, these guidelines will be tailored to potential user groups: staff in public institutions and at universities, students and volunteers assisting the heritage authorities.

All subsections of the guidelines will be held centrally, continuously developed and supplemented. The aim is not to standardise but rather to harmonise documentation procedures, which will lead to sustainably reusable and interoperable datasets and thus do justice to the objects, making them more findable and accessible.

This measure, with TA6 and TA7, promotes coherent N4O Community work across all TAs. Standards and specifications, training material and measures will be developed in a coordinated manner. Cross-cutting topics will be worked on at organisational level. These joint activities and shared structures will guarantee that all data-generating research processes are mapped to the data management lifecycle.

Tasks in M1.7	
T1.7.1	Build community
T1.7.2	Establish common ground: standards, protocols and guidelines for documentation and fieldwork
T1.7.3	Develop and pilot training concepts
T1.7.4	Actively mediate between expert and community clusters: science meets the public
T1.7.5	Enable internal consortium coordination and knowledge transfer
T1.7.6	Develop demand-oriented models for services in TA1
User stories for M1.1	ID 51, ID 65;, ID 66, ID 67
TRAILs related with M1.1	-
Participants in M1.1	This measure is shared by all the TAs: each co-applicant and each participant is integrated into it.

5.1.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA1

ID	Description
KPI1.1.1	By 2026, primary documentation data standards are formulated according to community needs (with proposals approved by the GA) and developed for all steps in the documentation process.
KPI1.1.2	By the end of 2023, documentation of the first developed standards is made accessible (with TA6) in the N4O Commons.
KPI1.1.3	By the end of 2024/early 2025, an N4O Community survey shows that the first developed standards are known to 50% of the community and actively used by 25% of the community.
KPI1.2.1	By the end of 2023, documentation tools for a completely media break-free digital workflow are developed and made available (with TA6) in the N4O Commons.
KPI1.2.2	By the end of 2024/early 2025, an N4O Community survey shows that the tools provided by N4O are accepted as standard by 25% of the community and actively used.
KPI1.3.1	By the end of 2023, a catalogue of criteria for creating archivable data and data worth preserving is developed (with TA5) and made available (with TA6) in the N4O Commons.
KPI1.3.2	By the end of 2024/early 2025, an N4O Community survey shows that the catalogue of criteria is accepted as standard by 50% of the community and actively applied.
KPI1.4.1	By mid-2022, a TWG to harmonise and map authority files is established, and continues to confer regularly until 2026.
KPI1.4.2	By the end of 2023, a catalogue of existing authority files is compiled (with TAs 2-5) and made available (with TA6) in the N4O Commons.
KPI1.4.3	By the end of 2025, the mapped vocabularies are available in open access in a service operated by TA5 and can be integrated into the recording tools via an interface.
KPI1.4.4	By the end of 2024, the published vocabularies are known to 50% of the community, as demonstrated by an N4O Community survey.
KPI1.5.1	By mid-2025, strategies are developed for converting non-valid, proprietary and insufficiently documented data into data which is both archivable data and worth preserving.
KPI1.5.2	By the end of 2025, the developed strategies are made available (with TA6) in the N4O Commons.
KPI1.5.3	By the end of 2025, (with TAs 5-7) a consulting concept for dealing with old data stocks is developed and implemented.
KPI1.5.4	By the end of 2024, the published strategies are known to 50% of the community as demonstrated by an N4O Community survey.
KPI1.6.1	By mid-2023, guidelines are conceptualised with the other TAs (especially TA6) in a community-driven process.
KPI1.6.2	By the end of 2024, the guidelines are available to the community.
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ID	Description
KPI1.6.3	By December 2024/early 2025, an N4O Community survey shows that the guidelines are known to 50% of the community and actively applied by 25% of the community.

5.1.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

There are links to TA2 on contextualising collection objects, insofar as these are archaeology/building history artefacts. There are also close bilateral links to TA4: TA1 generates primary documentation data in situ during data capture, while TA4 deals with processing, interpreting, systematising and supplementing this data in the context of heritage conservation and scholarship. With TA6, technical and content-related documentation, archiving standards and tools developed in TA1 and TA5 will be communicated to the community and established, taking user feedback into account.

5.2 Task Area 2: Collecting

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum – Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology (RGZM)	Prof. Dr. Alexandra Busch
Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz (SPK)	Prof. Dr. Christina Haak

5.2.1 Brief description and aims

To enable systems for research collections to exchange data based on common standards, four measures are planned. Specific standards for the interoperability between collection management systems, domain-specific research collections and provenance research, as well as standards simplifying integration into major union systems are developed in a community-driven process in M2.1 (G2.1, G2.3). Authority files and vocabularies enriched and aligned by community-driven processes in M2.2 will improve the interoperability of systems for research collections (G2.1, G2.2, G2.3). Data discovery services (S2.4) for retrieving objects across distributed research collections and domain-specific object data hubs are provided by M2.3 (G2.2, G2.3). Knowledge is transferred (M2.4) into the N4O Community in close collaboration with TA6 and TA7 (G2.1, G2.2, G2.3). Within the N4O RDM strategy, TA2 addresses all issues in relation to collections. A considerable number of FAIRification services (S2) are made available to the consortium within this TA, incorporating collection management systems and domain-specific research collections from a wide range of disciplines. TA2 will ensure interoperability of the related (meta)data using LOD principles. These activities will integrate and harmonise data and lead to the development of versioned, publishable and citable data products which are the core of the envisaged knowledge graph and contribute to the LOD Cloud as part of the Semantic Web. Thus TA2 contributes to the FAIRification of collection data associated with N4O.

5.2.2 Goals of TA2

Goal	Description
G2.1	Enable collection researchers and curators to use documented tools, data and systems in their daily work to describe and discover objects.
G2.2	Enhance data from research collections with qualified references by using commonly accepted and semantically aligned authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies based on domain-specific knowledge modelling.
G2.3	Enable systems for research collections to exchange data through common community standards for interoperability.

5.2.3 Measures and tasks in TA2

M2.1 Data interoperability and exchange for collection research This measure will enable collection management systems and domain-specific research collections to exchange data through common standards (G2.3), and support stakeholders using interoperable systems in their daily work (G2.1) (N4O Objective 2, 3). For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Definition of data access and authorisation levels (DiS) in white papers (T2.1.1)
- Catalogue of standards and ontologies (CReS) created by entering data in a registry for data exchange formats and knowledge modelling concepts relating to collection research (T2.1.2–5)
- Definition of interfaces for the exchange of data between heterogeneous systems (IntS) realised by white and blue papers to review existing ontologies and data formats (e.g. CIDOC-CRM, LIDO, JSKOS, EDM) and to describe and enhance domain-specific data reference models as a solid basis for data exchange between systems relevant for collection research (T2.1.1–5).

Tasks in M2.1	
T2.1.1	Define different data access and authorisation levels to fulfil legal, ethical or research strategy requirements across different collection research domains
T2.1.2	Improve and implement TA-specific standards, required meta-data fields and specifications for collection management systems and domain-specific research collections
T2.1.3	Improve and implement TA-specific standards and specifications to improve the integration of distributed systems for research collections into domain-specific object data hubs
T2.1.4	Improve and implement TA-specific standards for research collections and provenance research to improve the integration of distributed systems for research collections into major and object collection union systems
T2.1.5	Create and establish TA-specific standards and specifications for RDM in provenance research
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Tasks in M2.1	
User stories for M2.1	ID 16, ID 49; ID 17, ID 45, ID 69;, ID 18, ID 20, ID 33, ID 41; ID 29, ID 31; ID 38, ID 46, ID 47, ID 59, ID 72;, ID 90, ID 96, ID 98
TRAILS related with M2.1	TRAIL 2.1 Environment Analysis TRAIL 2.3 Semantic Interoperability TRAIL 2.4 Provenance Research
Participants in M2.1	ID 5, ID 11, ID 16, ID 29, ID 36, ID 48, ID 50, ID 58

M2.2 Data standardisation and knowledge modelling for collection research

This measure will enable collection management systems and domain-specific research collections to exchange data through authority files and community-driven vocabularies (G2.3), so stakeholders can use interoperable data in their daily work (G2.1), and link data from research collections by generally accepted, semantically aligned authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies, using domain-specific knowledge modelling approaches (G2.2) (N4O Objective 2, 3). For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Catalogue of standards and ontologies, of authority files and community-driven vocabularies, of datasets and repositories (CreS) by entering data in a registry, powered by DANTE and BAROC in TA5, for knowledge modelling, entity identification concepts, collection and provenance research data (T2.2.1)
- Enriched and semantically aligned authority files and community-driven vocabularies for standardisation (AVS/DaS) by creating new records in authoritative systems (e.g. GND, ISIL) and enriching data from specific research collections (e.g. Otfried von Vacanos Typenindex, Linked Open Samian Ware Data, Graffiti auf römischen Goldmünzen of SFB 933, IKMK, NAVIS) (T2.2.2–3)
- Ingest of data into union systems (InS/DiS/SuS) realised by entering enriched/linked data into major and object collection union systems (e.g. Europeana, DDB, Wikimedia Universe, museum-digital, numid.online), and a white paper documenting best-practice workflows (T2.2.2–3)
- Standards, transform rules and interfaces for interdisciplinary knowledge modelling, including aspects of fuzzy semantics (IntS/QuaS) realised by white papers, blue papers and OER, to develop FAIRification tools in M2.3 (T2.2.4)

Tasks in M2.2	
T2.2.1	Catalogue and semantically align existing authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies in research collections
T2.2.2	Create and develop interoperable authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies for research collections as well as major and collection union systems
T2.2.3	Create and develop interoperable authority files and community-driven vocabularies for research collections and provenance research
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Tasks in M2.2	
T2.2.4	Create and implement TA-specific standards, interfaces and domain-specific aspects of knowledge modelling in research collections and provenance research
User stories for M2.2	ID 19, ID 32, ID 97, ID 98, ID 99, ID 20, ID 34, ID 23, ID 28, ID 30, ID 31, ID 35, ID 45, ID 48
TRAILS related with M2.2	TRAIL 2.1 Environment Analysis TRAIL 2.2 Fuzzy Best Practice TRAIL 2.3 Semantic Interoperability TRAIL 2.4 Provenance Research TRAIL 2.5 Iconography Wikimedia TRAIL 4.2 Mapping
Participants in M2.2	ID 1, ID 4, ID 5, ID 8, ID 15, ID 26, ID 33, ID 40, ID 44, ID 46, ID 48, ID 53, ID 57

M2.3 Services and tools for collection research Based on the deliverables of M2.1 and M2.2, this measure will enable stakeholders to use FAIRification services daily to describe and discover objects in research collections (G2.1), a task that requires enriched FAIR data (G2.2) and interoperable systems (G2.3). Therefore, the measure will provide low-threshold applications for implementing data identification and enhancement standards, by supporting the semantic alignment of authority files and community-driven vocabularies and by handling domain-specific aspects of knowledge modelling (including fuzziness and wobbliness). For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Catalogue of RDM tools (CreS) by entering data in a N4O-specific registry, provided by TA6 (M6.3) und TA7, and in international established registers (e.g. open-archaeo, Linked Pipes) (T2.3.1)
- FAIRification tools for managing knowledge modelling (SAS) by developing and implementing existing software and API solutions (e.g. WissKI, re3dragon, Academic Meta Tool) (T2.3.2)
- FAIRification tools for managing fuzzy wobbling semantics (SAS) by developing existing software (e.g. Cocoda) (T2.3.3)
- Service for retrieving objects across distributed research collections (DiS) by developing a collection-specific data discovery service (S2.4) (T2.3.4)

Tasks in M2.3	
T2.3.1	Catalogue existing services and tools for the FAIRification of research collections and provenance research
T2.3.2	Implement and improve FAIRification tools for aspects of domain-specific knowledge modelling in collection research
T2.3.3	Implement and improve FAIRification tools for managing data quality and semantic alignments in authority files and community-driven vocabularies for research collections and provenance research
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Tasks in M2.3	
T2.3.4	Implement and improve FAIRification tools for retrieving objects across distributed research collections and domain-specific object data hubs
User stories for M2.3	ID 19, ID 36, ID 95, ID 97, ID 21, ID 24, ID 25, ID 26, ID 27, ID 30; ID 34, ID 41, ID 45, ID 69, ID 92, ID 93, ID 46, ID 47, ID 59, ID 72, ID 76
TRAILS related with M2.3	TRAIL 2.2 Fuzzy Best Practice TRAIL 2.6 Vagueness Modelling Tool TRAIL 2.7 LOD Lookup Resolve Tool TRAIL 4.2 Mapping TRAIL 4.3 Geo-Service
Participants in M2.3	ID 5, ID 15, ID 33, ID 40, ID 53, ID 57

M2.4 Commons contribution and coordination The aim of this measure is knowledge transfer concerning community-driven standards for data exchange, object identification and data enrichment methods to create needs-based services for collection research (N4O Objective 1, 5). Through its incorporation into the Coordination Office (TA7), M2.4 ensures dovetailing with activities in N4O as a whole. Moreover, TA2 will share knowledge specific to research collections with other NFDI consortia, in particular with NFDI4Culture, and TA1 on 3D metadata for objects in collections. This measure will convey the knowledge aspects related to G2.1, G2.2 and G2.3.

For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Collection of written output (CreS) like documentation, best practices, guidelines, workflows and evaluation reports which are uploaded into the N4O Commons platform, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T2.4.2)
- Catalogue of authority files and community-driven vocabularies, RDM and FAIRification tools, standards and ontologies, and datasets and repositories (CreS) created by entering data in a N4O-specific catalogue service, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T2.4.2)
- Concepts for semantic and technical integration and alignment of object descriptions (IntS/PaS) generated by entering white and blue papers in the N4O Commons, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T2.4.2)
- Tools for managing knowledge modelling, including fuzzy wobbling semantics (SAS) produced by research software engineering, documentation and training, coordinated by TA6 and TA7 (2.4.2/3)
- Qualification, education and training (QuaS) delivered by providing OER and organising interactive workshops, with TA6 (T2.4.3)
- Community engagement and knowledge transfer (SuS) through engagement in cluster discussions and community outreach, coordinated by TA7 (T2.4.1/4)

Tasks in M2.4	
T2.4.1	Build community, mediate and support CCs and TWGs
T2.4.2	Establish common ground: create services for research collections
T2.4.3	Develop and pilot training concepts
T2.4.4	Enable internal consortium coordination and knowledge transfer
User stories for M2.4	ID 42, ID 44, ID 45, ID 48
TRAILS related with M2.4	The tasks in M2.4 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M2.4	ID 1, ID 5, ID 14, ID 40, ID 53

5.2.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA2

ID	Description
KPI2.1	By mid-2024, people involved in research collections formulate requirements and community needs in a TWG organised in N4O and successfully submit a proposal for approval by the GA, resulting in a domain-specific product backlog.
KPI2.2	By mid-2024 a TWG organised in N4O identifies (data) services and generic tools for research collections and provenance research resulting in an international online catalogue that reflects domain-specific community needs.
KPI2.3	By mid-2027, 1.0 versions of the tools and their documentation are accessible.
KPI2.4	By the end of 2027, the FAIRly accessible research software source code, usage of the tools and services and the associated documentation is cited more than 20 times in scientific papers.
KPI2.5	Between 2024 and 2027, at least two (virtual) workshops per year are held on authority files, community-driven vocabularies, ontologies and semantic modelling.
KPI2.6	By 2024, a TWG has identified domain-specific authority files, vocabularies and ontologies resulting in an online catalogue which reflect the domain-specific community needs.
KPI2.7	By 2025, improved or newly developed authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies are findable in international interdisciplinary authority catalogues.
KPI2.8	By 2027 at least 10 systems for research collections are using the community specific exchange standard and at least five linked collection research repositories are using the community specific standards related to fuzziness and wobbliness.
KPI2.9	By mid-2026, 1.0 versions of improved authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies are accessible in interoperable formats.
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ID	Discription
KPI2.10	Between 2023 and 2027, at least two (virtual) workshops per year are held on standardising tasks for interoperable systems exchanging data.
KPI2.11	By 2024, a TWG organised in N4O identifies domain-specific tasks for interoperable systems exchanging data and defining information access levels resulting in white papers and blue papers which reflect the domain-specific community needs.
KPI2.12	By 2025, improved or newly developed standards for interoperable data exchange are integrated into the N4O Commons (with the help of TA7).
KPI2.13	By the end of 2027, 1.0 versions of improved or newly developed recommendations are accessible as white papers and blue papers.

5.2.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

Recommendations for handling knowledge modelling, e.g. fuzziness and wobbliness, will be developed with TA1, to counter the lack of standardisation in fieldwork documentation methods for data comprising vague or uncertain elements. Handling of uncertainty is a requirement not only in the collection research community (TA2), but also in analytics and experiments (TA3), where conclusions and interpretations based on interpolated and aggregated data are often affected by accuracy issues. TA2 is cooperating with TA4 to enrich authority files and community-driven vocabularies, and to improve semantic alignment tools managing chronological and geospatial information. As part of the ontology and the data enrichment service for conservation processes (TA4), developing community standards for handling vocabularies is pivotal. TA2, TA5 and their partners will collaborate on aspects of research software engineering, and on discovery tools specific to collection research, semantic term alignment services and FAIRification tools for creating and/or improving authority files and community-driven vocabularies. With TA6 and TA7, TA2 will transfer knowledge in M2.4 (e.g. creating OER, guidelines, manuals and documentation; workshops and training).

5.3 Task Area 3: Analytics and Experiments

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum – Leibniz Research Museum for Geo-resources	Prof. Dr. Thomas Stöllner
Universität Kiel	Prof. Dr. Matthias Renz

5.3.1 Brief description and aims

Scientifically supported material analyses, imaging procedures and technological experiments are key tools for researching and archiving cultural assets. Heterogeneous and complex datasets in this area are difficult to survey. Therefore, the central aim of TA3 is to develop an overview of existing research datasets in order to develop and provide platforms, standards and services on this basis (G3.1) to meet N4O Objectives 2, 3 and 4 for modern laboratory-based analysis. A broad group of users in all research areas will be offered comparable analytic measures, quality standards and data repositories (G3.2, N4O Objective 1). This includes a national overview of laboratories, measuring equipment and existing institutional data repositories to be integrated into the structures. With other NFDI consortia in the sciences in the N4O Commons (N4O Objective 6), we will do preparatory work to set quality standards (G3.2). In TRAILS, digital datasets of various archaeological analysis methods will be linked to the datasets generated by TAs 1, 2 and 4. Over the next five years we will draw up comprehensible guidelines for documenting analytical and experimental procedures and results, enabling open reuse of scientific data and manuals by reviewers of applications and publications (N4O Objective 5). Students and colleagues will be trained in the standards developed with TA6 (N4O Objective 1 and 5).

TA3 addresses the diverse processes that encompass research into objects and ensures that the information obtained is linked to those objects (see section 4.2). In the field of analytics and experiments, the N4O will address the current lack of DiS connecting existing collections. TA3 also aims to create simple and rapid data entry tools (SAS) from current laboratory workflows into the new DiS (see section 4.4). The activities of TA3 will integrate and harmonise data and develop versioned, publishable and citable data products. Thus TA3 contributes to the FAIRification of data associated with N4O.

5.3.2 Goals of TA3

Goal	Description
G3.1	Adapt and implement existing data models and interfaces for data in analytics and experiments.
G3.2	Analyse requirements for linked digital repositories and metadata in analytics and experiments and provide appropriate solutions.
G3.3	Evaluate and compile existing protocols and guidelines for analytics and experiments.

5.3.3 Measures and tasks in TA3

M3.1 Data models and interfaces: development, curation and enhancement – G3.1, G3.2, G3.3 In order to link the various N4O data to protocols and results of analysis, TA3 will develop extensive meta-vocabularies, which provide contextual information on archaeological objects with data derived from studies on artefacts, their origin, production, use and storage. With TA5 and TA6, linking tools for universally readable code systems are being developed, with the perspective of semi- and fully automated LOD.

The TA3 team plans to integrate this work into an Analytics and Experiments Service Tool (AEST). This DiS, developed by DBM with GNAA, will provide an overview of institutions and researchers working on archaeometry and archaeobiology in Germany. Laboratory tools and their specific authority data will be made available to the N4O Community. This TA will produce white papers, a general ontology for structuring analytical data, blue papers and qualification information on software (open source and commercial) for analysing and evaluating analytical data.

Tasks in M3.1	
T3.1.1	Create meta-thesauri for analytics and experiments
T3.1.2	Improve in-silicio analytical tools, laboratories and repositories and best practices
T3.1.3	Develop generic data structures, models and tools for lab/experiment protocols
T3.1.4	Harmonise existing metadata models
T3.1.5	Identify and link existing data repositories
T3.1.6	Create an online data service, helpdesk and basic tools
User stories for M3.1	ID 3, ID 4; ID 11, ID 22, ID 43
TRAILS related with M3.1	-
Participants in M3.1	ID 23

M3.2 From geoarchaeology to artefact: process-related archaeometry and material sciences – G3.2 Appropriating and transforming georesources is one of the basic cultural techniques of humanity. Since the Late Palaeolithic, people have been shaping their environments and changing their habitats. Geoarchives of soils, landscapes and mineral resources (lithic raw materials, ores, pigments, etc.) play a decisive role in understanding the past conditions in which humans appropriated raw material. Based on these conditions, people produced objects and created new materials. The processes connected with producing these materials and their origin are important indications of the exchange processes in early societies.

To date, there are numerous partial repositories and databases in geoscientific archaeometry. In this measure, they will be unified and made accessible in a digital service (e.g. online repositories on the chemical composition of metal, the composition of ancient glass and the mineralogical and chemical data of ancient ceramics). Image-based methods of petrography and metallography (microsections, thin sections) are included. In the first five years, we will devise and implement a web-based service: Georesources in Human History. White papers will demonstrate how to integrate databases into this service. The DBM and partners will host and develop this service for material-science-based archaeometry for geoarchaeology of ancient soils and geoarchives, ancient raw material sources, their exploitation and artefact analysis.

Data from use cases in TRAIL 3.5 on Cartagenan lead will help to establish the core data model that the community can use for data entry. GNAA will support the tool and communicate it to the N4O community while specified geochemical data standards will be harmonised with the NFDI4Earth community (connection to DiS in M3.1). Based on georesource management systems, we will produce an ontology and a classification of scientific methods in order to establish an overarching research service.

Tasks in M3.2	
T3.2.1	Compare existing research repositories and create the specification for an overarching research service, Georesources in Human History
T3.2.2	Develop a Landscapes, Soils and Mineral Deposits online repository (DBM, University Cologne)
T3.2.3	Analyse requirements for a Metals online repository, incorporating existing repositories (DBM, CEZA, RGZM, SPK-SMB, Rathgen Forschungslabor), to produce a white paper
T3.2.4	Analyse requirements for a Glass online repository, incorporating existing repositories (DBM, CEZA), to produce a white paper
T3.2.5	Analyse requirements for a Ceramics online repository, incorporating existing repositories (DBM, CEZA, Rathgen Forschungslabor), to produce a white paper
T3.2.6	Analyse requirements for a Provenance and Pb Isotopes online repository, incorporating existing repositories (CEZA and DBM)
T3.2.7	Assess and ensure interoperability based on example datasets (see TRAIL 3.5) and those of other NFDI consortia
User stories for M3.2	ID 4, ID 16, ID 18, ID 21, ID 50; ID 43, ID 45; ID 52; ID 53
TRAILs related with M3.2	TRAIL 3.4 Georesources in human history: the lifecycle of lead from Roman Cartagena
Participants in M3.2	ID 06, ID 16; ID 38

M3.3 Humans, plants and animals as agents and resources – G3.2 Archaeology is concerned with the scientific exploration of archaeological remains of humans, plants and animals. It comprises anthropological, archaeobotanical and archaeozoological investigations and provides manifold information on the anthropogenic use of bio-resources, mobility and health status of humans and animals, origins and development of anthropogenic ecosystems, the relationship of humans to their natural environment and changes in climate and biodiversity. Morphological analysis of human, plant and animal remains has recently been supplemented with innovative molecular biological approaches, including stable isotope and archaeogenetic analyses. Subject-specific repositories developed by archaeobiologists, such as ArchbotLit, Anthrobook, ArbotDat, and OssoBook, enable archiving of relevant eco- and biofacts. N4O is working to systematically link analytical data from isotope research (M3.2) and archaeogenetics (T3.3.5). This measure envisages the development of three web services: ArbDat+, Poseidon 2.0 and OssoBook.

1. ArboDat will be developed in TRAIL 3.2 into a user-friendly, extensible online software system to overcome challenges for collaboration and data sharing within the com-

munity, ArboDat+. Current and potential users including other experts in archaeobotany will use it to search archaeobotanical data repositories and an expert standardised data entry system. To achieve this goal, ArboDat+ will be integrated into the “Research Data Commons” (RDC) of the “Common Infrastructures (section-infra)” section of the NFDI e.V., which is an infrastructure developed as part of a number of NFDI consortia (incl. NFDI4BioDiversity and NFDI / GAIA-X project FAIR Data Spaces) providing uniform access to data, software and computational resources, as well as enabling a reliable data exchange, collaborative work and providing connections to PANGEA in order to ensure the long-term operation of the ArboDat+ services (sustainability). The scientific long-term support for this is provided by the Niedersächsisches Institut für historische Küstenforschung (NIhK).

2. The existing Poseidon framework is the starting point in TRAIL 3.3. Poseidon already provides i) a minimal data format to package archaeogenetic data, ii) software to handle such packages and iii) an extensive public data repository including more than 5,000 ancient human genomes. The TRAIL will develop a tool to link genetic data extracted from human remains to archaeological context data and other analytic data (e.g. from stable isotope analysis). The service will provide community access to research data throughout its lifecycle, integrating it and easing analysis.

3. OssoBook will be transformed into an open source, web-based tool permanently hosted by the Staatliche Naturwissenschaftliche Sammlungen Bayerns (SNSB), their EDP and archaeozoological expert network. OssoBook is an existing archaeozoology tool allowing expert communities to build on standardised data entries (based on blue papers). This measure will make the tool more widely accessible and usable, so it can later be harmonised with corresponding zoological data at NFDI4Biodiversity. The RDM and IT concept of OssoBook will be implemented in Anthrobook, an expert tool developed by anthropologists at SNSB for recording human remains from archaeological sites, which is currently in its test phase.

Tasks in M3.3	
T3.3.1	Develop an online research service, ArboDAT+
T3.3.2	Incorporate tools and repositories for seeds/fruits/macrob-otany, e.g. CAU Kiel and NIhK Wilhelmshaven (ArchbotLit and ArboDAT)
T3.3.3	Integrate OssoBook (SAPM/SNSB München) into the online service
T3.3.4	Develop an online research service, Archaeogenetics, based on Poseidon
T3.3.5	Assess and ensure interoperability between these services and those of other NFDI consortia
User stories for M3.3	ID 1, ID 4, ID 6, ID 7, ID 11, ID 12;, ID 18, ID 37, ID 42
TRAILs related with M3.3	TRAIL 3.2 ArboDat+: Development of a concept for a centralised standardised ArboDat service TRAIL 3.3 Poseidon 2.0: A data repository for genetic, bioarchaeological and archaeological data
Participants in M3.3	ID 23, ID 30, D 34, ID 38; ID 42

M3.4 Experiments, reconstruction, replication and reproduction – G3.2, G3.3 Archaeologists often lack the infrastructure, theoretical basis, resources and/or

tools to perform the requisite experiments. M3.4 will link and expand existing experimental and traceology databases and contribute to developing binding standards for analysing and testing archaeological object classes. Developed within TRAIL 3.4, a flexible, easy-to-use visual workflow tool will allow researchers to record and illustrate paradata: experimental design, the protocol of sample preparation, procedure or analysis. The tool will incorporate different types of experimental setup, ranging from high-tech controlled automated procedures in a lab to full-scale reconstructions in the field or well-documented re-enactment by a broader public (CC). Users will be able to customise the prototype developed in the TRAIL, and increasing familiarity with their needs will be used to improve it. The tool will be hosted and curated by LEIZA/RGZM.

Tasks in M3.4	
T3.4.1	Develop an Experiments and Replication online repository
T3.4.2	Develop a Traceology online repository
T3.4.3	Assess and assure interoperability between these services and those of other NFDI consortia
User stories for M3.4	ID 2, ID 3, ID 4, ID 5, ID 16, ID 43, ID 62
TRAILs related with M3.4	TRAIL 3.3 Workflow tool for archaeological experiments and analytics
Participants in M3.4	ID 30, ID 38, ID 42, ID 50

M3.5 Commons contribution and coordination This measure ensures efficient coordination of the work programme within the consortium in close collaboration with TA6 and TA7. Furthermore, it promotes coordination across all TAs to ensure coherence of standards and specifications as well as training materials and measures. Cross-cutting topics will be worked on at organisational level. These joint activities and shared structures will guarantee that all data-generating research processes are mapped to the research data lifecycle.

Tasks in M3.5	
T3.5.1	Build community
T3.5.2	Establish common ground: standards, protocols and guidelines for science-based archaeology (see DiS, AEST in M3.1)
T3.5.3	Develop and pilot training concepts
T3.5.4	Actively mediate between ECs and CCs: science meets the public
T3.5.5	Enable internal consortium coordination and knowledge transfer
T3.5.6	Develop demand-oriented operating models for services in TA3
User stories for M3.5	ID 5, ID 15, ID 43
TRAILs related with M3.5	-
Continued on next page	

Tasks in M3.5	
Participants in M3.5	This measure is shared by all the TAs: each co-applicant and each participant is integrated into it.

5.3.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA3

ID	Description
KPI3.1.1	By 2023, existing data models and interfaces are evaluated.
KPI3.1.2	By 2025, the data models are adapted to community needs and implemented in at least eight repositories.
KPI3.1.3	Between 2022 and 2026, numbers accessing the relevant repositories and interfaces have risen by 25%.
KPI3.1.4	By December 2025, as shown by the N4O Community survey, the data models are used in 25% of the relevant subject-specific laboratories in Germany.
KPI3.2.1	By the end of 2024, the relevant community requirements for linked digital repositories and metadata has been evaluated.
KPI3.2.2	By 2026, appropriate solutions will be implemented.
KPI3.2.3	Between 2022 and 2027, uploads and downloads on the relevant repositories increase by 25%.
KPI3.2.4	By December 2025, as shown by the N4O Community survey, the metadata formats are used in 25% of the relevant subject-specific laboratories in Germany.
KPI3.3.1	By 2024, existing relevant protocols and guidelines are evaluated and collected in an accessible manner.
KPI3.3.2	By mid-2027, the guidelines and protocols are accepted by the community and the (mean) number of references rises by 25%.
KPI3.3.3	By the end of 2025, as shown by the N4O Community survey, the guidelines and protocols are taught and used in 25% of the relevant subject-specific laboratories in Germany.

5.3.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

TA3 cooperates on several aspects with other TAs. Within M3.1 it aims at linking the data from N4O with those generated in analytics and experiments, resulting in close ties to TA1, TA2 and TA4. TA6 will manage the description of object biographies and the research data lifecycle. With TA5 technical interfaces and standards are coordinated to create linked datasets and tools. The standardised handling of uncertainty, developed by TA2, will be used by TA3 to describe uncertainties inherent in statistical analyses. The geoarchives planned in M3.2 will be linked to the geoservice within TA4. Strong ties to the conservation specialists and services in TA4 exist in the description of chemical and physical properties of materials, for which discovery services are developed within M3.3 (Metal, Glass, Ceramics) and M3.4 (Provenance and Pb Isotopes). The development of databases for the Bones repository connects to field archaeology (and TA1). Protocols and guidelines for experimental archaeology will be an important contribution to the N4O Commons coordinated in TA6.

5.4 Task Area 4: Protecting

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinland-Pfalz (GDKE)	Dr. Ulrich Himmelmann
Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum – Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology	Christian Eckmann

5.4.1 Brief description and aims

TA4 Protecting deals with interference of heterogeneous research data generated in the context of protecting and preserving tangible and intangible, movable and immovable cultural heritage. The first, modular project phase, with community involvement, will lay the foundation for incorporating specialist perspectives on heritage management into TA5 to improve the quality of research data (N4O Objective 2; G4.1). TA4 will create standardised interfaces for data exchange, with a view to making the extensive datasets held by various institutions and the LDAs more accessible for research, exchange and continuing professional development, ease data entry for monitoring data, and facilitate data submission for the bodies that hold data (N4O Objective 2, 3, 4; G4.2, G4.3, G4.4). Some applications (web application for volunteers in heritage conservation/web-based basic FAIRification tool for restoration/conservation) should be ready for use by the end of phase 1 (N4O Objective 4), with scope for development by the community.

Standards and interfaces rooted in best-practice experiences from the N4O Community (TA6) (G4.1, G4.2, G4.5), along with mapped/harmonised community-driven vocabularies (G4.1, G4.2) underpin all further measures. They also enable bi- or multilateral data exchange between two or more institutions at an early stage in the project. The CCs will be comprehensively integrated into these measures. The online data services described under M4.3 (G4.3, G4.4, G4.5) are based on the interfaces developed in M4.1. They convey a view of current data in data holders' systems that are retrievable via a URL and, if authorised, can be integrated into external systems. Services related to monument data usually contain georeferences indicating the location of sites, monuments, excavations, etc. In M4.4 (G4.5, N4O Objective 7), information on M4.1–3 is prepared for the work of TA6 and TA7.

The services developed in TA4 will play an important role within the N4O RDM strategy. The aim is to harmonise shared and community-driven vocabularies, for which machine-readable interfaces will be provided. The discovery service for site and monument data will include a common online geodata service. TA4 will promote voluntary work and citizen science for N4O, thereby opening it to the community as a whole. These activities of TA4 integrate and harmonise data, developing versioned, publishable and citable data products. Thus, TA4 contributes significantly to the FAIRification of data associated with N4O.

5.4.2 Goals of TA4

Goal	Description
G4.1	Coordinate a community-driven evaluation of existing RDM strategies at LDAs, restoration and conservation institutions.
Continued on next page	

Goal	Description
G4.2	Develop community-driven interfaces and vocabularies in the field of cultural heritage preservation.
G4.3	Provide core services for geodata handled at LDAs.
G4.4	Develop machine- and human-readable interfaces and digital web services for the restoration and conservation community and to analyse historical/prehistoric manufacturing/production processes.
G4.5	Strengthen voluntary engagement as citizen science in monument recording and conservation.

5.4.3 Measures and tasks in TA4

M4.1 Interfaces and standards for availability of monument and restoration-related data – G4.1, G4.2, G4.5 The development of interfaces and standards for exchange of data relating to monuments, sites, objects and protection measures, combined with the mapped or harmonised authority files and community-driven vocabularies described in M4.2, form an essential basis for all further measures within TA4. For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Definition of data access and authorisation levels (DiS) in white papers (T4.1.2).
- Catalogue of standards and ontologies (CReS) created by entering data in a registry for data exchange formats and knowledge modelling concepts relating to monuments and conservation science (T4.1.1/3–8).
- Definition of interfaces for data exchange between heterogeneous systems (IntS) in white and blue papers discussing existing standards (e.g. INSPIRE) and modelling new ones to create a solid basis for data exchange between governmental and university systems including citizen science/volunteers' data (T4.1.3–8).
- Standards and interfaces for interdisciplinary knowledge modelling (IntS) in a white paper and an OWL ontology (including a blue paper) describing conservation and restoration processes, historical/prehistoric manufacturing and production techniques as basis for a reference implementation for an archaeological research collection (T4.1.7).

Tasks in M4.1	
T4.1.1	Evaluate standards and interfaces for the exchange of data relating to monuments, sites, objects and protection measures
T4.1.2	Define information access levels
T4.1.3	Develop a standard and an interface for site and monument data
T4.1.4	Develop a standard and an interface for data relating to heritage management measures
T4.1.5	Develop a standard and an interface for data relating to protected status/legal effect
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Tasks in M4.1	
T4.1.6	Develop an ontology for conservation and restoration processes and historical/prehistoric manufacturing/production techniques
T4.1.7	Development and implementation of interfaces for conservation and restoration processes
T4.1.8	Develop a standard/interface for volunteers' data (citizen science)
User stories for M4.1	ID 6, ID 7, ID 8, ID 11, ID 12, ID 22, ID 72, ID 76, ID 68, ID 69, ID 70, ID 73, ID 75, ID 71, ID 74, ID 77, ID 78, ID 79, ID 84, ID 85, ID 80, ID 81
TRAILs related with M4.1	TRAIL 4.1 Interface
Participants in M4.1	ID 22, ID 28, ID 31, ID 36, ID 37, ID 48, ID 56

M4.2 Mapping monument and restoration-related community-driven vocabularies and ontologies – G4.1, G4.2 The aim of this measure is to map and/or harmonise existing authority files and community-driven vocabularies used by the data-holding bodies with reference to monuments, sites, objects, protected areas and restoration or conservation measures. With M4.1 (standards and interfaces), these authority files and vocabularies form an essential basis for all further measures in TA4. At present, there is enormous heterogeneity in the quality and availability of the authority files and vocabularies maintained by the individual data-holding bodies. This measure, taken in the first project phase (years 1 and 2) and continued as necessary, is an essential foundation for all further measures within TA4. For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Catalogue of standards and ontologies, authority files and community-driven vocabularies (CReS) created by data entries in a registry, powered by DANTE in TA5, for knowledge modelling and entity identification concepts as well as research data relating to monuments and conservation science (T4.2.1).
- Enriched and semantically aligned authority files and community-driven vocabularies for standardisation (AVS/DaS) by creating new records using DANTE and enriching data using Cocoda (T4.2.2–7).

Tasks in M4.2	
T4.2.1	Catalogue existing authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies
T4.2.2	Map existing authority files and community-driven vocabularies to chronology and dating
T4.2.3	Map existing authority files and community-driven vocabularies for addressing (measures in) monuments and sites
T4.2.4	Map existing community-driven vocabularies on protected status and its legal impacts
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Tasks in M4.2	
T4.2.5	Map existing authority files and community-driven vocabularies on conservation, restoration and production materials as well as methods and conservation state
T4.2.6	Create new and map existing authority files and community-driven vocabularies on historical/prehistoric manufacturing/production techniques
T4.2.7	Create and develop interoperable authority files, community-driven vocabularies and ontologies for monuments and conservation science, as well as major and collection union systems
User stories for M4.2	ID 6, ID 7, ID 8, ID 11, ID 12, ID 22, ID 72, ID 76, ID 68, ID 69, ID 70, ID 73, ID 75, ID 71, ID 74, ID 77, ID 78, ID 79, ID 84, ID 85, ID 80, ID 81
TRAILs related with M4.2	TRAIL 4.2 Mapping
Participants in M4.2	ID 22, ID 28, ID 31, ID 36, ID 37, ID 48, ID 56

M4.3 Specifying web-based (geo)services for monument and restoration-related data – G4.3, G4.4, G4.5 This measure aims to develop online data services for sites/heritage objects, protected areas, measures and data relating to objects and conservation. The services make the information available online, updated daily, on the basis of the interfaces described in M4.1 and using the standardised community-driven vocabularies described in M4.2, and can be readily integrated into other systems (e.g. into the services described in M4.3). As the services described here build on the preliminary work described in M4.1 and M4.2, they are developed in the middle phase of the project (year 3), and updated as required.

For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Catalogue of RDM research tools (CreS) created by data entries in an N4O-specific registry, provided by TA6 (T4.3.1).
- Research toolkit for knowledge modelling (SAS) extended by a web-based FAIRification knowledge modelling tool for conservation science (T4.3.6).
- Service developed for retrieving objects across distributed systems (DiS) by developing joint geodata services (T4.3.2–5).

Tasks in M4.3	
T4.3.1	Evaluate existing online data services and FAIRification tools for sites/heritage objects, protected areas, measures and data relating to objects and restoration
T4.3.2	Develop a joint (geo)data service for data on sites and monument data
T4.3.3	Develop a joint (geo)data service for data relating to measures
T4.3.4	Develop a joint (geo)data service for data on protected status/impact
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Tasks in M4.3	
T4.3.5	Develop a joint (geo)data service for volunteers' data (citizen science)
T4.3.6	Develop an interactive web-based knowledge management FAIRification tool for conservation and restoration processes and historical/prehistoric manufacturing/production techniques
User stories for M4.3	ID 6, ID 7, ID 8, ID 11, ID 12, ID 22, ID 72, ID 76, ID 68, ID 69, ID 70, ID 73, ID 75, ID 71, ID 74, ID 77, ID 78, ID 79, ID 84, ID 85, ID 80, ID 81
TRAILs related with M4.3	TRAIL 4.3 GeoService
Participants in M4.3	ID 22, ID 28, ID 31, ID 36, ID 37, ID 48, ID 56

M4.4 Commons contribution and coordination – G4.5 The aim of this measure is knowledge transfer to protect exchange standards, objects identification and data qualifying methods in order to create services specific to monument and conservations research (N4O Objective 1, 5). Through its incorporation into the Coordination Office (TA7), this measure is dovetailed with the activities in the consortium as a whole. This measure will focus on transferring knowledge gained in G4.1–5. To establish the content and systems developed in M4.1 to M4.3 in the community and to strengthen skills, we require a continuous professional development programme.

For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Collection of written output (CoS) created by entering documentation, best practices, guidelines, workflows and evaluation reports in a N4O Commons platform, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T4.4.2).
- Catalogue of authority files and vocabularies, RDM research tools, standards and ontologies, datasets and repositories (CreS) created by data entries in a N4O-specific catalogue service, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T4.4.2).
- Concepts for semantic and technical integration and harmonisation of object descriptions (IntS /PaS) created by entering white and blue papers in a N4O Commons platform, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T4.4.2).
- Tools for managing knowledge modelling, including fuzzy and wobbly semantics (SAS) created by research software engineering, documentation and training, coordinated by TA7 (T4.4.2/3).
- Qualification, education and training (QuaS) created by providing OER and organising interactive workshops, with TA7 (T4.4.3).
- Community engagement and knowledge transfer (PaS) created by engagement in cluster discussions and activities for community outreach, coordinated by TA7 (T4.4.1/4).

Tasks in M4.4	
T4.4.1	Community building, mediation and supporting CCs and TWGs
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Tasks in M4.4	
T4.4.2	Establish common ground: Services for monuments and conservation related data
T4.4.3	Develop and pilot training concepts
T4.4.4	Enable internal consortium coordination and knowledge transfer
User stories for M4.4	ID 42, ID 44, ID 65
TRAILS related with M4.4	The tasks in M4.4 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M4.4	This measure is shared by all the TAs: each co-applicant and each participant is integrated into it.

5.4.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA4

ID	Description
KPI4.1.1	From 2022 to 2024, standards and interfaces, community-driven vocabularies, services and tools are evaluated, with 16 LDAs and at least 70% of the restoration community forming a TWG within N4O.
KPI4.1.2	Throughout the project, at least two working meetings per project year are held (with TA6) to evaluate data interference in the LDAs and to discuss open restoration/conservation issues.
KPI4.1.3	By the beginning of 2025, the different standards in N4O Commons are analysed, with TA6.
KPI4.2.1	By 2023, a TWG completes the commons process of formulating standards for vocabularies and interfaces and successfully submits a proposal for approval by the GA.
KPI4.2.2	Between 2023 and 2026, these standards and interfaces are implemented in the LDAs with an annual average of four implementations.
KPI4.2.3	By 2023, a TWG formulates standards for vocabularies and interfaces for restoration/conservation and manufacturing/production processes and successfully submits it for approval by the GA.
KPI4.2.4	By mid-2026, a 1.0 version of the ontology of restoration/conservation and production methods, the associated vocabularies and interfaces is modelled and implemented.
KPI4.3.1	From 2023, the interface-based and INSPIRE-compliant online geodata services of various data providers (16 LDAs) are available as one common data service.
KPI4.3.2	By mid-2025, all 16 LDAs, 25 researchers, 3 specialist authorities and 10 non-professionals use this common geodata service, which is implemented in 70% of their systems.
KPI4.3.3	From mid-2024, the data of all 16 LDAs can be displayed and searched via the common online geodata service.
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ID	Description
KPI4.3.4	By mid-2025, 16 LDAs, 25 researchers, 3 specialist authorities and 10 non-professionals use the common geodata services for research.
KPI4.4.1	By 2024, a TWG has analysed requirements with the responsible (voluntary) heritage conservation communities, and a successful proposal is submitted to the GA resulting in product backlogs.
KPI4.4.2	By mid-2025, a web-based citizen science app is developed and (with TA6) available in the N4O Commons.
KPI4.4.3	By mid-2026, the web-based citizen science app is used by 500 non-professionals and all 16 LDAs.

5.4.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

TA4 has links to TA1, TA2, TA3, and TA5. The link to TA1 mainly concerns excavation data and find notifications. Community-driven vocabularies are developed in a compatible and standardised manner with the other TAs. Links to TA2, and between preserving and collecting in general, consist of finds and objects in collections originating from sites and monuments. For TA4, a data cycle with TA3 is required. The repositories for geoarchives planned in TA3 will connect their spatial metadata to TA4. The connection between TA4 and TA5 entails close cooperation in establishing services. With the legal obligation to provide information on heritage/monuments and protected areas in the geoportals of the German federal states, TA4 is a competent partner providing INSPIRE-compliant services. In conjunction with TA6, teaching materials for the N4O Commons will be drawn up and communicated to the community via TA7.

5.5 Task Area 5: Storage, Access and Dissemination

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
German Archaeological Institute, Head Office Berlin, Zentrale wissenschaftliche Dienste	Henriette Senst
Verbundzentrale des GBV (VZG), Department Digital Library	Frank Dührkohp

5.5.1 Brief description and aims

TA5 provides technical services and infrastructures to meet the changing needs raised in TAs 1–4 for object-related RDM. To this end, it draws on existing services, connects these within a network and develops them in line with the FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles. Existing services operated by TA5 members will be made available to all participants in N4O as core services, developed in a research-driven manner and scaled for a wider circle of users. For each of the core services and tools offered in the TAs, co-applicants provide support as their own contribution in a second-level helpdesk. This diversity and complexity of the data in N4O engender specific challenges in curation, networking, preservation and provision. For this reason, TA5 will develop and implement quality criteria, harmonise authority data and data formats, and enable standardised systems, since a unified approach to objects from the start of data production improves

metadata quality. These core services will be made interoperable and available in other information systems using standard interfaces.

To make all object-related research data findable and accessible via a single access point, this TA will create a general index of all relevant metadata for a rich metadata discovery service, with an associated search front end. A graph database and standardised APIs will enable retrieval and dissemination of metadata. Data will be continually transferred from the core services to specialist information systems in the discovery service.

TA5 will provide infrastructural services to disseminate research products that exist and are not being developed within N4O, to make them more broadly accessible to the archaeology research community. TA5 designs and implements core services in a sustainable and economical process model. Six measures will provide a new level of technical infrastructure to harmonise RDM and make it available to the whole N4O Community, including other partners in NFDI. These activities will contribute to the FAIRification of data associated with N4O by providing versioned, publishable and citable data products.

5.5.2 Goals of TA5

Goal	Description
G5.1	Provide services within N4O that are accepted, used and improved by the professional community.
G5.2	Make an accountable contribution to media consistency and quality assurance for the object-related research data lifecycle.
G5.3	Transfer object-related research data to a permanent public domain in compliance with the FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles, guaranteeing reliable access and permanent interpretability of the data.
G5.4	Make heterogeneous research data findable and interoperable via intuitively usable, efficient and uniform discovery systems.
G5.5	Make technical services sustainable for long-term use to ensure continuous cross-linkage and use independently of institutions.

5.5.3 Measures and tasks in TA5

M5.1 Provision of LTA services with open interfaces for N4O data and development of IT recommendations – G5.1, G5.3, G5.5 TA5 ensures that from day one of N4O’s work, a core LTA service will be available to the archaeological community. It will rely on established and accepted tools, and produce guidelines aimed at research projects aiming to integrate data and innovations within a sustainable infrastructure. IANUS is a subject-specific national research data centre that curates and processes archaeology data, as do the German federal states’ archives. These services are continuously adapted and scaled to keep up with the academic community’s constantly evolving requirements, national and international developments in LTA, and development of the NFDI infrastructure. The IANUS IT recommendations will be developed in the community. TA5 will support researchers producing and re-using object-specific data through a large part of the research data lifecycle. The implementation of discipline specific, understandable and practical data management plans and the distribution through an established system like RDMO is guaranteed. Key tasks in TA5 include data collection and specification of open, preferably standardised and automated LTA interfaces between data repositories, specialised systems and downstream infrastructures for LTA. The TA will take into account concepts of the OAI reference model for structuring submission and archiving packages (SIPs and AIPs) and to define significant properties,

archiving formats and format migrations to maintain interpretability. These must then be implemented in both data capture and archiving systems. The challenge of FAIRifying object-related legacy data is addressed by separate measures, above all by meetings with the professional community to define subject-related, formal and technical criteria and by implementing interfaces tailored to these.

Tasks in M5.1	
T5.1.1	Provide core services for subject-specific LTA (IANUS, baureka.online) and develop/scale these as required
T5.1.2	Document existing LTA interfaces for subsequent use of established analysis and documentation software
T5.1.3	Identify missing LTA interfaces to define technical specifications, properties and archiving formats for specific data types, formats and origin contexts
T5.1.4	Implement, test and adapt new LTA interfaces in data entry systems (ADABweb, iDAI.field, ArchaeoDocs, Goobi, KuniWeb) and repositories (DAM)
T5.1.5	Implement new LTA interfaces in archive systems (IANUS, baureka.online)
T5.1.6	Develop specific LTA interfaces for long-tail/legacy data
T5.1.7	Develop the IANUS IT recommendations
User stories for M5.1	ID 1; ID 44, ID 45, ID 87, ID 92, ID 93, ID 47, ID 86, ID 89, ID 49, ID 90, ID 94, ID 95, ID 96
TRAILS related with M5.1	-
Participants in M5.1	ID 13, ID 18, ID 25, ID 41

M5.2 Quality assurance of N4O data through curation and validation – G5.1, G5.2, G5.5 To improve (meta)data transfer to a permanent public domain (e.g. repositories, data portals, archives, discovery systems, information infrastructures), a catalogue of common criteria for high-quality object-related data will be developed, taking account of both subject-specific and generic requirements. This will provide the basis for adequate data preparation during pre-ingest and manual or automated curation in data archives. Preservation policies with format and metadata mappings must be worked out, processes established and supporting tools developed to achieve and validate the required data quality. The outcome will be an N4O-specific catalogue of criteria for qualitative data and a partly automated validation process.

Tasks in M5.2	
T5.2.1	Develop a FAIR catalogue of technical, formal and content criteria and key properties for object-related qualitative data and metadata
T5.2.2	Based on the criteria in T5.2.1, develop tools to support (partly) automated data validation process
User stories for M5.2	ID 2, ID 92, ID 93, ID 33, ID 47, ID 94, ID 95, ID 96
Continued on next page	

Tasks in M5.2	
TRAILS related with M5.2	-
Participants in M5.2	ID 40, ID 41

M5.3 IT services for authority and metadata from TA1–4 – G5.1, G5.3, G5.5

Quality assurance for research data is supported to a large extent by the use of authority files. This measure will bring together existing approaches to authority files, vocabularies and keyword lists in a common authority data service. An existing platform, DANTE (operated by VZG), will be used for this purpose. In a continuous feedback loop with TA1–4, the DANTE platform will be expanded and supplemented with specialised vocabularies. The authority files made available via the DANTE API can be integrated for standardised indexing by any system, ingested into the GND via the DNB GND4C project and made available for Wikidata.

As soon as the project begins, software solutions will be made available for general use as core services. These services have been tested and used in the professional community to integrate authority data and implement proven models. These services support the indexing of excavation and object data, retro-digitisation of documents, and reuse of metadata and media data via standardised interfaces.

Tasks in M5.3	
T5.3.1	Operate DANTE as a core service to provide authority data and vocabularies from TA1–4 and adapt these to integrate new subject-specific vocabularies and functionalities
T5.3.2	Operate and develop existing software solutions to capture and maintain metadata in a standardised way (kuniweb, Goobi, ADABweb, ArchaeoDox, iDAI.field)
User stories for M5.3	ID 10, ID 14, ID 19, ID 32, ID 95, ID 96, ID: 34, ID 36, ID 94, ID 35, ID 42, ID 43, ID 68, ID 92, ID 93, ID 47, ID 85
TRAILS related with M5.3	-
Participants in M5.3	ID 3, ID 8, ID 16, ID 27, ID 29, ID 35, ID 43, ID 48, ID 55

M5.4 Discovery system as single access point for subject-specific information

– G5.1, G5.3, G5.4, G5.5 In order to make decentralised subject-specific information accessible to scholars and the general public, a discovery system will be developed, which will bundle and make searchable the data on all research products of N4O via a common metadata index that integrates:

- Metadata on objects, sites and monuments from local/institutional subject-specific systems
- Information on analogue and digital archived data
- All sorts of research publications

- Data enrichment integrated through automatic named entity recognition in compliance with quality criteria.

Excerpts of the metadata of the individual data providers are regularly harvested, centrally processed and stored in a general index operated by VZG. On this technical basis, the general index can be searched online via its own front end with simple and extended retrieval functionalities (including relevance ranking and faceted browsing) and the search engine can be integrated as a backend into any individual discovery service via corresponding interfaces.

Tasks in M5.4	
T5.4.1	Create a concept for the discovery system and for processing the harvested metadata
T5.4.2	Develop a technical backend for the concept developed in T5.4.1
T5.4.3	Enrich data from the metadata index by automatic named entity recognition and make it available in a web service
T5.4.4	Develop a search and retrieval front end for the website and an app for mobile devices
User stories for M5.4	ID 1, ID 2, ID 6, ID 7, ID 8, ID 76; ID 9, ID 13, ID18, ID 19, ID 32, ID 95, ID 96, ID 23 – ID 31, ID 68, ID 92, ID 93, ID 94, ID 80, ID 81, ID 88
TRAILS related with M5.4	-
Participants in M5.4	ID 13, ID 40, ID 48

M5.5 Provision and networking of N4O data – G5.2, G5.3, G5.4 To provide the data processed by the previous measures in accordance with the FAIR principles and network it (inter)nationally, existing services will be evaluated, provided or expanded and new services developed to support and advise the expert community on the publication and archiving of research data. Existing PID systems and services are developed based on a N4O-specific PID concept to provide comprehensive core services for digital publications, to create and shape useful resources. A metadata portal with appropriate interfaces will be designed, developed and operated to make data available in, network it with and transfer it to other information infrastructures (e.g. WikiBase, CLARIAH or DDB, Europeana) via a documented, standardised API. The data for the DDB, Europeana and other specialist portals will be made accessible via these standardised interfaces for the core services.

Tasks in M5.5	
T5.5.1	Analyse the existing PID systems/services (e.g. for granularity), formulate best practices and develop an object-specific PID concept
T5.5.2	Provide core services for specialised, integrated digital publications (Propylaeum, AV-Portal, KuLaDig) and advisory services for the specialist community (second-level helpdesk)
Continued on next page	

Tasks in M5.5	
User stories for M5.5	ID 1, ID 2, ID 6, ID 7, ID 8, ID 76, ID 9, ID 13, ID 17, ID 61, ID 68, ID 87, ID 92, ID 93, ID18; ID 19, ID 32, ID 95, ID 94, ID 96, ID 23 – ID 31; ID 80, ID 81, ID 88
TRAILS related with M5.5	-
Participants in M5.5	ID 16, ID 39, ID 49

M5.6 Commons contribution and coordination – G5.1–5 The aim of this measure is knowledge transfer within the community, with a focus on infrastructure components for LTA, object indexing and quality assurance. In close cooperation with TA7, activities and knowledge are shared and linked to activities throughout the consortium. TA7 develops process and business models for these components to continue, while TA5 provides the core services for the consortium to use. These services can be networked with core services of other NFDI consortia in coordination with TA7.

Tasks in M5.6	
T5.6.1	Coordinate the work meeting to approve and publish white and blue papers on the N4O Commons with TA7
T5.6.2	Coordinate the development of core services, in consultation with TA7
T5.6.3	Coordinate and provide quality assurance for standardised vocabularies from TA1–4, in consultation with TA7
T5.6.4	Coordinate the second-level helpdesk for TA5 services, in consultation with TA7
T5.6.5	Coordinate collaboration with services not developed within, but used by, N4O (e.g. AV Portal), in consultation with TA7
T5.6.6	Enable community engagement and knowledge transfer via cluster discussions and community activities, coordinated by TA7
User stories for M5.6	ID 19, ID 95, ID 96, ID 20, ID 35, ID 40, ID 42, ID 47, ID 66, ID 67
TRAILS related with M5.6	-
Participants in M5.6	This measure is shared by all the TAs: each co-applicant and each participant is integrated into it.

5.5.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA5

ID	Description
KPI5.1.1	Between 2023 and 2027, a 25% increase in the number of user accesses to the information systems provided by TA5 can be proven by evaluating user statistics.
KPI5.1.2	Between 2023 and 2027, the number of verified and traceable datasets in the discovery and retrieval services provided by TA5 increases by 25%.
KPI5.1.3	Between 2023 and 2027, the number of institutions that can operate and support interfaces for long time archiving and discovery systems increases by 25%.
KPI5.1.4	Between 2023 and 2027, within the central authority file hub, community-driven vocabularies have increased by 25%.
KPI5.2.1	By mid-2027, ten reference institutions and systems have completed a media break free digital process from data entry to LTA, with supported use of qualitative object-related research data.
KPI5.2.2	By the end of 2025, infrastructures modelling the complete research data lifecycle of object-related data, are being used by 25% of the N4O Community, as a survey of it will show.
KPI5.3.1	Between 2023 and 2027, the number of datasets within TA5 systems that fulfil the FAIR criteria increases by 50%.
KPI5.3.2	By 2027, 80% of object-related data with the N4O services meet 75% of the criteria on the check lists created by the RDA FAIR Maturity Model TWG.
KPI5.4.1	By mid-2027 at latest, open N4O data will be made public and retrievable in N4O-external systems.
KPI5.5.1	By 2027, 80% of the software components developed within TA5 are documented.
KPI5.5.2	By 2027, 50% of the service components developed within TA5 based on an operating and business model.

5.5.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

TA5 is connected to TA1, TA2, TA3 and TA4 and provides some core service for those. TA 5 provides a long-term archiving solution to secure the data from TA 1 to TA 4. The vocabularies developed by TA 1-4 will be made available for general use via a central vocabulary service of TA 5. The data collected in TA 1-4 will be made available for research via a discovery service of TA 5. In collaboration with TA 1, an excavation database will be developed and made available as a core service. In collaboration with TA 2, a collections database will be made available to collections and museums as a core service. TA 5 also uses the geoservices developed by TA 4 to qualify the data within the core services. In conjunction with TA6, teaching materials for the N4O Commons will be drawn up and communicated to the community via TA7.

5.6 Task Area 6: Qualification, Integration and Harmonisation

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
University of Applied Sciences Mainz, School of Engineering, Department of Geoinformatics and Surveying	Prof. Dr. Kai-Christian Bruhn
Max Planck Institute for the History of Science (MPIWG)	Dr. Dirk Wintergrün

5.6.1 Brief description and aims

TA6 develops suitable teaching and learning materials in line with the needs of the community, thus enabling up-to-date initial training and continuing professional development related to RDM. Furthermore, TA6 regularly supports training events to supplement existing university and non-university programmes. Based on the preparatory work of IANUS, a specified competence framework will be derived from the FAIR4S framework of EOSC, in line with the Data Literacy Charta of the Stifterverband (G6.1, N4O Objective 6). TA6 is responsible for systematically developing and refining a set of qualification profiles (G6.2, N4O Objective 6) with a regularly updated directory of (inter)national training opportunities based on services in IANUS and CLARIN-DARIAH. OER materials are bundled or created, and made available in the N4O Commons (G6.3, N4O Objective 5).

TA6 is dedicated to developing concepts for semantic harmonisation of object descriptions to improve the integration, comparability, interoperability and reusability of data (especially through ontologies and metadata schemes). In this context, TA6 organises processes to coordinate the subject-specific needs and developments within TAs 1–4 with regard to semantic modelling of objects and their contexts, drawing them together to produce complete object biographies (G6.3, N4O Objective 4). Taking existing approaches into account (incl. CIDOC-CRM, LIDO), options for a TA-independent object data model are discussed and a minimum set of properties (ObjectCore) derived from it; this is essential for describing each object to enable basic exchange and minimum comparability of object data in compliance with the FAIR principles (G6.4, N4O Objective 3).

5.6.2 Goals of TA6

Goal	Description
G6.1	Establish a multi-layered competence framework for university education and vocational qualification.
G6.2	Derive multidimensional qualification profiles for new staff positions in RDM.
G6.3	Establish an environment of viable OER and integrate it into flexible transfer scenarios.
G6.4	Develop bases for the complete digital description of contexts and stories of objects (object biographies).
G6.5	Develop an ObjectCore data model as a minimum exchange format.
Continued on next page	

Goal	Description
G6.6	Develop initial training and continuing professional development on RDM.

5.6.3 Measures and tasks in TA6

M6.1: Data skills: establishing prerequisites – G6.1, G6.2 Based on preliminary work by IANUS and experiences from various university courses (T6.1.1), a specified RDM competence framework will be derived, formulated and updated from the FAIR4S framework of EOSC in consultation with the edutrain section of NFDI. The corresponding tasks address two challenges. Active qualification structures, especially at universities, need a framework that ensures that the qualification is based on common competencies (T6.1.2). Many contents and concrete regulations for RDM will only be developed in N4O and must be integrated into specific curricula, e.g. for qualification as a data steward or digital documentation specialist (T6.1.3). University teaching does not serve parts of public administration, non-university research institutions and the private sector. Similarly, science qualifications must be integrated more strongly. M6.1 must therefore offer a flexible solution to which universities are keen to contribute and implement autonomously, while expanding the addressees.

Tasks in M6.1	
T6.1.1	Create a systematic catalogue of existing courses and trainee programmes
T6.1.2	Define a multi-faceted competence framework
T6.1.3	Derive qualification profiles
User stories for M6.1	ID 14, ID 40, ID 42, ID 48, ID 91, ID 51, ID 65, ID 66, ID 67
TRAILS related with M6.1	The tasks in M6.1 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M6.1	ID 7, ID 12, ID 14, ID 24, ID 26, ID 36, ID 38, ID 39, ID 47, ID 50, ID 51, ID 52

M6.2 Qualification: meeting all community needs – G6.1, G6.2, G6.6 TA6 coordinates and directs collaborative provision and versioning services for OER to support initial training and continuous professional development, based on a common and technically robust foundation. TA6 designs and organises events to supplement existing university and non-university courses and organises peer-to-peer continuing professional development within the consortium.

Tasks in M6.2	
T6.2.1	Create and disseminate OER
T6.2.2	Hold qualification and training events
T6.2.3	Exchange knowledge between RDM professionals
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Tasks in M6.2	
User stories for M6.2	ID 14, ID 40, ID 42, ID 48, ID 91, ID 51, ID 65, ID 66, ID 67
TRAILS related with M6.2	The tasks in M6.2 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M6.2	ID 7, ID 12, ID 14, ID 24, ID 26, ID 36, ID 38, ID 39, ID 47, ID 50, ID 51, ID 52

M6.3: Improving integration and harmonisation of N4O data – G6.5 TA6 is responsible for creating a transdisciplinary catalogue of digital science methods for all the stages in compiling a complete object biography in digital and machine-readable form. To do this, M6.3 will propose a core metadata set to uniquely identify the object and its related data and metadata; this can be used in TAs 1–4. TA6 maintains an inventory of all data formats and standards used in TAs 1–6 and coordinates the efforts to align these and develop best practices on data standards and formats for N4O repositories. TA6 coordinates the use of vocabularies, ontologies and authority files in all TAs to align these and map similar entities.

Tasks in M6.3	
T6.3.1	Create an inventory of data and metadata format and standards used in TAs 1–4
T6.3.2	Create an inventory of authority files, ontologies and community-driven vocabularies used in TA1–4
T6.3.3	Define core requirements for object data and best practices
T6.3.4	Suggest mappings of metadata, ontologies and vocabularies
User stories for M6.3	ID 10, ID 14, ID 19, ID 32, ID 36, ID 94, ID 95, ID 96, ID 34; ID 35; ID 42, ID 43, ID 68, ID 92, ID 93, ID 47, ID 85
TRAILS related with M6.3	The tasks in M6.3 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M6.3	ID 22, ID 25, ID 30, ID 34, ID 53, ID 60, ID 76, ID 80, ID 83, ID 84

M6.4 Objects in context: modelling the interdisciplinary research cycle on objects – 6.5 N4O will create an integrated knowledge base about objects, which will be represented in a knowledge graph implemented in RDF, based on the N4O Core Ontology. TA6 will design the N4O ontology based on existing models, in particular CIDOC-CRM. It will analyse the data and metadata used in TAs 1–6 based on the inventories created in M6.3 and define a core ontology based on these.

TA6 will also collect the needs originating in research on object data to develop a query pattern. A prototype ontology will be implemented in WissKI to enable researchers outside archaeology to integrate objects into their research strategies and enrich the object biographies with their research results. This measure will be conducted in close cooperation with TA5 and with NFDI4Memory, to ensure that the data model aligns with data models based on the needs of historical research.

Tasks in M6.4	
T6.4.1	Create an overview of existing approaches to modelling objects in OWL
T6.4.2	Design the N4O Core Ontology
T6.4.3	Design query patterns to enable interdisciplinary research by allowing simple and tailored queries
T6.4.4	Implement the prototype of the N4O Core Ontology
User stories for M6.4	ID 10, ID 14, ID 19, ID 32, ID 36, ID 94, ID 95, ID 96, ID 34, ID 36, ID 35, ID 42, ID 43, ID 68, ID 92, ID 93, ID 94, ID 47, ID 85
TRAILS related with M6.4	The tasks in M6.4 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M6.4	This measure is a cross TA 1–4 activity and will involve all participants with expertise in data modelling and metadata.

M6.5 Commons contribution and coordination – G6.1, G6.2, G6.3, G6.4, G6.5 The aim of this measure is knowledge transfer concerning qualification and training as well as overarching metadata on the object research lifecycle (N4O Objectives 4, 5). Through its incorporation into the Coordination Office (TA7), it ensures dovetailing with the activities in the consortium as a whole. Moreover, TA6 will share knowledge with other consortia, in particular with NFDI4Culture and NFDI4Memory on training and qualification. For this purpose, the following services will be improved and/or implemented:

- Collection of written output by entering documentation, best practices, guidelines, workflows and evaluation reports in the N4O Commons, coordinated and maintained by TA7 (T2.4.2)
- Active implementation of advisory and support services via the central helpdesk
- Supporting the coordination of the consortium and its governance bodies

Tasks in M6.5	
T6.5.1	Build community and support CCs and TWGs
T6.5.2	Develop and pilot training concepts
T6.5.3	Coordinate knowledge transfer between consortia
User stories for M6.5	ID 42, ID 44, ID 45, ID 48
TRAILS related with M6.5	The tasks in M6.5 are anchored in the permanent work programme and accompany all TRAILS, also those of the other TAs.
Participants in M6.5	ID 1, ID 6, ID 11, ID 19, ID 29, ID 44, ID 48, ID 50, ID 56, ID 57

5.6.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA6

ID	Description
KPI6.3.3	By mid-2027, tangible foundations for complete digital description of object biographies are developed; their applicability and potential for new, innovative research questions are demonstrated by four use cases.
KPI6.4.1	Throughout the duration of the consortium (2022–2026), annual NFDI conferences are held to coordinate which properties and contextual information of an object are relevant for the heterogeneous research interests of the community.
KPI6.4.2	By mid-2026, a proposal model object biography, as well as the vocabularies and authority file used to describe them, will be included in the N4O Commons.
KPI6.4.3	By mid-2026, an ObjectCore data model based on the object biography is used by members of the N4O Consortium in their respective systems or as a reference implementation in the core services of N4O.
KPI6.5.1	By 2027, the competence framework is formulated and available for updating in the Commons.
KPI6.5.2	From 2023 to mid-2024, qualification profiles are derived from the competence framework based on the technical work in TA1–4.
KPI6.5.3	By the end of 2025, materials for initial training and continuing professional development are developed in accordance with the qualification profiles.
KPI6.5.4	From 2024 on, N4O actively supports 6 RDM training measures per year.
KPI6.5.5	By mid-2027, the competence framework is included in the curricula of two study programmes.
KPI6.5.6	From 2023, materials for continuing professional development are available in the N4O Commons, as a basis for self-study, for development and for independent integration into teaching formats.

5.6.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

TA6 works closely with TA7, particularly on developing incentive systems and on implementing and optimising governance processes. TAs 1–5 cooperate closely with TA6 in M6.5 to coordinate regarding qualification, relevant RDM methods, the establishment of transparent and participative N4O Commons processes, as well as an overarching conceptual reference frame for the biography of objects and the development of an ObjectCore data model.

5.7 Task Area 7: Support and Coordination

Co-applicant institution	Co-spokesperson
German Archaeological Institute, Head Office Berlin	Philipp von Rummel

5.7.1 Brief description and aims

TA7 ensures efficient operation of the consortium with smooth and collaborative governance processes that represent the diversity of the community and promote gender balance. TA7 is the backbone of the N4O Coordination Office (CO) and is in charge of the integrated helpdesk service, administrative and technical coordination (G7.7, N4O Objective 8) TA7 provides advice and coordination structures for the whole consortium; it is therefore essential that all TAs participate. Building on established structures such as the Berlin-Leipzig Declaration and the Memorandum group (NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+, NFDI4Objects), TA7 collaborates on cross-cutting topics in NFDI, and provides robust technical management to enable convergence of infrastructural approaches across the entire N4O (G7.1, N4O Objective 8, 9).

In addition to embedding N4O in the structure of the entire NFDI, TA7 is dedicated to shaping the structure and content of the whole consortium. N4O is supported by professional associations with high membership numbers. Community management measures and structures created in TA7 will make it as easy as possible for participants to contribute actively with minimum workload. The CO can rely on expert support from participants and co-applicants in answering legal and ethical questions relevant to the N4O Community. Questions include technical implementation of software to automate extraction of licence, legal and provenance information, e.g. using FDO. The consortium is committed to the FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles; TA7 will raise awareness among our members on these issues (G7.6, N4O Objective 2). In this regard, TA7 empowers researchers to manage their FAIR data and will create structures to increase RDM capacities and competencies (G7.4, N4O Objective 6). TA7 fosters sustainable research- and community-driven development of the consortium (G7.3, N4O Objective 5). To that end, incentive systems and admission processes will enable future participation in N4O: in TA7, efficient, committed involvement in NFDI working groups will ensure knowledge transfer (G7.2, N4O Objective 6). TA7 will develop and implement specific measures to establish and consolidate N4O's international relations in Europe and beyond (G7.5, N4O Objective 7). With regard to N4O's RDM strategy, TA7 is responsible for organisational, technical integration and dealing with overarching issues. By coordinating support services and the helpdesk (see section 4.4), TA7 significantly contributes to the acceptance of N4O services in the community. TA7's task is to ensure transparent, demand-led, largely redundancy-free and sustainable development of complex, software-based systems within the consortium. Quality assurance, user and community feedback will factor heavily in the development of these services. With these activities, TA7 will contribute to the community work and FAIRification of data associated with N4O.

5.7.2 Goals of TA7

Goal	Description
G7.1	Establish consortium operations, governance processes and technical management to ensure diversity and gender balance of active participants in the consortium.
G7.2	Engage N4O in the sections of the NFDI by promoting and moderating joint NFDI infrastructures and establishing evaluation processes to boost exchange of expertise, particularly between the humanities and sciences.
G7.3	Encourage science- and community-driven development of N4O and ensure its collaborative governance and sustainability.
G7.4	Establish and consolidate N4O's international relations in Europe and worldwide to create synergies and international embedding.
G7.5	Direct and develop ethical guidelines in line with FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles to raise awareness among the community.
G7.6	Coordinate a community-oriented organisational structure.

5.7.3 Measures and tasks in TA7

M7.1 Administrative coordination (CO) – G7.1, G7.3 The DAI has a wealth of experience in dealing with (inter)national consortium projects, so N4O is able to handle recruitment procedures quickly and award permanent contracts, thus avoiding constant loss of expertise. The CO, based at the DAI Head Office, is responsible for professional and corporate administration of N4O and implements the integrated coordination, governance model (section 3.4 and section 5.6, TA6) and internal evaluation processes. Each TA will be provided with a ½ FTE position belonging to TA7 to ensure smooth running of administrative processes as well as to integrate and supervise services (M7.5) in TA7. These positions will coordinate processes between all TAs and co-applicants and ensure long-term acceptance within the community and sustainability of N4O services. To this end, it is essential to direct, respect and adhere to the process for admitting new consortium participants and for integrating new and innovative contributions from their users in accordance with the statutes of the NFDI e.V. and the regulations derived from it for N4O (see section 3.5).

Incentive systems implemented through TA7 will motivate both early career researchers (ECR) and established scholars to generate research data according to N4O guidelines (see section 3.4). Similarly, continuing professional development and diversity measures will promote qualification of the N4O Community at all educational levels, through the N4O governance body and processes like recruitment, lecture programmes, management of working groups, RDM mentoring by women for women, family-friendly working, prioritising digital meetings over travelling, or enabling part-time jobs.

Tasks in M7.1	
T7.1.1	Develop a virtual workspace and staff a functioning CO for N4O at the main applicant institution
T7.1.2	Coordinate and control financial flows, contract management and their reporting
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Tasks in M7.1	
T7.1.3	Ensure diversity and gender balance among consortium staff and roles in CCs, AB and GA
T7.1.4	Establish structures for exchange on cross-cutting topics and their specification with other consortia and sections in NFDI e.V.
T7.1.5	Implement integrated public relations for N4O, including corporate design and targeted advertisements through appropriate communication channels and participation in events to promote NFDI content to the professional community
T7.1.6	Design and implement incentive systems for use of N4O services and NFDI guidelines fostering the cultural change in RDM (selection process and criteria for awarding Flex Funds in M7.1)
T7.1.7	Manage the internal evaluation of the N4O programme in year 2, to optimise the work of the consortium (see section 3.1)
T7.1.8	Develop a sustainability concept and exit strategy for N4O

M7.2 N4O Helpdesk and website – G7.3, G7.7 TA7 sees its role as providing the first point of contact, not only for internal consortium issues and the N4O Community but for the entire RDM target group. The helpdesk, integrated into the CO (see M7.1) and accessible to all users via a website, will provide constant low-threshold support to our community. TA7 undertakes to record and monitor user behaviour and feedback to ensure the sustainability of the helpdesk and website. As a result, community acceptance will enable the necessary agility in the ecosystem of the nascent NFDI. The measure comprises planning, implementation, management, and sustainable operation of a website as a single point of entry for users to access all of N4O's services and resources. The website is coordinated centrally through TA7, while content is contributed and maintained by the TAs. The measure will make N4O's content and services available in international infrastructures.

Tasks in M7.2	
T7.2.1	Conceptualise, develop and implement an open N4O website with a central helpdesk
T7.2.2	Establish a workflow to collect and consolidate community and user requests to the central helpdesk and make them available to the whole community
T7.2.3	Implement the helpdesk, providing advice and assistance on RDM to the N4O Community
T7.2.4	Advise on legal tasks, supported by the legal departments of the co-applicant institutions (and those of other consortia, e.g. NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Earth, FAIRAgro) and on technical implementations for software to automate extraction of licence, legal and provenance information
T7.2.5	Monitor and evaluate user activity on helpdesk and assess learning progress through regular community surveys
User stories for M7.2	ID 64, ID 91
Participants in M7.2	ID 01, ID 36

M7.3 Governance processes and N4O Commons – G7.1, G7.2, G7.3 This measure bundles all the governance processes of N4O (sections 3.4 and 3.5). It comprises establishing structures in the community to develop a shared knowledge commons based on the FAIR principles. The contents of the N4O Commons are developed and maintained in a participatory manner with quality assurance (section 3.4.4). This includes the CO actively supporting the work of TWGs and CCs. TA7 regularly organises knowledge transfer and networking with stakeholders within and beyond the consortium. The measure serves to strengthen networking within N4O, e.g. on methodological issues and data technology requirements, while building bridges to professional communities in other NFDI consortia. It is immaterial in this context whether the dialogue partners are data or service providers or users. Facilitating compliance with FAIR and CARE principles is one key area of collaboration with other NFDI consortia. Through the engagement of participants in decolonisation and critical heritage debates, N4O can make an important contribution to connect these topics with RDM.

Tasks in M7.3	
T7.3.1	Coordinate CCs and TWGs to offer low-threshold meetings to the community
T7.3.2	Define content criteria for N4O Commons as a regulatory framework for consortium work
T7.3.3	Direct and monitor the development of ethical guidelines to respect FAIR and CARE principles as a contribution to the N4O Commons valuable for the entire NFDI
T7.3.4	Develop a Commons section on the N4O website
T7.3.5	Support the workflow and implementation for Commons documents
User stories for M7.3	ID 14, ID 19, ID 20, ID 35, ID 40, ID 42, ID 47, ID 65, ID 66, ID 67, ID 95, ID 96
Participants in M7.3	ID 01, ID 05, ID 14

M7.4 Service integration and supervision – G7.2, G7.4 M7.4 is part of the CO and oversees the technical coordination of the consortium’s work programme. The development of complex software systems for a large number of stakeholders inevitably leads to redundancies, planning errors and conflicting objectives. Modern software development is based on different models, which serve to identify these problems in good time and avoid costly erroneous developments. TA7 aims to achieve best practice in software development and its integration into consortium partners’ information systems. Since the user and programmer communities of the consortium only overlap to a limited degree, this requires TA7 to plan intensively in time. TA7 will also provide advisory services on “hard” technical decisions, concerning file formats or database technologies, and on “soft” planning factors, such as compatible high-level concepts or the definition of interfaces and documentation methods. TA7’s task is to ensure transparent, demand-led, largely redundancy-free and sustainable complex, software-based systems for N4O.

Tasks in M7.4	
T7.4.1	Establish transparent and community-based processes to identify conflict between different N4O services and products
T7.4.2	Develop processes and guidelines for redundancy-free and sustainable system integration (software, formats, interfaces)
T7.4.3	Manage the workflow for integrating new contributions and services into N4O
T7.4.4	Support decision-making processes and the technical implementation of best practice and development models
T7.	Ensure interface compatibility for technical convergence and sustainable structures
Participants in M7.4	ID 05

5.7.4 Key Performance Indicators for TA7

ID	Description
KPI7.1.1	At the end of 2021, diversity and gender balance is established in the steering board.
KPI7.1.2	At the end of 2023, diversity and gender balance is established in the CC, EC, AB and GA.
KPI7.1.3	By mid-2023, scientific, service integration and coordination roles are assigned respecting diversity and gender balance.
KPI7.2.1	By early 2023, the Memorandum group members have been contacted to form a working group.
KPI7.2.3	Twice yearly in 2023–2027, working groups meet to coordinate cross-cutting topics based on the Berlin-Leipzig Declaration.
KPI7.3.1	Yearly in 2023–2027, the GA meets to decide on consortium-related topics.
KPI7.3.2	In 2023 and 2025, two NFDI retreats ensure smooth cooperation within the N4O team.
KPI7.4.1	By the end of 2023, a process of allocating grants for ECRs and students to encourage data sharing is established.
KPI7.4.2	Yearly in 2023–2027, 10 grants enable ECRs and students to join workshops on data literacy and encourage FAIR data production.
KPI7.5.1	Throughout the duration of the consortium, the AB will consist of at least 50% international advisors.
KPI7.5.2	Yearly in 2023–2027, N4O members will join at least one (inter)national RDM conference to engage with international RDM scholars worldwide.
KPI7.6.1	Yearly in 2023–2027, (with TA6) an Annual N4O Conference with groups and features concerning FAIR, TRUST and CARE principles are organised and advertised to the community.
KPI7.6.2	By mid-2024, information on FAIR, TRUST and CARE principles are available on the N4O Commons.
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ID	Description
KPI7.6.3	Throughout the duration of the consortium, its activities are promoted via social media, professional associations, N4O web presence and networking to reach the relevant community.
KPI7.7.1	By early 2023, an accessible helpdesk for N4O is established.
KPI7.7.2	In early 2024 and early 2026, internal audits ensure anonymised feedback on N4O's work.
KPI7.7.3	In mid-2024 and mid-2026, two surveys ensure anonymised feedback on N4O's work.

5.7.5 Cooperation with other Task Areas and cross-area dependencies

TA7 interacts closely with all other consortium TAs. There are particularly close links with TAs 1–5 on service integration with regard to management, advisory input and implementation of conflict resolution strategies. TA6 and 7 collaborate closely, especially on developing incentive systems and continuing professional development (M7.1 and M7.3), as well as on implementing and optimising governance processes. The CO established in TA7 is available to all TAs as a service provider and advice centre for administrative, legal and technical questions. All co-applicant institutions join in operating the CO (M7.1, see section 3.4.2).

6 Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Complete Designation
AAT	Getty Arts & Architecture Thesaurus® Online
AB	Advisory Board
ABCD	Access to Biological Collections Data Ontology
ADABweb	Allgemeine Denkmaldatenbank webbasiert (General web based heritage database)
ADS	Archaeology Data Service
AdW	Akademie der Wissenschaften und Literatur, Mainz (Academy of Sciences and Literature, Mainz)
AdWH	Heidelberger Akademie der Wissenschaften (Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities)
AIP	Archival Information Package
AMH	Archaeological Museum Hamburg
ARIADNE	Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe
ARS3D	African Red Slip Ware Digital Project
ASM	Bavarian State Archaeological Collection Museum for Prehistoric and Early Medieval Archaeology
AVS	Authority File and Vocabulary Services
BA	Bachelor of Arts
BARTOC	Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies and Classifications
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BBAW	Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum (CIL), Corpus Nummorum, Inscriptiones Graecae
BBT	Backbone Thesaurus
BCDH	Bonn Center for Digital Humanities
BerGSAS	Freie Universität Berlin (Free University of Berlin), Berlin Graduate School of Ancient Studies
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (Federal Ministry of Education and Research)
CAA	Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (Association)
CAA-DE	Computeranwendungen und quantitative Methoden in der Archäologie (CAA) e V. (German Chapter of the CAA - Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology Association)
CAD	Computer-aided design
CARE	CARE-Principles: Collective Benefit - Authority to Control - Responsibility - Ethics
CAU	Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel (Kiel University)
CC	Community Cluster
CCA-BW	Competence Center Archaeometry Baden-Württemberg
CEZA	Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie (Curt Engelhorn Archaeometry Center)
CIDOC	Comité international pour la documentation de conseil international des musées (International Committee for Documentation of the International Council of Museums)
CIDOC-CRM	Conceptual Reference Model (by CIDOC)
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CO	Coordination Office
CONA	Cultural Objects Name Authority
CORDH	Consortium for Open Research Data in the Humanities
COSCH	Colour and Space in Cultural Heritage (COST Action)
CRoS	Catalogue and Registry Services
CS3DP	Community Standards for 3D Data Preservation
DAI	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (German Archaeological Institute)
DANS	Dutch Data Archiving and Networked Services
DANTE	Datendrehscheibe für Normdaten und Terminologien (Data hub for norm data and terminologies)
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DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DArV	Deutscher Archäologenverband (German Archaeological Association)
DaS	Data Services
dASIS	Distributed Archaeological Site Information System (RGZM project)
DASV	Dachverband Archäologischer Studierendenvertretungen (Umbrella association of German archaeological student representatives)
DBM	Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum (German Mining Museum)
DBV	Deutsche Bibliotheksverband (German Library Association)
DGG	Deutsche Geophysikalische Gesellschaft (German Geophysics Association)
DGUF	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Ur- und Frühgeschichte (German Society for Pre- and Protohistory)
DINI	Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e.V. (German Initiative for Networked Information)
DiS	Discovery Services
DMB	Deutscher Museumsbund (German Museum Association)
DNB	Deutsche Nationalbibliothek (German National Library)
DOG	Deutsche Orient-Gesellschaft (German Oriental Society)
DVA	Deutscher Verband für Archäologie (German Association for Archaeology)
EAC	Europae Archaeologiae Consilium
ECR	Early-Career Researchers
EDM	Europeana Data Model
EFG	Extension For Geosciences
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FAU	IZdigital Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Interdisciplinary Centre for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences
FISH	Forum on Information Standards in Heritage
FDO	FAIR Digital Objects
FIZ	Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur, Karlsruhe (Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure)
FTE	Full time equivalent
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GA	General Assembly
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GBV	Gemeinsamer Bibliotheksverbund (Common Library Network)
GDA	Generaldirektion der Staatlichen Archive Bayerns (Bavarian State Archives)
GDCh	Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker, Fachgruppe Analytische Chemie (Division of Analytical Chemistry of the German Chemical Society)
GDI-DE	Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland (Geodata infrastructure Germany)
GDKE	Generaldirektion Kulturelles Erbe Rheinland-Pfalz (General Management of Cultural Heritage in Rhineland-Palatinate)
GfA	Gesellschaft für Anthropologie (Association for Anthropology)
GHGA	German Human Genome-Phenome Archive
GIS	Geographisches Informationssystem (Geographic Information System)
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
GNAA	Gesellschaft für Naturwissenschaftliche Archäologie (Society for Scientific Archaeology)
GND	Gemeinsame Normdatei der DNB (Integrated Authority File)
GND4C	GND für Kulturdaten (Integrated Authority File for Cultural Data)
GPI	Getty Provenance Index®
GVK	Gemeinsamer Verbundkatalog (Common Union Catalogue)
hA	hessenARCHÄOLOGIE, Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Hessen
HAUM	Herzog Anton Ulrich Museum, Braunschweig
HAWK	Hornemann Institut der Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaft und Kunst Hildesheim / Holzminden / Göttingen (Hornemann Institute of the University of Applied Sciences und Arts Hildesheim / Holzminden / Göttingen)
HZK	Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany at the Helmholtz-Zentrum für Kulturtechnik der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
ICOM	International Council of Museums
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IntS	Interoperable Data Set Services
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
ISIL	International Standard Identifier for Libraries and Related Organizations
IZdigital	Interdisziplinäres Zentrum für digitale Geistes- und Sozialwissenschaften, Erlangen (Interdisciplinary Centre for Digital Humanities and Social Sciences)
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JGU-IKM	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Institute for the History of Arts and Musicology
JGU-ECSG	Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, Efficient Computing and Storage Group
KENOM	Kooperative Erschließung und Nutzung der Objektdaten von Münzsammlungen (Cooperative indexing and use of object data of coin collections)
KDWT	Centre for Heritage Conservation Studies and Techniques
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAD-SA	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie Sachsen-Anhalt, Landesmuseum für Vorgeschichte, Halle (Saale) (State Office for Heritage Management and Archaeology of Saxony-Anhalt, State Museum of Prehistory in Halle (Saale))
LAD-Saar	Landesdenkmalamt Saarland (State Office for Heritage Management of the Saarland)
LAD Th	Thüringisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege und Archäologie (State Office for Heritage Management and Archaeology of Thuringia)
LAD-BW	Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Baden-Württemberg (Heritage Management Office of Baden-Württemberg)
LADO	Linked Open Archaeological Data Ontology
LCCN	Library of Congress Control Number
LIDO	Lightweight Information Describing Objects
LOD	Linked Open Data
LO(U)D	Linked Open (Usable) Data
LTA	Long-Term Archiving
LVA	Landschaftsverband Rheinland
LVR-ABR	LVR-Amt für Bodendenkmalpflege im Rheinland (LVR State Service for Archaeological Heritage)
LWL-MfA	LWL-Museum für Archäologie, Westfälisches Landesmuseum, Herne (LWL Archaeological Museum, Westphalian State Museum)
MA	Master of Arts
MfN	Museum für Naturkunde (Museum of Natural Science) – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MPI-EVA	Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Department of Archaeogenetics in Leipzig
MPIWG	Max Planck Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science)
MUAS	Mainz University of Applied Sciences
M2M	Machine-to-Machine Interface
NFDI-RDC	NFDI Research Data Commons Platform
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NihK	Niedersächsische Institut für historische Küstenforschung (Lower Saxony Institute for Historical Coastal Research)
NLD	Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Projekt “Denkmalatlas Niedersachsen” (State Office for Heritage Management of Lower Saxony, Project “Monuments Atlas Lower Saxony”)
NLM	Niedersächsische Landesmuseum Hannover, Das WeltenMuseum (Lower Saxony State Museum, The WorldMuseum)
N4O	NFDI4Objects
NTM	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Lab Non-Textual Materials
NUDS	Numismatic Description Schema
NUMID	Netzwerk universitärer Münzsammlungen in Deutschland (Network of university coin collections in Germany)
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OER	Open Educational Resources
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PaS	Process as a Service
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PID	Persistent Identifier
QuaS	Qualification Services
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDC	Research Data Commons
RDM	Research Data Management
RGK	Römisch-Germanische Kommission des DAI
RGZM	Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum Leibniz-Forschungsinstitut für Archäologie (RGZM Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology)
ROCEEH	The Role of Culture in Early Expansion of Humans (Research Project)
RUB	Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften (Ruhr University Bochum, Institute of Archaeological Studies)
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen, Lehrstuhl für Architekturgeschichte (RWTH Aachen University, Chair of Architectural History)
SAPM	Staatssammlung für Anthropologie und Paläoanatomie, München (State Collection for Anthropology and Palaeoanatomy, Munich)
SAS	Software Application Services
SC	Steering Committee
SEADDA	Saving Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age
SIP	Submission Information Package
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SNSB	Staatssammlung für Anthropologie und Paläoanatomie München, Bavarian Natural History Collections (Bavarian State Collection for Anthropology and Palaeoanatomy)
SP	Spokesperson
SPK	Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz (Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation)
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
StoS	Storage Services
SUB	Georg-August-Universität Göttingen (University of Göttingen), Göttingen State and University Library
SuS	Support Services
TB	Terabyte
tDAR	the Digital Archaeological Record
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographical Names® Online
TRAIL	Task-Related Activities for the Implementation and Launch of services
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User Community, Sustainability, Technology
ThULB	Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek (Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Thuringian University and State Library)
TUB-DP	Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Art History, Chair of Digital Provenance
TUB-IURP	Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Urban and Regional Planning
TUBr	Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institut für Geschichtswissenschaft
TUD	Technische Universität Darmstadt (Technical University of Darmstadt), Department of Classical Archaeology, Faculty of Architecture
TWG	Temporary Working Group
UAS-MW	Hochschule Mittweida (Mittweida University of Applied Sciences), Faculty Applied Computer Sciences & Biosciences
UB	Universitätsbibliothek (university library)
UBA	Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg (University of Bamberg), Institute for Archaeology, Heritage Conservation and Art History
UBH	Universität Heidelberg (Heidelberg University), Heidelberg University Library, Department Publikationsdienste, FID Propylaeum Classics
UBN	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (University of Bonn)
UFG	Ur- und Frühgeschichte (Pre- and protohistory)
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UFZ	Helmholtz-Zentrum Umweltforschung, Department Monitoring- und Erkundungstechnologien (Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Monitoring and Exploration Technologies)
UHA	Universität Hamburg, Institut für Archäologie und Kulturgeschichte des antiken Mittelmeerraumes
UHE	Universität Heidelberg (Heidelberg University), Heidelberg Centre for Cultural Heritage, Institut für Klassische und Byzantinische Archäologie
ULAN	Getty Union List of Artist Names® Online
UL	Ägyptisches Museum Georg Steindorff, Universität Leipzig (Georg Steindorff Egyptian Museum, Leipzig University)
UTU	University of Tübingen, eScience Centre
UzK-CoDArchLab	CoDArchLab University of Cologne, Institute for Archaeology, Cologne Digital Archaeology Laboratory
UzK-DCH	DCH University of Cologne, Data Centre for the Humanities and Cologne Centre for eHumanities
UzK-DDH	DDH University of Cologne, Department for Digital Humanities
VARUS	VARUSSCHLACHT im Osnabrücker Land gGmbH – Museum und Park Kalkriese
VIAF	Virtual International Authority File
VLA	Verband der Landesarchäologen in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland (Association of the State Archaeologists of the Federal Republic of Germany)
VZG	Verbundzentrale des Gemeinsamen Bibliotheksverbundes (GBV) der Länder (Central Network Office of the Joint Library Network of the German federal states)
ZBSA	Zentrum für Baltische und Skandinavische Archäologie in der Stiftung Schleswig-Holsteinische Landesmuseen Schloss Gottorf (Centre for Baltic and Scandinavian Archaeology in the Schleswig-Holstein State Museums Foundation Schloss Gottorf)

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